

Towards a Green Economy in the Mediterranean

Assessment of National Green Economy and Sustainable Development
Strategies in Mediterranean Countries

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Foreword

The Mediterranean region is widely recognised as one of the world's most sensitive environmental, political, social, economic and cultural hotspots. Unique, yet fragile natural ecosystems are severely – and sometimes irreversibly – damaged by human activity; valuable resources are depleted, with water scarcity majorly exacerbated by increasing climate variability; urban sprawl and pollution levels continuing to be on the rise. Together with political and social unrest, leading to instability and armed conflicts, these pressures have forced populations to relocate resulting in one of the worst humanitarian crises since the Second World War. In addition, the impacts of the global economic recession have been hard felt on the economies of the region with stagnation, low competitiveness, high unemployment rates, and further marginalisation of women and youth. The huge economic inequalities within and between countries still remain and feed into the vicious circle of political and social unrest, impeding a peaceful and inclusive development of the Mediterranean region.

Of course there is no “one-size fits all” solution that could magically tackle all these complex and inter-connected issues. Each country, region and community is different, faces specific challenges and has varying gaps and needs to address. However, the emergence of the Green Economy concept, as coined at the global Rio+20 Sustainable Development summit, is a serious attempt to promote a more inclusive and environmentally-friendly economic development at both global and local level with a high potential, if applied properly, of reducing social inequalities, enhancing the quality of life and well-being of communities on both the northern and southern shores of the Mediterranean.

In this report, we first describe the Green Economy approach and other sustainability-related concepts and frameworks. Then we identify and examine major Green Economy and Sustainable Development initiatives and actors at international and Mediterranean levels. A description of the methodology and findings of the study (overall and country specific) follows, comprising the main part of document. Complementary information on financing issues has been included before closing with a set of recommendations that if implemented can significantly boost a greener and more inclusive economy in the Mediterranean region.

This report is an initiative of dedicated civil society organizations aiming solely to boost the transition towards a green and fair economy in the region. Earlier versions have been widely shared and openly discussed in an effort to be as inclusive and participatory as possible. The authors cannot dare claim to have evaluated the status of *all* environmental, social and economic indicators of the Mediterranean countries. It focuses primarily on the assessment of *existing strategies that are publicly available and accessible* and on the opinions and perceptions of key Green Economy and Sustainability practitioners in order to give a good indication of each country's direction and rate of progress towards achieving sustainable development.

We hope that this report, supported by the MAVA Foundation and co-led by eco-union, MIO-ECSDE and the Green Economy Coalition, will mobilise a participative, rich and evidence-based public debate on the transition towards a Green Economy and contribute to an inclusive, peaceful and sustainable Mediterranean region.

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Table of contents

Foreword	2
Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	5
Green Economy and Sustainable Development Concepts	5
Gaining insight from stakeholders	5
Assessment of national strategies in the Mediterranean	5
Financing Green Economy	6
Recommendations to catalyse and mainstream Green Economy in the Mediterranean	6
Conclusion	7
1 Green Economy: Concepts, approaches, stakeholders	9
1.1 Overview of Green Economy concepts and actors	9
1.2 Other concepts and initiatives related to Green Economy	17
1.3 Approach taken in this study	25
1.4 Mediterranean stakeholders and initiatives promoting Green Economy	26
2 A quick-survey of Green Economy in the Mediterranean	32
2.1 Methodology	32
2.2 Profile of respondents	33
2.3 Concepts, definitions and perceptions on implementation	35
2.4 Brown economy	42
3 Assessment of published national strategies in the Mediterranean	44
3.1 Overall methodology	44
3.2 Limitations of the methodological approach	45
3.3 Overview of national strategies' assessment	45
3.4 Country profile indicators	53
4 Country assessment details	56
4.1 Albania	56
4.2 Algeria	58
4.3 Bosnia and Herzegovina	60
4.4 Croatia	62
4.5 Cyprus	64
4.6 Egypt	66
4.7 France	68
4.8 Greece	70
4.9 Israel	72
4.10 Italy	74
4.11 Jordan	76
4.12 Lebanon	78
4.13 Malta	80
4.14 Montenegro	82
4.15 Morocco	84
4.16 Palestine	86
4.17 Portugal	88
4.18 Slovenia	90
4.19 Spain	92
4.20 Tunisia	94
4.21 Turkey	96

5 Financing Green Economy	98
5.1 Introduction	98
5.2 Review of financial actors	99
5.3 International financial frameworks, tools and initiatives	101
5.4 Climate finance	103
5.5 Examples of national strategies	105
5.6 Women's access to finance	106
5.7 Recommendations	107
6 Recommendations and conclusions	109
6.1 Design ambitious, coherent and consistent national strategies	109
6.2 Improve awareness, commitment and involvement	110
6.3 Phase out Brown Economy, mainstream Green Finance and enhance Green Economy implementation	111
6.4 Conclusions	112
7 References	113
7.1 References for the Chapter on GE concepts	113
7.2 References and links for the Chapter on the country assessments	114
7.3 References for Chapter on Financing	120

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results of a review exercise covering Green Economy (GE) strategies and Sustainable Development (SD) policies in almost all Mediterranean countries. An extensive literature review was conducted over a three-month period followed by a methodological assessment of the findings which was complemented by an on-line survey addressed to key regional and national GE/SD actors that brought in useful insights on what is happening on the ground in the countries. Based on these findings and the valuable inputs of an expert workshop that took place in Morocco (Tangier, 20 July 2016) this document proposes a number of concrete recommendations that aim to accelerate the much needed transition towards a Green Economy in the Mediterranean region.

Green Economy and Sustainable Development Concepts

Several green economy and sustainable development concepts and initiatives have been developed and promoted at global and regional level. The study briefly presents those more relevant to the Mediterranean region, mainly coming from major Intergovernmental Organizations such as the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the European Union, but also from other bodies such as the Green Economy Coalition (GEC), the Global Green Growth Institute, the Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation and others.

The Green Economy approach opted by the authors is the one supported by the GEC and most civil society organizations, where a green economy vision should be conceived and implemented through communities' and stakeholders' engagement. This model, based on the core principle of equity, accountability and sufficiency, requires bottom-up dialogue processes and participative policy design. It does not intend to only mitigate specific environmental damages but rather to radically reform all economic and financial sectors in order to eliminate negative externalities and guarantee prosperity for all, within ecological limits.

Gaining insight from stakeholders

The authors were from the very beginning fully aware that national GE/SD strategies and policies being in place is one thing but if they are actually implemented is quite another. Given therefore that the current study, due to finite resources, could not extend into assessing the *implementation* of existing GE/SD strategies, policies and initiatives, an on-line survey was designed and sent to regional and national GE/SD stakeholders and practitioners in order to gain some insight on what is actually happening in the countries. The results from more than 300 respondents clearly show that countries are not ambitious enough.

National governments, businesses and local authorities are seen as the main GE/SD drivers by the majority of the respondents. However, their level of commitment (including the financial sector) is seen as either low or medium, requiring therefore a much higher dedication to the GE/SD vision and goal to meet expectations. The main identified barriers to progress are the weak commitment of public authorities, poor political and technical capacity and lack of the necessary financial instruments.

The energy sector as well as agriculture, tourism, waste and water management are seen as the sectors most relevant to Green Economy. Only half of the respondents can say for sure that there is a national strategy on GE or SD in their country, showing weak communication tactics of the public authorities on the issue. In the cases where strategies exist, the prevailing opinion of the respondents is moderate. At regional level, only one third of respondents is aware of relevant regional GE/SD policy frameworks (such as the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development, of the Regional Plan on Sustainable Production and Consumption), while almost 20% even say that there is none, which again signifies weak communication and dissemination of progress achieved in the region on mainstreaming GE and SD. The regional status of GE/SD is seen by those who do know about it, to be fair or weak, with a large margin for improvement.

Assessment of national strategies in the Mediterranean

The main part of this study focuses on the review of published and accessible national strategies on Green Economy and Sustainability. The methodology used to assess these national strategies, policies and initiatives followed four steps: i) identification of relevant national strategies, policies and initiatives through literature research; ii) description/presentation of what is written; iii) assessment of what is written; and iv) conducting the above-mentioned region-wide survey in order to get feedback on what is actually being done.

The large majority of the countries have out-dated or incomplete national GE/SD strategies. Often they are vague, not giving clear definitions or indicators. Only five countries (France, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Tunisia) can claim to have good, up-to-date and detailed strategies with clear indicators, or – in the case of Italy – supporting legislation in place. Seven countries (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Cyprus, Egypt, Slovenia and Spain) have outdated GE/SD strategies or none at all. The rest of the Mediterranean countries (Algeria, Croatia, Greece, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Malta, Montenegro, Palestine and Turkey) are somewhere in between these two groups of countries.

The following figure gives an overview of the status of the assessed countries.

Financing Green Economy

The study presents different green financing definitions, barriers, flows and institutions active in the Mediterranean region. Specific focus on women's access to finance is also included. The brief analysis made suggests that public finance, regulations and policies all play an important role in attracting and mobilizing private investment into Green Economy. However, estimating green financial flows is complex due to lack of aggregated data. As a result, the evaluation effort focuses mainly on renewable energy and climate finance. There are opportunities to gain insight from the climate financing experience that can help shift such patterns of green inclusive growth to other Green Economy sectors.

Recommendations to catalyse and mainstream Green Economy in the Mediterranean

The report includes main overall findings and proposes recommendations on how to accelerate Green Economy happening at national and regional level based on the findings of the country strategies' assessment and the survey results.

Recommendation 1: Design ambitious, coherent and consistent national strategies

- **Align and mainstream Green Economy/Sustainable Development concepts:** The concept of GE/SD is interpreted differently by countries and bodies where often the economy is given priority over societal and environmental issues. Country policies and strategies have to express more clearly their interpretation of Sustainable Development and Green Economy concepts, based on recognized international standards, international agreements and scientific literature. The core principles of social equity, community ownership and ecological limits, should form the basis to build national Green Economies. Additionally, the Mediterranean countries must put emphasis on sustainable *coastal* and *marine* related sectors and activities such as Tourism and Fisheries, or Building and Transport in view of foreseen coastal population increase, etc.
- **Clearly formulate objectives, actions and indicators:** It is important that the countries improve their national strategies, through participatory consultations, to have a common vision, specific objectives and well defined course of action and commitments regarding GE and SD. All countries should have clearly formulated (on a consensus basis) targets, actions and indicators in order to monitor the progress of implementation, through (bi)annual reviews and open data sharing processes easily accessible and understandable by stakeholders and citizens.
- **Integrate new international commitments:** All countries should review and update their strategies and policies in light of these new international commitments. Objectives, actions and indicators linked to the SDGs, the MSSD (2016-20125) and Climate Change commitments should be integrated into national sustainability strategies. For the majority of countries this would mean to set more ambitious and concrete targets which have to be meticulously tracked with consistent and coherent monitoring processes, together with supporting finance and implementation mechanisms.

Recommendation 2: Improve awareness, commitment and involvement

- **Raise awareness about national and regional sustainability strategies:** Countries need to put more effort in communicating and disseminating national GE/SD strategies to all relevant stakeholders, including economic actors and opinion leaders. Targeted awareness campaigns showing the benefits of GE and SD will help to engage citizens. On a regular basis, the outcomes of the strategy – both positive and negative – should be widely shared to enhance transparency and accountability. By doing so, countries will enter in a virtuous circle to improve the quality, attractiveness and inclusiveness of the strategy and its associated policies. Similarly, the communication strategy of the MSSD 2016-2015 needs to be considerably strengthened.
- **Strengthen the engagement and commitment of relevant stakeholders:** Well designed stakeholder consultations should be undertaken during the revision/elaboration, implementation and monitoring of national, sectorial or local Green Economy and Sustainable Development strategies. When necessary, technical and financial support – through capacity building, operational grants, etc. – might also be provided to ensure real and constructive contributions from civil society organizations, in particular from distant or marginalised groups that might have difficulties to participate in such processes. Civil society plays here a constructive ‘watchdog’ role in counterbalancing the vested interests of powerful industrial or other lobbies, political wrong-doing and corruption. Addressing these challenges early, even if difficult, paves the way for smoother progress in the medium and long term.
- **Promote GE/SD initiatives led by local or sectoral stakeholders:** Local, national and regional (Mediterranean) institutions should promote actions, tools and mechanisms (through the web, handbooks, networking or capacity building activities, etc.) to identify, assess and disseminate successful local or sector specific GE/SD initiatives. They should also provide technical and financial support to scale-up and extend their impact to other geographical or sectorial areas.

Recommendation 3: Phase out Brown Economy, mainstream Green Finance and enhance Green Economy implementation

- **Phase out ‘brown’ incentives and initiatives:** Financing of Brown Economy, in particular through (hidden) subsidies, has to be phased out as soon as possible, following the OECD¹ and G7/G20² commitments. Projects that go directly against environmental and social sustainability and serve only short-term and non-equitable benefits, have to be stopped to avoid wasting precious natural and financial resources and send the right messages to the market and decision-makers.
- **Catalyse and mainstream Green Finance:** Public funding of Green Economy has to be scaled up, both at local, national and regional level, e.g. through the launch of green public banks as they exist in the UK, Greece and France. Such institutions should focus exclusively on supporting sustainable and responsible investments, in particular for households (energy efficiency), R&D (cleantech) and SMEs (green businesses). A Green Mediterranean Financial Initiative funded by a large Green Bonds programme could be launched to provide access to finance for green initiatives and infrastructures. Tax systems should also be reviewed to tax environmentally damaging activities and reinvest in challenged and marginalized communities and areas.
- **Pursue regional cooperation and peer learning:** International cooperation in GE areas should be further strengthened. International organisations such as UNEP/MAP and its RACs, the UfM Secretariat or OECD; or regional initiatives such as the Mediterranean Commission for Sustainable Development, the Horizon 2020 Initiative for a Cleaner Mediterranean, etc. can assist countries in these efforts and further nurture regional dialogue and progress on Green Economy and Sustainable Development. Countries can learn from each other through experience sharing, benchmarking and regional cooperation. Peer exchanges and learning mechanisms between national and international stakeholders as well as among national peers are strongly encouraged.

Conclusion

Overall it can be stated that all Mediterranean countries still have a long way to go to mainstream green and sustainable development principles into their economies. While some countries have well defined Green Economy/Sustainable Development strategies (such as France, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Tunisia), they still lack concrete implementation mechanisms, stakeholders’ commitment and systematic follow-up and evaluation. Several countries have not yet developed/published relevant national policies that sufficiently take into account Green Economy, the SDGs or other sustainable development elements and commitments (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Cyprus, Egypt, Palestine, Slovenia, Spain).

Dedicating scarce human and financial resources to design such long term strategies may be viewed as disconnected from priorities and realities on the ground that include addressing high unemployment rate, extreme poverty, human rights infringements, high rates of population growth, armed conflicts and terrorism, or corruption. Yet, embracing Green Economy and Sustainable Development is perhaps the only option at hand that could promise a more secure, equitable and prosperous

1 <http://www.oecd.org/environment/support-to-fossil-fuels-remains-high-and-the-time-is-ripe-for-change.htm>

2 <http://www.mofa.go.jp/files/000160266.pdf>

Mediterranean region in the decades to come.

In the case of Libya and Syria (the two countries that could not be included in this review), should their forthcoming reconstruction process include the development of an ambitious, consistent and participative national strategy on Green Economy and/or Sustainable Development, a meaningful and promising contribution to an inclusive, resilient and more likely to be sustained rebuilding effort could be boasted.

Given the historical consistency of the Mediterranean in being on the one hand a region of convergence but on the other of frequent conflict, developing and implementing robust long-term Green Economy/Sustainable Development strategies could strengthen the resilience of the region as a whole, the countries individually and of their communities, in resisting or better adapting to external and internal shocks that tend to negatively impact the region.

1

Green Economy: Concepts, approaches, stakeholders

This introductory chapter analyses the main concepts and initiatives regarding Green Economy (GE) and Sustainable Development (SD) at global and Mediterranean levels. It includes brief descriptions of some of the major stakeholders and projects that play a key role in promoting GE/SD in the region.

1.1 Overview of Green Economy concepts and actors

1.1.1 UNEP framework

Green economy concept

The United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) has been leading the development and dissemination of the Green Economy concept at the global level. According to UNEP, green economy aims “to improve human well-being and social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcity”. In this type of economy, revenue growth and employment come from public and private investments that reduce carbon emissions and pollution, enhance the rational use of resources and energy efficiency and prevent loss of biodiversity and environmental services.

Green Economy flagship report

In the context of the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UNCSD) which took place in Rio de Janeiro in 2012 (so called Rio+20), UNEP published a Green Economy Report³, entitled «Towards a green economy, pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication». This report, intended to promote green economy policies to reduce poverty and foster sustainable development, was UNEP’s key contribution to the Rio+20 process. It focuses on the greening of ten key economic sectors as listed below.

3 <http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/GreenEconomyReport/tabid/29846/Default.aspx>

Figure 1.1: Sectors considered to be driving the defining trends of the transition to a green economy, Source: Green Economy Report, UNEP, 2011

In this report, UNEP demonstrates that if 2% of global GDP was invested to green ten economic sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, water management, forestry, renewable energies, manufacturing, waste, buildings, transport and tourism, it would significantly increase the GDP growth rate, as well as reduce energy and water demand compared to the business-as-usual scenario.

Figure 1.2: Projected trend in annual GDP growth rate. Source: Green Economy Report, UNEP (2011)

In other reports, UNEP demonstrates the business case for environmental sustainability⁴ as well as the links between environment and trade⁵.

4 http://www.unep.org/publications/contents/pub_details_search.asp?ID=6263

5 <http://web.unep.org/greeneconomy/trade-and-green-economy-handbook>

Commitment at Rio+20

At the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UN CSD) in 2012, heads of states and governments, supported by non-governmental stakeholders, local authorities, businesses and NGOs, agreed in the Rio+20 Declaration to focus on green economy in the context of sustainable development and poverty eradication. It was the first time that green economy was officially acknowledged as a relevant tool for world nations to promote sustainable development.

Collaborations and activities

Today UNEP continues its work on Green Economy through capacity building and research activities as well as advisory services to governments. It has launched the PAGE initiative (Partnerships for Action on Green Economy) together with other UN bodies (UNIDO, UNITAR, ILO, UNDP) to train policy and decision makers in a more transversal manner. Finally, it is collaborating with the private sector through its Financial Initiative⁶ and its inquiry to design a sustainable financial system⁷.

Critical assessment

UNEP has been a major institutional actor in mainstreaming the green economy concept at global level by developing a robust socio-economic model that received official endorsement at the Rio+20 Summit. Its approach has also moved from a purely environmental perspective to a more holistic approach including poverty reduction and social inclusiveness. However, as an intergovernmental institution interacting at national level, it cannot directly engage with local stakeholders to build a fair participatory process that takes into account the voices of civil society and guarantee ownership of the local communities.

1.1.2 OECD approach

'Green Growth' approach

For the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), an intergovernmental policy think tank, the financial and economic crisis was a starting point to think about a new way of making business, as the current economic system was clearly problematic, and at the same time climate experts called for a quick reduction of fossil fuel consumption. For the OECD, Green Growth appeared as a response to these critical emerging issues and a chance to face the global challenge of sustainability.

According to the OECD flagship report "What is Green Growth and how can it help deliver sustainable Development?"⁸, Green Growth means fostering economic growth and development while ensuring that natural assets continue to provide the resources and environmental services on which our well-being relies. Its work is based mainly on providing tools and guidelines to governments to design appropriate policies and monitor adequately their implementation.

Political commitment

OECD started promoting Green Growth through a ministerial declaration⁹ approved by 34 industrialized countries in 2009¹⁰. It then published its Green Growth Strategy¹¹ in 2011 in order to provide concrete recommendations and measurement tools to support countries' efforts to achieve economic growth and development, while at the same time ensure that natural assets continue to provide the ecosystem services on which our well-being depends.

Green growth indicators

OECD has identified Green Growth Indicators, distributed in four main groups: environmental and resource productivity, natural asset base, environmental life dimension and economic opportunities and policy responses. The OECD disseminates the Green Growth Indicators to guide, evaluate and compare the development of green economy in different countries.

6 <http://www.unepfi.org/>

7 <http://www.unepinquiry.org/>

8 <http://www.oecd.org/greengrowth/whatisgreengrowthandhowcanithelpdeliversustainabledevelopment.htm>

9 OECD Declaration on Green Growth adopted at the Meeting of the Council at Ministerial Level on 25 June 2009, <https://www.oecd.org/env/44077822.pdf>

10 Now OECD has 35 members.

11 Towards Green Growth, OECD, 2011. <http://www.oecd.org/env/towards-green-growth-9789264111318-en.htm>

Figure 1.3: Green Growth Indicators framework (OECD), Source: Towards Green Growth, OECD, 2011

Critical assessment

As a policy-driven think-tank from (and mainly for) industrialized countries, OECD has primarily focused on tools and handbooks for policy makers of the developed world¹². Its approach on Green Growth maintains the traditional paradigm that economic growth is the key for development, although it tries to mitigate the collateral environmental damages. As a multi-national organization, it is not really designed to integrate the voice of civil society in the policy and decision process, even though multi-stakeholder involvement is encouraged. OECD aims to make messages to be applicable also to non-OECD countries but its capability to foster real change in non-OECD countries is relatively limited.

1.1.3 Global Green Growth Institute

The Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) is a new intergovernmental organization headquartered in Seoul created at the Rio+20 summit to promote green growth. The GGGI has three major objectives: the implementation of national green growth plans; the dissemination of research results; and the engagement of the private sector. Working mainly in low-income and emerging economies it focuses on four thematic priorities: energy, water, land-use and cities.

The GGGI uses a similar approach as the OECD: its definition of Green Growth means fostering economic growth and development while ensuring that natural assets continue to provide the resources and environmental services on which our well-being depends. It focuses on the synergies and trade-offs between the environmental and economic pillars of sustainable development.

GGGI work

GGGI mainly provides advisory services to partner governments by applying its value chain model based on diagnosis, assessment, sectorial planning, financing and implementation steps (see below). It is currently working with 20 countries from emerging and developing economies in Asia (China, India, Indonesia), Africa (Ethiopia, Rwanda, South Africa), the Middle East (Morocco, Jordan, UEA) and South America (Colombia, Mexico, Peru).

¹² However, OECD includes (and gathers experience from and for) OECD countries such as Mexico, Turkey and Chile where the per capita GDP is close to several countries of the Mediterranean region

Figure 1.4: The Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) value chain¹³

Green Growth Knowledge Platform

In 2012, a memorandum was signed between the GGGI, UNEP, the OECD and the World Bank to establish a **Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP)** sharing policy guidance, good practices, tools, and data necessary to support the transition to a green economy. For the first time, major international institutions with different background and objectives joined forces to accelerate knowledge development and dissemination around Green Economy.

Critical assessment

As a new organization, GGGI is still developing its technical and human capability to effectively support governments to move towards Green Growth. But similarly to the OECD, the GGGI approach is mainly marked by top-down processes and policy-driven activities through traditional macro-economic assessments. It does not fully integrate societal stakeholders and local communities into the analysis and policy formulation phases. Also it usually does not publish the outcomes of its work with partner countries, which reduces the potential for good practices dissemination and replication. By using the Green Growth concept, its approach continues to lay emphasis on economic growth as opposed to trying to achieve economic growth within environmental and ecological limits.

1.1.4 European Union

Approach

The European Commission (EC) refers to a natural resource crisis as a system that overuses fossil resources as if they were infinite. Europe and the world in general are threatened by scarcity of natural resources. To face that problem, the EC supports European countries in their transition toward a green economy. In a report¹⁴ published in July 2014, the EC estimates 20 million jobs could be created between 2014 and 2020 by transitioning to a Green Economy. The EC proposes in particular to the EU Member States to support job creation by increasing taxes on pollution rather than on labour, to anticipate skills gaps in the areas of the Green Economy, to accelerate sectorial changes and to enhance international cooperation.

The European Union's ten-year jobs and growth strategy Europe 2020, launched in 2010, aims to create the conditions for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. In particular, specific targets cover the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by 20% (30% if the conditions allow it) from 1990 levels, 20% final energy consumption from renewable sources, and a 20% improvement in energy efficiency. The last target is the reduction of poverty with at least 20 million fewer people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion. In December 2011, the EU also launched the **Eco-innovation Action** Plan which aims to assure the transition toward a resource-efficient and low carbon economy.

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA)¹⁵, a Green Economy is one in which policies and innovation enable societies to generate more value each year, while maintaining the natural systems that sustain it.

13 <http://gggi.org/activities/ggpi/ggp-overview/>

14 Green Employment Initiative, EC Comm, 2014. <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2014/EN/1-2014-446-EN-F1-1.Pdf>

15 <http://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/economy/intro>

Figure 1.5: EEA Green Economy framework¹⁶, Source: European Environment Agency

Critical assessment

The European Commission promotes a green economy that is in line with the OECD's Green Growth Strategy, where economic growth is a necessary factor for an optimal Green Economy. This dominant growth imperative—strengthened since the 2008 economic crisis — has resulted in further liberal economic policies. Thus, policies aim at improving efficiency of production, rather than sufficiency of consumption. Even though binding targets like the 20-20-20 targets for 2020 and regulation (fuel standards, EE standards, etc.) exist, most EU legislation relating to Green Economy is in the form of soft law tools. Therefore, apart from demanding strict compliance where mandated, EU's assistance with finance, monitoring, developing governance and market tools is crucial.

1.1.5 Green Economy Coalition

GEC approach

The Green Economy Coalition (GEC) is the world's largest multi-stakeholder network on green economy. Through its diverse set of members from intergovernmental organisations, businesses, trade unions, research institutes and NGOs, it aims to accelerate the transition toward a green global economy. According to GEC, the economic, social, and environmental crises are inter-linked and could be solved by a global transition towards a green and fair economy. GEC suggests that there is no "one size fits all" Green Economy concept but that instead core principles, such as social equity, community ownership and ecological limits, should form the basis for bottom-up processes to build national visions on Green Economy.

Therefore, the GEC works on five interrelated action areas in order to foster green growth according to a symptoms-causes-solutions mode, called the Big Picture:

- Measuring what matters,
- Influencing financial systems,
- Greening high impact sectors,
- Investing in people,
- Managing natural capital.

16 <http://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/economy/intro>

Figure 1.6: The GEC Big Picture model

Principles

The GEC has also developed and endorsed nine principles that should apply to a Green Economy, according to the box below.

Box 1 : Nine Principles of a Green Economy¹⁷

1. **The Sustainable Principle:** It is a means to deliver sustainable development.
2. **The Justice Principle:** It supports equity between and within countries and people.
3. **The Dignity Principle:** It creates genuine prosperity and wellbeing for all.
4. **Healthy Planet Principle:** It restores lost biodiversity, invests in natural systems and rehabilitates those that are degraded.
5. **The Inclusion Principle:** It is inclusive and participatory in decision-making.
6. **The Good Governance and Accountability Principle:** It is accountable, participative and transparent.
7. **The Resilience Principle:** It contributes to economic, social and environmental resilience.
8. **The Efficiency and Sufficiency Principle:** It delivers sustainable consumption and production.
9. **The Generations Principle:** It invests for the present and the future.

According to the GEC, these principles should be applied to deliver an inclusive, participative and sustainable Green Economy.

Activities

GEC's activities include the coordination of national multi-stakeholder dialogues on Green Economy, research on green transition policies, the representation of the voices of stakeholders in national and international processes, and finally lobbying

17 <http://www.greenecommycoalition.org/updates/sign-9-principles-green-economy>

key decision makers.

It has organized several national participative dialogues¹⁸ in the Caribbean, India, Brazil, Mali, Spain, Kazakhstan, Zambia, Cambodia and the Greater Mekong region. It also coordinates once a year a global convention on Green Economy where international experts and national stakeholders are invited to exchange on conceptual and methodological approaches to Green Economy.

Critical assessment

As a global platform that gathers a large variety of stakeholders GEC’s approach receives diverse input from experts, civil society and researchers. It strongly advocates participatory, open and transparent dialogues as necessary tools to reach consensus and engage with local actors. However, GEC’s real impact on policy making is dependent on the willingness and commitment of diverse stakeholder groups that need to cooperate effectively in concrete activities to drive significant change in targeted countries and sectors.

1.1.6 Review of the approaches and actors

Inclusive Green Growth vs. Green Economy

In the aftermath of Rio+20, governments and international organisations have adopted the language of “inclusive Green Growth”. The World Bank has noted that “welfare gains” are the aim of Green Growth while the OECD and UNEP have shown the benefits of Green Growth for the poorest, including healthy soils, cleaner water supplies, less pollution and the creation of green jobs.

However, there remain some important conceptual distinctions between notions for “inclusive Green Growth” and a broader understanding of a “Green Economy”. First, Green Growth does not explicitly address equity issues and for the most part assumes that trickle-down economics will improve the living standards of the poorest. Second, Green Growth aims at resource efficiency and more sustainable patterns of consumption and production but is not informed or guided by ecological limits. Finally, Green Growth tends to put more emphasis on economic tools, market instruments and metrics, rather than on changing and greening the economic model as a whole.

Mapping of Green Economy actors

As shown in the image below, the definition of Green Economy is variable and covers different issues according to the origin and mission of their promoters. Some actors focus on reducing carbon emissions and promoting climate friendly economy (GGGI); others are supporting resource efficiency and cleaner economic growth (OECD, World Bank, UNEP); and finally some of them are advocating towards more equity and justice (GEC, trade unions, social NGOs).

Figure 1.7: Mapping of Green Economy actors (Source: GEC 2016)

18 <http://www.greeneconomycoalition.org/what/national-dialogues>

SWOT analysis of the Green Economy concept

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadly popular concept at international level • Positive impact on environmental, economic and social transformation • Cross-cutting approach thus promoting cross sectoral integration • Uses local/regional practises and knowledge • Promotes stakeholder engagement and empowerment of local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No global definition of Green Economy • Situational concept and characteristics vary according to the area under consideration • Lack of full understanding of the financial gains of transitioning to a green economy • Unknown damages to conventional business models, “brown” jobs and incumbent economic actors
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addresses climate change and sustainability issues • Creates qualified, stable and fair jobs • Revitalizes economies and opens up new business opportunities • Contributes to energy independency as well as water and food security • Reduces poverty, promotes equitable distribution of wealth and social equity • Increases societal resilience to internal and external shocks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of public and private funding • Challenges to changes in consumption and production patterns and life styles • Resentment to change by those who feel that their interests may be compromised or threatened

Table 1.1: SWOT analysis of the Green Economy concept (own elaboration)

1.2 Other concepts and initiatives related to Green Economy

1.2.1 Sustainable Development

Approach and link to GE

The Brundtland Report¹⁹ (1987) placed the concept of Sustainable Development at the forefront of international policy debate. The report defined sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. Since then, the concept of sustainable development has been used in major international agreements, where four recurring principles are considered to comprise the concept:²⁰

- The principle of intergenerational equity: the need to preserve natural resources for future generations
- The principle of sustainable use: exploiting natural resources aiming for long-term availability and considering environmental impacts
- The principle of Intragenerational equity: states should use natural resources considering the needs of other states
- The principle of integration: development plans and projects should integrate environmental considerations

One aspect of the Brundtland Report was to use the concept of sustainable development to question the development model based on the high rate of resource depletion for continued economic growth. However, it also supported rapid economic growth, resulting in an ambiguity that has enabled governments, corporations, and organisations to have different interpretations of the concept. Therefore, sustainable development is either referred to as seeing environmental protection, social equity and economic growth as equal spheres, or – depending on the interests – greatly prioritizing one of those aspects. Thus, the concept of sustainable development and sustainability are used to describe numerous types of policies ranging from expansion of the coal industry to the protection of natural areas.

19 World Commission on Environment and Development, Our Common Future (1987),

20 Sands, Philippe, and Jacqueline Peel. Principles of International Environmental Law. Cambridge University Press, 2012.

Sustainable development is usually referred to as being based on three pillars or constituted by three main fields, as depicted in the figure below: Environment, Society and Economy.

Figure 1.8: Sustainable Development pillars

Some argue that the concept of Green Economy emphasises on the intersection between environment and economy. However, others – including the authors – rather see the economy (and thus the Green Economy) as a subsystem to society, which is a subsystem to the environment. This view is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1.9: Sustainable development – within ecological limits

MIO-ECSDE goes further by proposing to conceptualise the relation between Green Economy, Society and the Environment (on the foundation of Governance) in the shape of a tetrahedron or pyramid, or even a double pyramid, which includes also regulation/institutions, science/technology/infrastructure and awareness/education/culture (influencing human behaviour) as the basic constituents of Governance.

Figure 1.10: Green Economy as part of Sustainable Development and 'serviced' by Governance tools (Scoullos, 2012).

UNEP began to promote green economy in 2008—over twenty years after the Brundtland Report—in the midst of an economic crisis, growing social inequality and as scientists warn that we may have already crossed a number planetary boundaries. Thus, green economy is presented as an effective pathway towards achieving sustainable development; a means for catalysing renewed national policy efforts and international cooperation for sustainable development.²¹

Initiatives

The 1992 Earth Summit led countries to draw up sustainable development strategies and many initiatives by public and private actors across the globe. The EU 2020 Strategy sets a number of initiatives to achieve SD, such as Resource Efficient Europe (COM (2011) 571), which lays out a route towards a sustainable economy by 2050—with the famous 20-20-20 targets to be reached by 2020. The UN continually promotes SD initiatives through its different bodies. For example, a key initiative of UNDP's Strategic Plan for 2014-2017 is the Global Policy Centre on Resilient Ecosystems and Desertification (GC-RED), which promotes inclusive growth, wellbeing and environmental sustainability in dry-lands; and the UNFCCC Paris agreement, adopted in December 2015 by 195 countries, sets a framework of GHGs emission reductions in order to ensure the possibility of sustainable development.

Critical assessment

The concept of sustainable development has set a milestone in integrating environmental concerns in socioeconomic development plans, and in increasing awareness of the negative impacts that our economy and industries have on the environment and society. However, constant ambiguous use of "sustainable development" and "sustainability"—often interchangeable with economic growth—has made it a 'fit-all' term to increase the attractiveness of plans that often disregard environmental protection and social equity. It is therefore imperative to refine the definition of sustainable development, to not only focus on economic growth but to emphasize sustainable economic development that promotes human wellbeing and environmental integrity.

1.2.2 Sustainable Development Goals

Approach and link to GE

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the "2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development" are a United Nations initiative that builds on the partially achieved Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). While the 2012 Rio+20 Summit embraced the concept of Green Economy as one of the important tools to achieve sustainable development, it also agreed that specific goals and targets for all countries should be developed in order to achieve Sustainable Development.

On 25 September 2015, the entire UN General Assembly adopted the 17 goals and 169 targets that comprise the SDGs to be achieved by 2030²². The SDGs "recognize that ending poverty must go hand-in-hand with strategies that build economic growth and addresses a range of social needs including education, health, social protection, and job opportunities, while tackling

21 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/topics/greeneconomy>

22 For a list of indicators see <http://unstats.un.org/unsd/statcom/47th-session/documents/2016-2-SDGs-Rev1-E.pdf>

climate change and environmental protection.²³ The SDGs are to be achieved by the adoption of Green Economy policies at national level and the active participation of the private sector in supporting Green Economy.

Box 2 : The 17 Sustainable Development Goals

1. **Poverty:** End poverty in all its forms everywhere
2. **Hunger and Food Security:** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture
3. **Good Health and Well-Being:** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages
4. **Education:** Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all
5. **Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment:** Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls
6. **Water and Sanitation:** Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all
7. **Energy:** Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and clean energy for all
8. **Economic Growth:** Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all
9. **Infrastructure, Industrialization:** Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation
10. **Inequality:** Reduce inequality within and among countries
11. **Cities:** Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable
12. **Sustainable Consumption and Production:** Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
13. **Climate Change:** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts
14. **Oceans:** Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development
15. **Biodiversity, Forests, Deforestation:** Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss
16. **Peace and Justice:** Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels
17. **Partnerships:** Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

Initiatives

While many initiatives relating to the different goals have been adopted globally since the 1992 Earth Summit, the SDGs came into force on 1 January 2016. In this early stage of the plan, countries are expected—though not obliged—to establish national frameworks adopting specific initiatives for the achievement of the SDGs.²⁴

Critical assessment

The SDGs are receiving a lot of attention from policy-makers and are being considered in national development plans. Therefore, they aspire to highly influence national strategies until 2030. However, there are many goals and targets that are unclear—an independent scientific assessment identified that only 29% of the 169 targets are “well developed.”²⁵ Furthermore, several goals arguably fall short; such as ending extreme poverty, which is measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day, an amount that may not eradicate malnourishment in many developing countries. The SDGs continue to focus on GDP growth (Goal 8), without hampering other goals such as Goal 12 (“Ensure sustainable production and consumption patterns”) and Goal 13 (“Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts”).

23 <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/development-agenda/>

24 http://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=A/RES/70/1&Lang=E

25 <http://www.icsu.org/publications/reports-and-reviews/review-of-targets-for-the-sustainable-development-goals-the-science-perspective-2015/SDG-Report.pdf>

1.2.3 Cleaner Production

Approach

UNEP defines Cleaner Production (CP) as “the continuous application of an integrated preventative environmental strategy to processes, products and services to increase efficiency and reduce risks to humans and the environment.”²⁶ CP aims for making industry and business reduce hazardous waste, emissions, and all environmental impacts of services and products. It is considered a win-win-win strategy that fosters economic growth, protects the environment and ensures the safety of workers.²⁷

Cleaner Production Centres

Since one of the main application fields for resource efficiency lies within the industrial sector, UNEP and UNIDO (United Nation Industrial Development Organization) launched together in 2008 a joint programme called Resource Efficiency and Cleaner Production (RE&CP). National Cleaner Production Centres (NCPCs) were established in more than 50 developing countries to promote the development of cleaner production in businesses, finance and government's policies. Their activities include information dissemination, professional training, plant assessments and support for policy change and technology transfer.

Critical assessment

The CP concept was popular in the 80s and 90s when it was urgent to eliminate large industrial pollution through major technological upgrades, often turnkey solutions implemented by private companies and financed by public donors. However, once low-hanging fruits were taken, the gain for resource efficiency is getting less attractive and more difficult to extract. In addition to that, CP usually promotes end of pipe solutions based on expensive and uncertain technical innovation, without taking into consideration a more holistic and societal approach to address resource scarcity.

1.2.4 Resource Efficiency

Approach

UNEP defines Resource Efficiency as the reduction of the total environmental impact of the production and consumption of goods and services during their whole life cycle, i.e. from raw material extraction to final use and disposal²⁸. It implies the reduction on waste and greenhouse gas emissions, the promotion of a safe chemical management and the implementation of cleaner products and technologies.²⁹

European Union

The EU identified Resource Efficiency³⁰ as one of the seven flagship initiatives to promote sustainable growth within the European 2020 agenda³¹. Its implementation is underpinned by a low-carbon strategy, an energy efficiency plan, eco-design directives and a roadmap to a resource efficient Europe, approved in 2011 but weakly implemented by Member States.

Critical assessment

Resource Efficiency is considered a key process of Green Economy. Economic strategies lay out Resource Efficiency targets for all sectors, primarily through technological innovation and environmental awareness. However, while resource efficiency has improved in the past decades, overall consumption of resources and GHGs emissions have steadily increased. This contradiction is described by the rebound effect (Jevons paradox), which occurs when efficiency gains are lost by an increase in consumption. While the rebound effect has been known for some time, policies specifically addressing it are in an early stage and concentrate on raising awareness, education and fiscal mechanisms.³²

1.2.5 Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP)

Approach

The concept of Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP) has been recognized as an overarching theme to link

26 <http://www.unido.org/en/what-we-do/environment/resource-efficient-and-low-carbon-industrial-production/cp/cleaner-production.html>

27 http://www.unep.fr/shared/publications/other/WEBx0072xPA/manual_cdrom/Guidance%20Manual/PDF%20versions/Part1.pdf

28 <http://www.unep.org/resourceefficiency/Home/ApproachandTools/tabid/55537/Default.aspx>

29 Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) is another policy approach worthwhile mentioning, see <http://www.oecd.org/env/tools-evaluation/extendedproducerresponsibility.htm>

30 http://ec.europa.eu/resource-efficient-europe/index_en.htm

31 http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/index_en.htm

32 http://ec.europa.eu/environment/eussd/pdf/rebound_effect_report.pdf

environmental and development challenges at the Rio Earth Summit in 1992. “The major cause of the continued deterioration of the global environment are the unsustainable patterns of consumption and production, particularly in industrialized countries, which is a matter of grave concern, aggravating poverty and imbalances”; according to the statements made at the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development.

According to UNEP, SCP is defined as “the use of services and related products, which respond to basic needs and bring a better quality of life while minimising the use of natural resources and toxic materials as well as the emissions of waste and pollutants over the life cycle of the service or product so as not to jeopardise the needs of future generations.”³³

Activities

In a report published in 2010³⁴ whose aim is to clarify the concept of SCP, UNEP defines a 10-year framework (10YFP) to implement SCP in the next decade through regional and national initiatives.

Figure 1.11: SCP model (Source: UNEP)

SCP in national policies

Due to UNEP’s guidance, significant progress was achieved during the last decades to implement SCP in national policies and in enterprises. In the Mediterranean region, a specific Regional Action Plan on SCP (SCP AP)³⁵ has been validated by the countries through the Barcelona Convention. National strategies are now being developed and adopted by Southern and Eastern Mediterranean countries through the technical leadership of UNEP.

Critical assessment

The SCP concept is an evolution of the cleaner production approach described above. As such, it focuses on reducing the negative environmental impact of industrial production through technological solutions, often expensive and owned by private companies (e.g. through patents). Only recently more emphasis has been laid on changing life-style patterns through education, training and awareness campaigns. However, it remains a set of technical tools to mitigate negative externalities within specific sectors. It lacks the ambition to radically transform the whole value chain.

1.2.6 Circular Economy

Approach

The Circular Economy approach was originally researched by scientists and academics within the industrial ecology field. But it has gained high public visibility with the publication of the flagship report “Towards a circular economy”³⁶ in 2012 by the Ellen

33 Norwegian Ministry of Environment, Oslo Symposium, 1994

34 http://www.unep.org/10yfp/Portals/50150/downloads/publications/ABC/ABC_ENGLISH.pdf

35 <http://www.switchmed.eu/en/corners/policy-makers>

36 <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy>

Mac Arthur Foundation. It defines Circular Economy as one that is restorative and regenerative by design, and which aims to keep products, components and materials at their highest utility and value at all times.

Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation

The Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation, mainly financed by large private companies, brings together businesses, national and local governments, cities, academic institutions and innovators to learn, build capacity, network, and collaborate around Circular Economy. It publishes a toolbox, methodology and assessment on a sectorial basis, in particular plastics, consumer goods and other manufacturing sectors.

Figure 1.12: Linear vs. Circular Economy (Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013).

European Union

The European Commission (EC) quickly adopted the Circular Economy concept, identifying it as a useful tool to promote Resource Efficiency and sustainable growth. In particular, it fits well with its strategy to reduce waste generation and increase waste recycling. The EU has recently approved a Circular Economy package³⁷.

Cradle-to-Cradle

The Cradle-to-Cradle (C2C) concept is a design philosophy that best fits a circular economy. It takes a biomimetic approach to design and manufacturing of products as it eliminates the concept of waste. Similar to nutrients, all materials involved in industrial and commercial processes are continually recovered and reused with a beneficial environmental impact. It is based on two cycles: the biological cycle for products or components of consumption; and the technical cycle for products or components that are recycled and reused. While the C2C concept has long been successful in cases of small-scale production, it has not been able yet to gain momentum on a large industrial scale.³⁸

Critical assessment

Circular Economy has been getting a lot of attention due to its original communicative style, strong business modelling, as well as clear leadership by public leaders. Yet, the concept relies mainly on a top-down approach pushed by private economic actors who see Circular Economy as an opportunity for technical innovation and market growth. It does not respond adequately to the inertia of the incumbent players that prefer to maintain the status-quo, nor to the inconvenient reflections on the sustainability of our lifestyles and does not clearly promote citizens participation and ownership. The EU Circular Economy package is

37 http://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/index_en.htm

38 <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy/schools-of-thought/cradle2cradle>

considered by environmental NGOs to be weaker than expected due to pressure from conservative businesses.³⁹

1.2.7 Blue Economy

Concept

The Blue Economy approach has been promoted by the UNEP flagship report “Green Economy in a blue world”⁴⁰. It recognises the vital importance of seas and oceans to provide food, water and energy to the growing number of people living in coastal areas and islands. Oceans and seas also create jobs for 120 million of fishermen around the world and transports 90% of global commerce. Blue economy is structured around five strategic economic pillars:

- fisheries and aquaculture,
- coastal tourism,
- maritime transport,
- deep sea minerals,
- marine-based renewable energy

It is worth noting that each sector impacts, more or less severely, natural ecosystems while at the same time depends on environmental integrity to prosper.

European Union

The EU’s “Blue Growth” strategy⁴¹ is a recent strategy to promote economic growth in the marine and maritime sectors. It recognizes that the oceans and seas are motors of the European economy which offer considerable potential for innovation and growth. In Europe, the “blue” economy represents 5.4 million jobs and gross value added of around 500 billion euros per year. The Integrated Maritime Policy outlines the areas where further growth of the sector is looked at:

- **Aquaculture:** Farming of finfishes, shellfishes and aquatic plants
- **Coastal and maritime tourism:** It represents between 5% to 10% of national GDPs
- **Blue biotechnology:** Exploration and exploitation of marine organisms to develop new materials, products and drugs
- **Ocean energy:** Use of tides and waves as well as differences in temperature and salinity to create clean and renewable energy
- **Seabed mining:** Extraction of the minerals occupying the ocean floor, in particular silver, gold, copper, manganese, cobalt, and zinc

Critical assessment

Oceans and seas remain widely unknown spaces while they cover most of the Earth’s surface. It seems therefore very attractive for policy makers and economic actors to advocate for the exploration and exploitation of such large potential natural resources. The definition of the term is also still very loose. Moreover, past experience of the human capability to destroy fragile ecosystems should alert for the precautionary principle to be applied in full force. Moreover, in the geopolitically sensitive Mediterranean region, the competition for scarce resources and the density of the population might further increase the existing instabilities.⁴²

1.2.8 Social Economy

Approach

The concept of Social Economy applies to economic organisations such as cooperatives, mutual societies, associations or foundations whose internal operations and activities are based on a principle of solidarity and social utility. These organisations adopt democratic and participatory management methods. They strictly regulate the use of profits they realize: individual profit is prohibited and benefits are reinvested.

39 <http://www.euractiv.com/section/science-policy/news/new-circular-economy-package-to-create-fewer-jobs-than-axed-bill-it-replaced/>

40 http://www.unep.org/pdf/green_economy_blue.pdf

41 http://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy/blue_growth/index_en.htm

42 http://wwf.panda.org/wwf_news/?247477/Principles-for-a-Sustainable-Blue-Economy

Activities

Social Economy operates in all sectors of the economy: social services, healthcare, insurance, banking, agriculture, renewable energies, recycling, housing sector, education, tourism, culture, sport, etc. According to the OECD⁴³, Social Economy is gaining in visibility at the international, national and local levels, contributing to employment, social inclusion, democratic participation and community building.

Figure 1.13: Social Economy

Critical assessment

Social Economy has been present since the beginning of the industrialization age in the primary sectors such as agriculture or fisheries. It was an effective way to share industrial, financial and commercial assets to produce, transform and distribute the outcomes of individualized workers. However, today the economic, technical and political capabilities of large private companies have almost destroyed the small-scale social economy initiatives. Yet, the economic crisis – caused at least in part by unethical behaviour of global multinationals – has promoted Social Economy once again as an innovative model to promote public ownership and value distribution by and to local communities. In that sense, Social Economy can be seen as a relevant tool to develop an inclusive Green Economy in particular in emerging and developing countries.

1.3 Approach taken in this study

In this study, the Green Economy approach followed is the one supported by the GEC and civil society organizations, where a Green Economy vision should be conceived and implemented through communities' and stakeholders engagement. This model, based on the core principle of equity, accountability and sufficiency, requires bottom-up dialogue processes and participative policy design. It does not intend to only mitigate specific environmental damages but rather to radically reform all economic and financial sectors in order to eliminate negative externalities and guarantee prosperity for all within ecological limits.

It is on this basis that the national GE strategies of the Mediterranean have been assessed (see Chapter 3). The approach chosen and methodology followed for the assessment is reflected in the criteria that have been chosen and how the weighting of each one (points per criterion) has been done (especially the qualitative criteria).

43 <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/thesocialeconomybuildinginclusiveeconomies.htm>

The following graph illustrates the preferred path for countries going from a rather low to a high Human Development Index: Instead of following the path that industrialised countries have taken in the past, i.e. by increasing the ecological footprint beyond sustainable levels and then trying to reduce the footprint again, less developed countries (especially those of the Southern and Eastern Mediterranean) would pursue a truly sustainable development strategy which allows them to stay consistently within the Earth's limits regarding biocapacity per capita.

Figure 1.14: Sustainable Development path - own elaboration from UNEP Green Economy Report

In the following table, the sectors that are the ones considered to be of more 'green' potential are: renewables, waste/recycling, public transport, green buildings, sustainable farming and forestry.

		Green potential	Green job progress to date	Long-term green job potential
Energy	Renewables	Excellent	Good	Excellent
	Carbon capture and storage	Fair	None	Unknown
Industry	Steel	Good	Fair	Fair
	Aluminum	Good	Fair	Fair
	Cement	Fair	Fair	Fair
	Pulp and paper	Good	Fair	Good
	Recycling	Excellent	Good	Excellent
Transportation	Fuel-efficient cars	Fair to Good	Limited	Good
	Mass transit	Excellent	Limited	Excellent
	Rail	Excellent	Negative	Excellent
	Aviation	Limited	Limited	Limited
Buildings	Green buildings	Excellent	Limited	Excellent
	Retrofitting	Excellent	Limited	Excellent
	Lighting	Excellent	Good	Excellent
	Efficient equipment and appliances	Excellent	Fair	Excellent
Agriculture	Small-scale sustainable farming	Excellent	Negative	Excellent
	Organic farming	Excellent	Limited	Good to Excellent
	Environmental services	Good	Limited	Unknown
Forestry	Reforestation/Afforestation	Good	Limited	Good
	Agroforestry	Good to Excellent	Limited	Good to Excellent
	Sustainable forestry management	Excellent	Good	Excellent

Figure 1.15: Green jobs progress to-date and future potential (UNEP 2008)

However, it should be noted that **tourism, water, fisheries** and **services** (such as education and training, health care, green finance, etc.) are also essential to promote GE and SD in Mediterranean countries.

1.4 Mediterranean stakeholders and initiatives promoting Green Economy

The Mediterranean is home to a variety of institutions, public or private, that play an active role in shaping the future of the region. In this section we present those that are most relevant in terms of promoting Sustainable Development and Green Economy in the Mediterranean.

1.4.1 Intergovernmental institutions

Political integration of the Mediterranean is far from being consolidated, yet several intergovernmental institutions are playing an active role in designing policies and implementing actions to promote sustainability of the region. They contribute to GE/SD strategies through political engagement as well as financial and technical support. A selection of the most relevant ones for GE/SD is presented below.

UNEP/MAP⁴⁴

The Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) is the first regional seas programme of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) involving 21 countries bordering the Mediterranean Sea, as well as the European Union. Through UNEP/MAP, the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention and its Protocols (1976) are determined to meet the challenges of protecting the marine and coastal environment while boosting regional and national efforts to achieve sustainable development. The Coordination Unit of UNEP/MAP, based in Athens, is the technical office responsible for the follow-up of the Barcelona convention, together with its Regional Activity Centers (RACs) located in various Mediterranean countries.

UNEP/MAP and the Barcelona Convention mainly focus on the environmental pillar of sustainability, although they have enlarged their scope to economic and societal issues through the creation of the Mediterranean Commission for Sustainable Development (MCSD) in 1996 as an independent Advisory Body (see more below) and more recently, the adoption of the Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production for the Mediterranean and its Roadmap for implementation (2016).

Plan Bleu⁴⁵

The Plan Bleu is a UNEP/MAP Regional Activity Center (RAC) set up in the 70s. It is a non-profit body based in Marseille acting as an observatory of the environment and development in the Mediterranean. It has technically supported the development of the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) (see below), initially launched in 2005 by the Contracting Parties of the Barcelona Convention and updated in 2016. The MSSD has been a tool for coordinated and joint progress in the fields of human and economic development, environmental protection and cultural advancement. Plan Bleu also publishes technical studies, reports and builds databases; establishes and facilitates experts' networks; and promotes stakeholder engagement. It is a relevant Green Economy actor as it leads regional programmes on blue economy, sustainable development strategies, sustainable tourism, etc.

SCP/RAC⁴⁶

The Regional Activity Center for Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP/RAC) is part of UNEP/MAP, based in Barcelona, and aims to promote pollution prevention and sustainable consumption and production patterns. It works with governments, businesses and civil society to raise awareness, build capacity and contribute to the exchange of knowledge at national and regional level. Together with UNEP and UNIDO, it is coordinating the SwitchMed⁴⁷ initiative, an EU funded project to support green entrepreneurs, cleaner production and SCP strategies in the Southern Mediterranean countries. It has a recognized expertise on SCP policies and GE entrepreneurship in the tourism, food, industry and housing sectors. SCP/RAC has been in charge of the Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production for the Mediterranean and its Roadmap for implementation (adopted in February 2016), which focuses on four priority areas: food, agriculture and fisheries; goods manufacturing; tourism; and, housing and construction. Those areas represent drivers of pollution generation and environmental pressures on the marine and coastal ecosystems but at the same time high contributors to the Mediterranean economies and to social well-being.

PAP-RAC⁴⁸

The Regional Activity Centre for Priority Action Programmes (PAP/RAC), established in 1977 and based in Croatia, is also part of the UNEP/MAP family. Its principal activity is the implementation of Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) in the Mediterranean, as per the mandate of the relevant protocol under the Barcelona convention. It also promotes the use of Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) tools at national and regional levels. It is also involved in the Blue Economy initiative⁴⁹ coordinated by the Plan Bleu.

44 <http://www.unepmap.org/>

45 <http://planbleu.org/>

46 <http://www.scprac.org/en>

47 www.switchmed.eu

48 <http://www.pap-thecoastcentre.org/?lang=fr>

49 <http://www.mava-blue-economy.com/>

MCSD and MSSD⁵⁰

The Mediterranean Commission for Sustainable Development (MCSD)⁵¹ was created by the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention in 1996 and manifests their commitment to sustainable development and to the effective implementation, at the regional and national levels, of the decisions of the Earth Summit and the United Nations Commission for Sustainable Development. It is made up of members representing each of the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention, as well as rotating representatives from the wider community (local authorities, the business community, NGOs, scientific community, intergovernmental organisations and eminent experts), that in principle have a mandate of 2 years. The MCSD dwells upon the assessment of major sustainable development issues of common concern to the countries of the region or set out in international and regional agendas. It makes relevant proposals and recommendations to the Contracting Parties.

The MCSD developed the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) which was adopted by the Barcelona Convention Contracting Parties in 2006. It was recently revised to its current version "MSSD 2016-2025"⁵² which also takes into consideration the adaptation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) to the Mediterranean region. It is based on the integration between socio-economic development and protection of natural resources. This principle is encapsulated in the subtitle of the Strategy: "investing in environmental sustainability to achieve social and economic development". MSSD 2016-2025 is also complementary to the Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production for the Mediterranean and its Roadmap for implementation. It is articulated around 6 objectives, one of which is Green Economy.

UfM⁵³

The Union for the Mediterranean is an intergovernmental institution that promotes dialogue and cooperation in the Euro-Mediterranean region, bringing together the 28 European Union Member States and 15 countries from the Southern and Eastern shores of the Mediterranean. Its main objective is to support projects and initiatives in six strategic areas: business development, social and civil affairs, higher education and research, transport and urban development, water and environment, and energy and climate action.

The UfM secretariat is offering mainly political support, through its labelization process, to several GE/SD projects/initiatives promoted by various types of promoters. It also offers a platform for networking and collaboration as well as some capacity building support to countries. However, it currently does not provide direct financial and technical support to those projects, which is a limitation of its potential impact in the region.

European Union

Nine Mediterranean countries are currently members of the European Union (EU). The European Commission (EC) is the EU's politically independent executive arm. It is alone responsible for drawing up proposals for new European legislation, and it implements the decisions of the European Parliament and the Council of the EU. The EC's Environment Directorate as well as the European Environment Agency (EEA) work on green and circular economy policies for the EU Member States. Through the EC's cooperation arm (EuropeAid), the EU also finances sustainability oriented actions and activities with a direct impact on the Mediterranean neighbourhood.

The European Neighbourhood Policy (previously ENPI)⁵⁴ is supporting political and economic reforms towards peace, stability and economic prosperity in the whole region with emphasis on bilateral relations between the EU and its neighbouring countries. It promotes political, economic and security stabilization of the region including job creation, tackling irregular migration, energy security and climate action⁵⁵. A specific program for the Southern Mediterranean region has been developed with an allocation of between €7.5 and €9.2 billion for 2014 – 2020. During 2007 – 2013, the EU has already made available a total of over €9 billion⁵⁶.

League of Arab States⁵⁷

The League of Arab States has as its purpose the strengthening of the relations between its member-states, the coordination of their policies in order to achieve co-operation among them and safeguard their independence and sovereignty, and a general concern with the affairs and interests of the Arab countries. Cooperation includes economic and financial affairs (including

50 <http://planbleu.org/en/activites/sustainable-development-and-mssd>

51 <http://www.unepmap.org/index.php?module=content2&catid=001017002>

52 <http://planbleu.org/en/activites/sustainable-development-and-mssd>

53 <http://ufmsecretariat.org/>

54 <http://eeas.europa.eu/enp/>

55 http://eeas.europa.eu/enp/pdf/financing-the-enp/enp_wide_strategic_priorities_2014_2020_and_multi_annual_indicative_programme_2014_2017_en.pdf

56 http://ec.europa.eu/enlargement/neighbourhood/southern-neighbourhood/index_en.htm

57 <http://www.arableagueonline.org/>

commercial relations, customs, currency and questions of agriculture and industry), communications (railroads, roads, aviation, navigation, telegraphs and posts), cultural affairs (passports etc.), nationality, social affairs and health affairs. In the Arab States region, a number of countries are grappling with challenges such as low growth, high unemployment – especially for youth, climate change, and conflicts. The League of Arab States, through its specialized Ministerial Councils, particularly those for Social Development and Environmental Affairs, are closely involved in sustainable development issues. At the UN Sustainable Development Summit in September 2015, the highest level of leadership from the Arab States region committed to the new agenda.

*RCREEE*⁵⁸

The Regional Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency is an independent intergovernmental organization that seeks to enable and increase the adoption of renewable energy and energy efficiency practices in the Arab region. The 17 Arab country members and the League of Arab States tackle specific issues in each country with regional governments and global organizations to initiate and lead clean energy policy dialogues, strategies, technologies and capacity development.

*CEDARE*⁵⁹

The Centre for Environment and Development for the Arab Region and Europe (CEDARE), based in Cairo, was established in 1992 as an international non-profit organization. It is a knowledge-based and technology-driven Centre of Excellence promoted by the Arab Ministers of Environment (Damascus Convention, 1991), with the support of the United Nations Development Programme, and the Arab Fund for Economic and Social Development. It works on water and land management as well as environmental governance issues.

*CMI*⁶⁰

The Center for Mediterranean Integration (CMI) a Marseille-based platform that brings together two major International Financial Institutions (World Bank, European Investment Bank), nine national Governments (Egypt, Greece, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Palestine, Tunisia, France and Italy) as well as two local authorities (City of Marseille, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur Region). It addresses a wide range of regional public goods issues related to education, refugees, mobility, climate change and cities with a special focus on youth. It published the report "Towards Green Growth in the Mediterranean"⁶¹ in 2012, highlighting the negative impact of environmental pollution and the positive socio-economic benefits of investing in green sectors.

1.4.2 Civil Society Organizations (CSO)

The Mediterranean hosts a number of regional organizations that have been working in the field of culture, economy and environment for decades. They actively contribute to the development and implementation of Green Economy and Sustainable Development strategies, through direct technical contributions, awareness raising and stakeholders' engagement. Some that are more active in GE/SD issues are detailed below.

*MIO-ECSDE*⁶²

The Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development (MIO-ECSDE) is a non-profit Federation of over 130 Mediterranean Non-Governmental Organizations working in the fields of Environment and Development in the Euro-Mediterranean area. It is a technical and political platform promoting the sustainable management of natural resources, waste, eco-systems, biodiversity, and cultural diversity.

In recent years MIO-ECSDE has made more concrete and intensified efforts to promote the pivotal shift towards a Green Economy in the Mediterranean. Together with SCP/RAC and within the framework of the Horizon 2020 Initiative for a Cleaner Mediterranean, it has carried out capacity building workshops and field visits on green economy and explored how national strategies can be developed and implemented through sustainable financing and green banking. The necessary actions to create the enabling environment and necessary momentum towards a Green Economy in the Mediterranean include the identification and eradication of what is generally agreed on as unsustainable in order to alleviate/reduce the pressures; the encouragement of the development and rapid implementation of no regret measures; the utilization in a wise and sustainable way of all natural and cultural assets.

58 <http://www.rcreee.org/>

59 <http://web.cedare.org/>

60 <http://www.cmimarseille.org/>

61 <http://www.cmimarseille.org/knowledge-library/towards-green-growth-mediterranean-countries-full-report>

62 <http://mio-ecsde.org/>

RAED⁶³

RAED was established in 1990 as an umbrella organisation aiming to meet the actual needs of NGOs in the different Arab Countries and making them effective actors in addressing environment and sustainable development challenges. The Arab League recognized RAED in 1995 as a representative of civil society in the Council of Arab Ministers Responsible for the Environment (CAMRE) and Council of Arab Ministers Responsible for Water Resources. After launching the Egyptian Sustainable Development Forum (ESDF) in 2012, which acts as a “think tank” to facilitate a process of dialogue among different stakeholders and determine the policy gaps in relation to legislation, strategies and national planning to achieve sustainability, RAED is trying to replicate the mechanism in other countries as well.

ASCAME⁶⁴

The Association of the Mediterranean Chambers of Commerce and Industry (ASCAME) is a non-profit international organization that represents the private sector of the Mediterranean, regrouping the Chambers of Commerce and Industry and similar entities of both shores of the region. It gathers more than 300 Chambers of Commerce and Industry and defends the interests of the millions of businesses across the Mediterranean region. It participates in several regional projects promoting renewable energy, sustainable tourism, water and natural resources management.

Other actors

Many other organizations also have a relevant role to promote GE/SD in the Mediterranean region thanks to their technical expertise, networking capability or political strength. A non-exhaustive list is mentioned here: Anima Network⁶⁵, FEMISE⁶⁶, IEMed⁶⁷, IPEMED⁶⁸, OCEMO⁶⁹, Global Footprint Network⁷⁰, IUCN⁷¹, etc.

1.4.3 Regional initiatives and projects

In recent years, apart from the Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) adopted by the Contracting Parties of the Barcelona Convention in 2005 and updated in 2016 (see 1.4.1), a diverse number of initiatives, mechanisms, projects and programs contributing to sustainable development have been launched at regional level, usually financed and promoted by international and intergovernmental institutions. A selection of the most relevant ones for GE/SD follows.

Horizon 2020⁷²

The Horizon 2020 Initiative for a Cleaner Mediterranean aims at tackling by 2020 the sources of pollution that are said to account for around 80% of the overall pollution of the Mediterranean Sea: municipal waste, urban wastewater and industrial pollution. Its actions focus on capacity building of stakeholders, financing of infrastructures that address the region’s major environmental hot spots, improvement of environmental monitoring, and research. The Horizon2020 Initiative supports and complements the implementation of the commitments under the Barcelona Convention and has also been integrated into the priorities and work of the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) thereby becoming a joint endeavour and commitment of all 43 UfM countries.

The need to integrate green economy principles in the Horizon2020 Initiative’s work programme was recognized by the UfM Ministers in charge of Environment and Climate Change in 2014. By calling for strengthening its pollution prevention dimension, Ministers are acknowledging the crucial role of green economy principles and sustainable consumption and production (SCP) patterns to prevent the further deterioration of the Mediterranean Sea as well as to ensure the sustainability of results (including pollution abatement investments).

MSESD⁷³

The Mediterranean Strategy on Education for Sustainable Development (MSESD) was formally endorsed in May 2014, in Athens, by the Ministers of the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) in charge of Environment and Climate Change. MSESD

63 <http://www.raednetwork.org>

64 <http://www.ascame.org/>

65 <http://www.animaweb.org/fr>

66 <http://www.femise.org/>

67 <http://www.iemed.org/>

68 <http://www.ipemed.coop/>

69 <http://www.ocemo.org>

70 <http://www.footprintnetwork.org>

71 <http://www.iucn.org/>

72 <http://www.h2020.net/>

73 <http://www.medies.net/articles.asp?cID=27&aID=760>

is a contribution of the Mediterranean region to the UN Decade on ESD and its post-2015 phase. In their Declaration, the UfM Ministers highlighted the cross-sectorial nature of environment and climate change challenges and the importance of fostering growth and job creation while ensuring better quality of life and a sustainable future. It was in this framework that they recognized the importance of Education and Awareness as a prerequisite to address the environment and climate-related challenges and endorsed the final text of MSES which was annexed to the Ministerial Declaration⁷⁴.

SwitchMed⁷⁵ / SCP AP

SwitchMed is a regional project financed by the European Commission and supported by UNIDO, UNEP-MAP and the SCP/RAC. It seeks to build a clean, circular and collaborative economy in southern Mediterranean countries by training stakeholders, supporting entrepreneurs and encouraging networking. It also supports policy makers to implement a regulatory and policy framework to promote sustainable products and services through the Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production for the Mediterranean (SCP AP).

The SCP AP was also approved in 2016 by the contracting parties of the Barcelona convention. Part of the SwitchMed initiative, it is supporting the development of national SCP strategies for Southern Mediterranean countries into four main economic sectors: tourism; housing and construction; goods manufacturing; food, fisheries and agriculture - all of them very relevant for the GE.⁷⁶

Blue Economy initiative⁷⁷

The Blue Economy initiative is a regional project funded by the MAVA foundation and implemented by Plan Bleu, SCP/RAC and PAP/RAC. Its objective is to identify indicators, select tools and recommend policies to promote the sustainable growth of sea-related economic activities such as fisheries, tourism, marine transport, renewable energy and sea mining. Final results will be published by the end of 2016.

MEDENEC⁷⁸

MEDENEC is a regional project funded by the European Union. It seeks to promote energy efficiency measures and renewable energy systems in buildings in Eastern and Southern countries of the Mediterranean. Its priority action is to improve the framework conditions and provide policy advice, support businesses and major national construction programs in order to reach the goal of reducing energy supply needs and the growing impact on the environment of buildings and inefficient facilities.

EDILE⁷⁹

EDILE (Economic Development through Inclusive and Local Empowerment) is a regional initiative, funded by the European Union (ENPI CBC MED programme) and coordinated by the Anima Network, to support investments with high positive spill-over effects on economic, social, environmental and community levels. The EDILE pilot phase, implemented since December 2013 in Lebanon, Palestine and Tunisia, has created operational tools to measure the local impacts of investment projects and worked on raising awareness, training, sharing good practices in terms of inclusiveness. It is now extended to Algeria, Egypt and Morocco alongside the development of the EDILE label which will allow promoting public and private investments which benefit their territories the most, in terms of local impact.

74 <http://ufmsecretariat.org/euro-mediterranean-cooperation-on-environment-and-climate-change-ufm-holds-ministerial-meeting-in-athens/>

75 <https://www.switchmed.eu/en>

76 <https://www.switchmed.eu/en/news/news-1/the-mediterranean-sustainable-consumption-and-production-scp-action-plan-has-been-finally-approved>

77 <http://www.mava-blue-economy.com/>

78 <http://www.med-enec.com>

79 <http://www.edile-initiative.org/>

2

A quick-survey of Green Economy in the Mediterranean

As already mentioned, due to finite resources, the study could not extend into assessing the *implementation* of existing GE/SD strategies, policies and initiatives and had to limit itself to assessing the existing and publically available documents. Therefore, in order to somewhat compensate for this, a short-lasting on-line survey was designed and sent to regional and national GE/SD stakeholders and practitioners in order to gain some insight on what is actually happening in the countries.

2.1 Methodology

The survey was conducted between 16 May and 2 June 2016. The database of contacts comprised of 6000 Sustainability-related practitioners from NGOs, researchers, businesses, IGOs and governments. The majority of contacts were provided by MIO-ECSDE while the GEC and eco-union complemented the list. The survey aimed to acquire information on what is being done in the field with a focus on:

- a) identifying documents or initiatives that are relevant to GE/SD in a given country, and
- b) capturing the perceptions of stakeholders on the quality and implementation of GE/SD strategies (where they exist).

A brief description of the survey and its results can be found in the following sub-chapters while the full questionnaire is available at www.medgreeneconomy.org.

2.2 Profile of respondents

A total of 339 responses were received. From one third of the countries more than 20 responses were received, for another third between 10 and 20, and for another third less than 10. Tunisia got most responses with 61 participants.

Figure 2.1: Med GE survey - Number of responses

The survey got a quite well-balanced response from men and women.

Gender / Genre (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.2: Med GE survey - Gender distribution

The large majority of respondents was over 30 years old.

Age (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.3: Med GE survey - Age distribution

Over one third of the responses came from employees of public authorities, NGOs in 2nd place.

Sector / Secteur (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.4: Med GE-survey - Sector distribution

Almost half of the respondents focused their answer on the entire Mediterranean, 36% on the national level. This means that the answers on national policies had to be analysed separately and with care.

Geographic scope / Focus géographique (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.5: Med GE survey - Geographic Scope Most of the respondents (>70%) have either an environmental/sustainability or an engineering/science background.

Academic background / Formation (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.6: Med GE survey - Academic background

About 60% of the respondents had more than 5 years of experience, 36% even more than 10 years.

Green Economy (GE) & Sustainable Development (SD) experience / Expérience en Économie Verte (EV) et Développement Durable (DD) (339 respuestas)

Figure 2.7: Med GE survey - GE/SD experience

2.3 Concepts, definitions and perceptions on implementation

According to the survey participants, the three most relevant Green Economy concepts are: environmental integrity & ecological limits, economic development & job creation and social inclusion & equity. Participation & transparency as well as ethics & justice were also voted but by fewer people. This view correlates well with the general definition of Green Economy.

According to you, what are the 3 most relevant concepts linked with Green Economy (GE)? / Selon vous, quels sont les 3 concepts clés liés à l'Économie Verte (EV) ?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.8: Most relevant GE concepts

The definition: "Improve human well-being and social equity while maintaining environmental capital" got most votes but "Promote inclusive economic growth while reducing environmental damages" and "Enhance quality of life for all within the ecological limits of the planet" were not far behind.

According to you, what would be the best definition of GE ? Selon vous, quelle est la meilleure définition de l'EV?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.9: GE definitions

National governments, businesses and local authorities are seen as main actors/drivers of a GE by the majority of respondents.

According to you, who are the 3 main actors to implement GE? Selon vous, qui sont les 3 acteurs clés pour développer l'EV?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.10: GE Main actors

The level of commitment of governments, local authorities, businesses and the financial sector is seen as either low or medium, very few see their engagement as high. The commitment of the financial sector is perceived by more than half of the respondents as low. The commitment of NGOs and scientists is perceived as medium to high.

In your country or region, what is the level of commitment on GE of the following actors? / Dans votre pays ou région, quel est le niveau d'engagement de ces acteurs sur l'EV?

Figure 2.11: Commitment of GE actors

Weak commitment of public authorities, poor technical & political capabilities and lack of financial instruments are seen as main barriers. But poor awareness of civil society and the lack of national regulatory frameworks were also voted by many.

Less important seems to be an unclear international regulatory framework. This may give a hint that national frameworks are seen as more important.

In your country or region, what are the 3 main barriers to develop GE ? / Dans votre pays ou région, quelles sont les 3 principales barrières pour développer l'EV?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.12: GE main barriers

The tools mostly used are education, financial instruments as well as public regulation and Corporate Social Responsibility alike. Green taxes and green public procurement seem to be perceived less important.

In your country or region, what are the 3 most relevant tools to promote GE / Dans votre pays ou région, quels sont les 3 outils principaux de promotion de l'EV ?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.13: Tools to promote GE

The energy sector, agriculture, waste, tourism and water are the most relevant sectors in the view of the respondents. Industry, transport and buildings are considered somewhat less relevant. It is interesting that fisheries are mentioned only by 12% of respondents, forests only by 16%. The financing sector is probably rather perceived as a supporting sector because it was mentioned only by 13%.

In your country or region, what are the 5 most relevant sectors for GE / Dans votre pays ou région, quels sont les 5 secteurs les plus pertinents pour l'EV?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.14: Most relevant sectors

About half of the respondents confirm that there is a national strategy on GE or SD.

In your country, is there any NATIONAL strategy on GE or SD ? Dans votre pays, y-a-t'il une stratégie NATIONALE sur l'EV ou le DD ?

(334 respuestas)

Figure 2.15: National strategies

But the level of uncertainty for most countries is high, except for Tunisia, Morocco, France and Jordan where the majority is sure that a national strategy exists. In many countries there are contradicting views or respondents do not know.

This shows that countries should make greater efforts to spread information about their national strategies.

In your country, is there any NATIONAL strategy on GE or SD ?
 Dans votre pays, y-a-t'il une stratégie NATIONALE sur l'EV ou le DD ?

Geographic scope / Focus géographique	Etiquetas de columna				Total
	Don't know / I No / Non	Yes / Oui	blank		
Albania / Albanie	6	11	3	1	21
Algeria / Algérie	3	10	10		23
Bosnia & Herzegovina / Bosnie-Herzégovine	1	4	1		6
Croatia / Croatie	2	5	6		13
Cyprus / Chypre			1		1
Egypt / Egypte	7	3	12	1	23
France / France	1		10		11
Greece / Grèce	10	12	7		29
Israel / Israël	1	1	7		9
Italy / Italie	5	2	4		11
Jordan / Jordanie	9	1	13		23
Lebanon / Liban	1	16	2		19
Malta / Malte		1	2		3
Montenegro / Monténégro	1		1		2
Morocco / Maroc	4	1	25		30
OTHER / AUTRE	8	6	3	2	19
Palestine / Palestine	4	5	1	1	11
Portugal / Portugal			3		3
Slovenia / Slovénie	1	1	1		3
Spain / Espagne	7	2	7		16
Tunisia / Tunisie	4	14	43		61
Turkey / Turquie	1	1			2
(en blanco)					
Total general	76	96	162	5	339

Table 2.1: GE/SD National strategies (detailed answers)

The evaluation of the quality of the national strategies is mainly considered as moderate. Note that 183 people responded to this question although only 162 answered yes in the previous question.

If positive, how do you evaluate the quality of the strategy? Si positif, comment évaluez-vous la qualité de la stratégie?

(183 respuestas)

Figure 2.16: Evaluation of national GE/SD strategies

On a country level the answers are diverse but due to the in general limited number of responses per country, the results are not representative. Only for Morocco (in general seen quite positive), Tunisia (medium) and Jordan (rather positive) were a reasonable amount of answers received.

In your country, is there any NATIONAL strategy on GE or SD ?
 Dans votre pays, y-a-t'il une stratégie NATIONALE sur l'EV ou le DD ?

Geographic scope / Focus géographique	(Todas) Yes / Oui							
Cuenta de Horodateur	Etiquetas de columna	1	2	3	4	5	blank	Total
Albania / Albanie				1	2			3
Algeria / Algérie			2	7	1			10
Bosnia & Herzegovina / Bosnie-Herzégovine				1				1
Croatia / Croatie			2	3	1			6
Cyprus / Chypre				1				1
Egypt / Egypte				8	3		1	12
France / France			3	3	3		1	10
Greece / Grèce		3	2	1			1	7
Israel / Israël		1	3	2	1			7
Italy / Italie			2	1	1			4
Jordan / Jordanie		1	1	4	4	2	1	13
Lebanon / Liban			1		1			2
Malta / Malte		1	1					2
Montenegro / Monténégro						1		1
Morocco / Maroc			4	8	12	1		25
OTHER / AUTRE				2	1			3
Palestine / Palestine				1				1
Portugal / Portugal		1		2				3
Slovenia / Slovénie			1					1
Spain / Espagne			2	4			1	7
Tunisia / Tunisie		2	10	20	6	4	1	43
Total general		9	32	70	37	8	6	162

Figure 2.17: Evaluation of national strategies (details, only respondents who answered yes in previous questions)

Note that 183 responded to this question although only 162 answered 'yes' in the previous question, so their response (i.e. evaluation) has to be considered with care.

Only one third of respondents is aware of a regional strategy, almost 20% even say that there is none. The Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) is apparently not well known.

At mediterranean level, is there is a REGIONAL strategy on GE or SD you are aware of ?
 Au niveau méditerranéen, y-a-t'il une stratégie RÉGIONALE sur l'EV ou le DD que vous connaissez?

(319 respuestas)

Figure 2.18: GE/SD regional strategy

The strategy is evaluated as fair, although it may be noted that the evaluation almost shows a normal distribution. Also here a few more responses were given than 'yes'-answers in the previous question (121 vs. 130 responses).

If yes, how do you evaluate this strategy? Si positif, comment évaluez-vous la qualité de cette stratégie?

(130 respuestas)

Figure 2.19: Evaluation of regional GE/SD strategy

The general state of GE/SD is seen fair to weak.

According to you, what is the GENERAL state of GE and SD in your country or region? Selon vous, quel est l'état GÉNÉRAL de l'EV et DD dans votre pays ou région?

(339 respuestas)

Figure 2.20: General state of GE/SD

2.4 Brown economy

The following issues related either to brown economy sectors or to unsustainable developments were mentioned in the survey (the list of countries per issue may therefore not be complete):

- Coal or other thermal power plants (Spain, Slovenia, Croatia, Montenegro, Bosnia-Herzegovina)
- Oil and gas drilling (Portugal, Croatia, Egypt, Cyprus, Israel, Italy, Spain, Tunisia, Algeria)
- Nuclear power plant projects (Turkey, France, Jordan)
- Plans for fracking (France, Algeria)
- Large hydro projects (Slovenia, Turkey, Albania)
- Road and highway projects (Algeria, Israel, Turkey, Greece, Jordan)
- Waste dumping (Lebanon, Tunisia, Albania)
- Infrastructure development for tourism (Spain, Tunisia, Croatia, Cyprus)

- Urban developments without proper planning, also in coastal areas (Morocco, Egypt, Malta)
- Use of or plans for nuclear energy (France, Jordan, Egypt)
- Mining (Greece, Morocco, Tunisia)
- Water/waste water and desalination projects (Israel, Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco, Spain, Tunisia, Croatia)
- Industries like chemical, cement, plastic, phosphor, etc. (Tunisia, Turkey, Algeria)
- Aquaculture (Tunisia)

Evaluation: A number of these activities, especially the energy related ones (oil and gas projects, fracking, coal and nuclear plants) are clearly not sustainable and may be substituted by renewables provided that narrow interests do not prevail. Policy makers have solid argumentation nowadays with costs of renewable technologies no longer being prohibitive, especially if externalities of conventional technologies are taken into account. In other sectors the issues are more complex, e.g. in the case of new roads, which can have positive impacts on mobility and short/medium term job creation but can also induce traffic, pollution, noise, environmental and cultural encroachment, etc.

3

Assessment of published national strategies in the Mediterranean

3.1 Overall methodology

The methodology used in this study to assess published national strategies has applied the following four steps:

- 1. Identifying the national GE/SD strategies:** The multi-disciplinary team examined in-depth the main strategy documents related to Green Economy and Sustainability in each country of the Mediterranean. The accessibility to these documents was considered as an indicator of how well the topic is established in the country. Feedback received through the survey and the stakeholder workshop served as an additional check to take the right literature into consideration.
- 2. Analysing the primary data/information:** An Excel template was designed to capture the key information of the document, i.e. the issuing organisation (ministry, agency, ...), year, revision date, number of pages, process of its elaboration (top-down or bottom-up, stakeholder involvement), fields covered, indicators, monitoring, etc.
- 3. Evaluating the primary data:** The evaluation was done in a way whereby it considers the various concepts and key points that make up a Green Economy as described in Chapter 1. Especially the assessment of the quality of the content (e.g. what is actually said about, for instance, the future energy supply) is done in accordance with the vision of an inclusive Green Economy that respects the Earth's limits.

The information was evaluated via a simple scheme between one and five points according to pre-defined criteria. A 'traffic light' colour coding helps to visualize the evaluation. Using only the three colours helps simplify the message while the points with decimals allow for some graduation between countries and criteria.

- 1,0 to 1,9 points: Rather weak, red colour
- 2,0 to 3,9 points: Fair or moderate, yellow colour
- 4,0 to 5 green: Good or very good, green colour
- 0: No information available, grey colour

The aim is to clarify if the different issues are described to an extent that shows that all relevant aspects have been duly considered; that the content is convincing and well explained.

The criteria have not been weighted, as this would have made the task very complex without providing additional insights. The overall average score determines in which category a country's strategy falls (good, moderate, weak). The thresholds chosen may be debatable; however, the authors are of the opinion that the strategies within the same category are comparable regarding their quality and relevance.

4. **Considering the Survey results – getting feedback from key stakeholders:** The survey allowed a) identifying additional documents or initiatives that are relevant for Green Economy / Sustainable Development in a given country and b) capturing the perceptions of stakeholders on the quality and implementation of a GE/SD strategy (if it exists).
5. **Organising a Workshop with selected stakeholders and experts:** A workshop with some 20 Green Economy experts and stakeholders was held in Tangier, Morocco, back-to-back to the MEDCOP 2016 meeting in order to get direct feedback on the first draft of the report. Comments regarding individual countries and inputs from the discussion were used to strengthen the report.

3.2 Limitations of the methodological approach

Limits of interpretation of results / country performance comparison: It is important to note that this report is *not* evaluating the state of Green Economy (or the “green-ness of the economy”) in the Mediterranean region. This would be done through another set of indicators, e.g. the ones proposed by the Green Growth Knowledge Platform whose indicators are shown for information only for each country assessed (see also section 3.4).

This report only intends to evaluate Green Economy strategies (or strategy documents) developed in the Mediterranean region. Therefore, this study cannot be used to compare countries' GE performance. For instance, a country may have a rather weak or even no specific strategy on Green Economy, while its performance regarding GE/SD indicators can be quite good, be it for successful sectorial policies, general awareness of people and government on SD related issues, status of development, etc. The results of this study can be used as necessary additional information in a country's GE performance assessment.

Potentially incomplete capturing of sectorial strategies: In general, we assume that countries would (or should) have one national strategy on GE/SD. Basing the evaluation on one or a few main documents and websites may not give a full picture of all activities carried out in a country. Certain countries may have developed a sectorial approach where GE/SD strategies are described and implemented only for certain sectors, like agriculture or energy, due to progressive leadership in these sectors or due to political constraints in other sectors. In this case, a weak result in the overall evaluation may be unfair. However, as the aim of the study is to give an overview of national strategies, it must also be assumed that there is no strong overall national leadership across sectors if no or a weak national strategy can be found.

The methodology does not consider the specific national context. Choices of green policies depend on many factors including the socioeconomic situation which can be affected by one or many other realities (terrorism, conflicts, migration, revolution, etc.). In certain countries job creation may have priority, in others national security. The extent to which unpopular or daring decisions can be taken by a government (e.g. phasing out fossil fuel subsidies) depends on the degree of its stability and political strength. There is much fluctuation among countries in the region. Furthermore, the existing natural assets of a country play a role when defining a GE strategy. This study has not further examined these country-specific aspects.

Mitigation: The limitations of the study are highlighted in all relevant chapters and communication material in order to avoid misperceptions.

Disclaimer: The publication includes data that was available up till the end of June 2016. Although we tried our best to assess all information consistently and ensure a precision in how the findings are documented, there will still be mistakes found in the following section. We apologize for any inconvenience that this may cause.

3.3 Overview of national strategies' assessment

3.3.1 Assessment table

The following table shows the result of the assessment and the comparison of countries:

Criteria	Albania 1	Algeria 2	Bosnia 3	Croatia 4	Cyprus 5	Egypt 6	France 7	Greece 8	Israel 9
Background	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Prepared by / Published by	4.0	4.0	3.0	4.0		4.0	4.0	5.0	4.0
Political backing	5.0	4.0	2.0	5.0		5.0	4.0	4.0	5.0
Level (national, regional, local)	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.5	4.0
History / background / key hits	4.0	5.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0
Website English version	5.0	1.0	1.5	5.0	5.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	5.0
Local language version	4.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0
First Date of publication	5.0	3.0	3.0	2.5	2.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0
Last update	5.0	3.5	3.0		2.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0
Planned follow-up	5.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	5.0	4.0
N° of pages (total, core, annex)	5.0	5.0	5.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	2.0
Number and description of goals	4.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.0	2.5	5.0	3.0	3.5
Number of indicators defined	2.0	2.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	3.5
Budget associated	1.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.5
Time line	4.0	2.5	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Stakeholder involvement	3.0	2.0	3.5	2.0	1.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	4.0
Document versions	0.0	3.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	2.0	1.0	3.5
Associated laws	4.0	5.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	3.5	5.0
3rd party assessment available	2.0		2.0			3.0		2.0	
References to ecological limits	2.5	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	3.0	4.0
Focus on local activities	1.5	2.0	4.0	2.0	1.0	3.0	5.0	3.5	4.0
Link to SDGs	4.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Average	3.3	3.1	3.0	3.1	2.6	3.6	4.1	3.5	4.2
Tools									
Green Procurment	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	1.5	5.0
Green Tax Policy	2.5	4.0	1.0	1.0	3.5	1.0	4.0	3.0	4.0
Total									
Sectors covered									
Agriculture	3.5	3.5	4.0	4.0	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	2.0
Fisheries	3.0	5.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	2.5
Forests	4.0	3.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	1.0
Renewable Energy	3.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	2.0
Manufacturing & industry	3.0	3.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.5	2.0	2.0	2.5
Waste	4.0	5.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	3.5	2.5
Buildings	1.0	1.5	1.0	2.0	1.0	3.5	2.0	1.5	2.5
Transport	1.0	1.5	2.0	5.0	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.0	2.0
Tourism	3.5	3.0	4.0	3.0	1.0	3.5	1.0	2.0	2.0
Cities	2.0	3.5	3.0	2.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Land and coastal management	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	1.0	3.0	3.5	2.0
Finance	1.0	5.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	5.0	0.0	2.0
Total	2.8	3.7	2.7	3.2	2.2	2.3	2.9	2.7	2.1
Sectors: Qualitative evaluation									
Agriculture: Quality	3.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
Fisheries: Quality	1.5	4.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.5	1.0
Water (rivers, sea, ...): Quality	3.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	1.0	1.5	3.5	3.0	3.5
Forests: Quality	3.5	4.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	1.0
Renewable Energy: Quality	2.0	2.5	1.5	4.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	2.0
Manufacturing & industry: Quality	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	3.5	4.0	2.0	3.5
Waste: Quality	3.0	2.5	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	2.5	4.0
Buildings: Quality	1.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	4.0
Transport: Quality	2.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	2.5	4.5	2.0	4.0
Tourism: Quality	2.0	3.5	4.5	3.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	1.0
Cities: Quality	2.5	2.5	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	4.5	3.5	4.0
Land and coastal management: Quality	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.5	3.5	1.0	5.0	3.5	2.0
Finance: Quality	1.0	3.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	1.5	2.5
Total	2.4	2.9	2.4	2.9	1.7	1.9	3.3	2.7	2.7
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics									
Governance & civil society engagement	2.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	3.5	5.0	2.0	3.0
Education and Training	2.5	3.0	4.0	3.5	4.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	3.0
Research and Innovation	2.0	3.0	2.0	3.5	4.5	3.5	5.0	2.0	3.0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	2.0	1.5	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.5	3.5	3.0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	1.5	2.0	3.0
Others: Health, others	3.0		3.5	5.0	5.0	3.5		3.0	3.0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	1.0	3.0		5.0	3.0			1.0	5.0
Total	1.9	2.6	2.4	3.1	2.8	2.8	3.8	2.5	3.3
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors - Quality									
Governance & civil society: Quality	2.5	2.5	3.0	3.0	1.0	2.5	4.0	2.0	3.5
Education and Training: Quality	2.5	3.0	2.0	4.0	3.5	2.5	5.0	3.0	3.0
Research and Innovation: Quality	1.0	2.5	1.0	2.0	2.0	2.5	3.0	1.0	3.5
Assessment of ecosystem services: Quality	2.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	1.5
Green Jobs & entrepreneurship: Quality	1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.5	4.0
Others: Health, others: Quality	2.5					2.5		0.0	
Total	2.0	2.0	1.8	2.2	1.7	2.2	4.0	1.6	3.1
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)									
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	2.0	4.0	3.0	3.0	1.0	3.0	5.0	2.5	3.5
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	3.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	3.5
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2.0	1.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	1.5	5.0	2.5	3.0
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	2.0	1.5	3.0	0.0	3.0
5 Policy design and implementation	2.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
6 Mobilizing investment	2.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.5
7 Public-private collaboration	3.0	3.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	2.5	2.0
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	2.0	4.0	0.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	2.5	3.0
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	3.5	1.5	3.0	2.5	3.0
Total	2.3	2.4	2.8	3.6	2.6	2.3	3.9	2.3	3.1
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2.6	2.9	2.6	3.0	2.3	2.6	3.6	2.8	3.2

Italy	Jordan	Lebanon	Malta	Montenegro	Morocco	Palestine	Portugal	Slovenia	Spain	Tunisia	Turkey	Average
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	
4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.1
4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	4.3
5.0	4.5	4.5	5.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.5
5.0	4.0	3.5	3.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.2
3.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	2.5	5.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	3.3
5.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	3.5	4.0	3.9
1.0	3.0	5.0		1.0	4.0	4.0	5.0		1.0	4.0	3.0	3.4
1.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	2.0	4.0	4.0	5.0		1.0	4.0	4.0	3.8
1.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.3
3.0	1.0	3.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	3.5	1.0	3.4
5.0	4.5	4.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.1
5.0	4.0	3.5		5.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	1.0	3.5
1.0	2.0	4.0		3.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	2.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.2
5.0	3.5	5.0	4.0	1.0	4.5	1.5	5.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.9
2.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	3.0	3.5	5.0	5.0	1.0	4.0	3.5	3.3
2.0	1.0	3.0	3.0	2.0	2.0		2.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.9
	4.0	5.0	3.5	3.0	4.5	2.5	5.0	4.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.6
					3.0	2.0				2.0	4.0	2.5
5.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	2.0	3.0	2.5	5.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.3
5.0	2.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	2.0	2.0	1.0	2.5	3.0	3.1
2.0	4.0	3.0	2.0	2.5	5.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	5.0	3.0	3.0
3.4	3.5	4.2	3.9	3.2	3.9	3.4	3.9	3.2	2.7	3.6	3.2	3.4
1.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	1.0	3.0	1.5	5.0	3.5	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.4
4.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	2.0	4.0	2.0	5.0	3.5	4.0	1.0	1.0	2.8
4.5	3.5	1.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	3.5	3.5
4.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	5.0	0.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.0	2.1
5.0	4.0	2.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	2.5	5.0	5.0	2.5	3.6
3.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	3.0	2.9
5.0	3.0	2.5	4.0	4.0	5.0	2.5	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	3.9
2.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	1.5	5.0	3.0	2.9
5.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	2.5	5.0	3.5	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.7
3.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	2.5
5.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	3.3
4.5	3.5	1.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	1.5	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	1.0	3.2
5.0	3.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	2.5	4.0	5.0	1.0	3.1
5.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	4.0	5.0	2.5	5.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	3.5
3.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	3.5	5.0	2.0	4.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	3.0	2.6
4.2	3.2	1.8	3.2	4.0	5.0	2.0	4.6	2.8	3.6	4.5	2.4	3.2
4.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.5	2.5	4.0	4.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.5	0.0	3.0	1.0	3.5	2.5	1.0	1.8
5.0	4.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	4.0	5.0	4.0	3.5
4.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	3.1
2.0	3.0	3.0	1.5	3.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	2.7
2.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	1.5	4.0	2.0	3.5	1.0	1.0	3.0	3.0	2.4
2.0	4.0	3.5	4.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	2.0	2.0	3.5	3.5	3.0
2.5	2.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	2.5	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.5	4.0	1.0	2.2
5.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	4.5	3.5	4.0	3.1
2.0	4.0	1.0	3.5	4.5	4.0	1.5	4.5	3.5	2.5	3.5	1.0	2.7
3.5	2.5	1.0	2.0	1.0	4.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	3.5	4.0	3.0	2.8
5.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	2.5	4.5	3.5	3.0	4.5	3.5	3.6
3.0	3.0	4.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	2.5	4.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	2.4
3.2	3.0	2.0	2.8	2.8	4.0	2.1	4.2	2.5	2.8	3.5	2.8	2.8
3.5	3.0	3.5	2.0	4.0	5.0	2.5	4.0	2.0	1.0	5.0	3.5	3.1
4.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	5.0	3.5	3.6
4.0	3.0	2.5	3.5	4.0	5.0	1.5	4.0	2.0	1.5	5.0	3.5	3.2
1.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.8
1.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.8
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	1.0	3.5	4.0	3.0	5.0	5.0	3.0	3.1
	3.0		2.0		5.0				3.0	5.0		3.3
2.4	2.6	2.5	2.8	3.0	3.9	2.1	4.0	1.8	2.1	3.9	2.6	2.8
3.0	4.0	4.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	1.5	2.0	3.5	3.5	3.0
5.0	3.0	4.0	4.5	4.0	4.0	2.5	4.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	3.5
4.0	2.5	2.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	1.5	4.0	2.5	2.0	3.5	3.5	2.5
3.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	1.9
3.0	0.0	3.5	4.0	1.0	4.0	2.5	4.0	2.0	1.0	1.5	1.5	2.1
3.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	1.0		3.0	3.0	2.6
3.5	2.9	2.6	2.4	2.5	3.5	2.4	4.5	2.0	1.8	2.8	2.8	2.6
3.5	4.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	4.5	3.0	4.0	1.5	1.0	4.5	3.5	3.2
5.0	4.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.0	3.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	3.7
5.0	3.5	3.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	1.5	5.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.2
3.0		3.0	3.0	1.0	4.5	0.0	5.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	2.0	2.4
4.0	2.5	2.0	5.0	4.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	3.5	3.3
1.0	3.5	3.5	2.0	3.0	3.0	1.5	5.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.3
2.0	3.5	3.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	4.0	4.0	2.0	1.0	4.0	3.5	3.0
5.0		3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	2.0	4.0	3.0	1.0	3.5	3.5	3.2
5.0	4.0	2.0		4.0	4.5	4.0	3.0	1.5	3.5	3.0	3.5	3.2
3.7	3.8	2.6	3.8	3.1	4.2	2.6	4.3	2.2	2.4	2.9	2.8	3.0
3.4	3.1	2.8	3.3	3.1	4.1	2.5	4.2	2.6	2.7	3.5	2.8	3.0

Table 3.1: Results of the assessment of the national strategies

3.3.2 Evaluation criteria

The following table shows the evaluation criteria used to assess the national strategies:

Criteria	Criteria definition and weighting
Prepared by / Published by	5: President; 4: Ministry; 3: other
Political backing	5: President or similar; 4: Minister; 3: State Secretary; 2: some kind of Commission
Level (national, regional, local)	5: National with regional specifications; 4: national; 3: regional/local
History / background	5: More than 10 years of GE / SD strategies in consistent way; 4: 5-10 years of GE strategy; 3: < 5 years; 2: < 2 years, 1: not clear
Website English version	5: Exhaustive English website with as many links as the local one; 4: most key documents translated into English; 3: some documents translated; 2: only general info in English; 1: no English website
Local language version	5: Exhaustive website with many links and background info; 4: clearly structured site with good info; 3: site ok but not everything clear, parts missing; 2: somewhat messy, not updated; 1: no website
First Date of publication	5: 2015 or 2016; 4: 2013-14; 3: 2010-12; 2: 2006-09; 1: older
Last update	5: 2015 or 2016; 4: 2013-14; 3: 2010-12; 2: 2006-09; 1: older
When is the next follow-up planned?	Depending on last update. 5: not later than 3 years after last update; 4: 4-5 years later; 3: 6-7 years, 2: later; 1: not planned
N° of pages (total, core, annex)	5: > 100 pages plus annexes and other documents; 4: > 100 pages, annexes, no other docs; 3: around 100 pages, 2: less than 70 pages, 1: shorter
Number and description of goals	5: Exhaustive explanation on several pages, several goals; 4: good explanation; 3: reasonable explanation; 2: goals not clearly defined; 1: very fuzzy;
Number of indicators defined	5: Over 70 indicators, clearly defined; 4: 30-70 indicators, well defined; 3: < 30 indicators, rough definition; 2: few indicators, 1: no indicators
Budget associated	5: Clear budget per goal or subject, earmarked and approved; 4: budget mentioned for main goals and overall; 3: overall budget estimation with some planning; 2: only rough mentioning; 1: no mention
Time line	5: 2050 clearly mentioned, concrete until 2020/2030; 4: clear until 2020 at least; 3: < 2020; 2: < 2018; 1: outdated
Governance: How are stakeholders involved in the development, implementation and monitoring? How has the policy/strategy been developed (top-down, bottom-up, ...)?	5: Large list of stakeholders incl. NGOs, etc., clearly described and their participation proven; clear bottom up approach with support from highest level; 4: stakeholders defined and process of participation described; bottom-up/top-down mixture; 3: stakeholders mentioned but not defined; 2: few stakeholders, or only isolated mentioning; mainly top-down; 1: no stakeholders mentioned
Are there different versions of the document for different stakeholders (executive summary, fact-sheet, broken down to sectors, etc.)?	5: Many different documents with different focus, showing clear commitment; 4: several special sub-documents; 3: few documents; 2: only 1 document with annex; 1: one short document
Are there laws associated? Which ones? Have they been approved already?	5: Several laws linked to the strategy, already in place; 4: laws linked, mainly planned; 3: few laws planned, not so clear; 2: vague ideas; 1: no laws
Is there any independent assessment made by third parties (e.g. NGOs)?	5: Several independent assessments, majority positive; 4: at least one positive assessment; 3: one assessment, mixed comments; 2: no or negative assessment; 1: bad assessment only
Are there references to ecological limits, planetary limits, finite resources, sufficiency?	5: Clear focus on ecological limits, growth as GDP growth not a goal; 4: limits are recognized; 3: limits mentioned but growth important; 2: limits not mentioned; 1: nature is purely only a resource for human use
Do they foster small scale, local economic activities, e.g. also community renewables, local businesses, community ownership, empowerment?	5: Focus on community businesses; 4: focus on both community and large business; 3: mainly large business focus; 2: almost only large business; 1: no mention of small business
Are the SDGs covered or linked? Active equity or green economy process?	5: SDGs already fully incorporated, all well linked; 4: SDGs mentioned and tried to be linked; 3: SDGs only partially mentioned; 2: SDG similar goals mentioned; 1: No reference at all

Criteria	Criteria definition and weighting
Tools	
Green Procurement	5: Exhaustive explanation on several pages, several goals, several indicators; 4: good explanation, 1 goal, several indicators; 3: reasonable explanation, at least 1 goal and 1 indicator; 2: short explanation, goals and indicators not so clear; 1: not mentioned or very poorly
Green Tax Policy	
Sectors covered (adapted from UNEP GE report)	
Agriculture	5: Exhaustive explanation on several pages, several goals, several indicators; 4: good explanation, 1 goal, several indicators; 3: reasonable explanation, at least 1 goal and 1 indicator; 2: short explanation, goals and indicators not so clear; 1: not mentioned or very poorly
Fisheries	
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	
Forests	
Renewable Energy	
Manufacturing & Industry	
Waste	
Buildings	
Transport	
Tourism	
Cities	
Land and coastal management	
Finance	
Sectors covered: Qualitative evaluation	For the qualitative assessment the criteria to achieve 5 points are described. Fewer points are given at the discretion of the reviewer.
Agriculture: Quality	5: a) Clear promotion of organic agriculture, b) food sovereignty / local supply, c) no GMO (Genetically Modified Organisms); 4: Only 2 of the 3 items are described
Fisheries: Quality	5: Only artisanal fisheries are supported, strict quota schemes aligned with scientific recommendations, only organic aquaculture if any, zero fish discard
Water (rivers, sea, ...): Quality	5: Strict environmental rules for water basins, re-use of waste and rainwater, high coverage of sewage plants
Forests: Quality	5: Sustainable forest management, fire vigilance, controlled use of biomass, biodiversity management
Renewable Energy: Quality	5: Focus on both large and small scale RE, specifically self-consumption, community ownership, distributed energy
Manufacturing & Industry: Quality	5: Eco-design, cradle-to-cradle, industrial symbiosis, SME support, extended product responsibility (against obsolescence), lifecycle assessments, ...
Waste: Quality	5: Zero waste policy, reuse-reduce-recycle concept, plastic (bags) ban, circular economy
Buildings: Quality	5: Net Zero Energy Buildings, Passive House, green certification (LEED, GBC, ...), Lifecycle approach, traditional construction know-how, energy certification, sustainable materials, social housing
Transport: Quality	5: Public transport, electric vehicles, bikes, trains, pedestrians, intermodality, carbon tax, no fossil fuel subsidies
Tourism: Quality	5: Eco-tourism, small scale, local business, rural tourism, responsible tourism, tourism carrying capacities, impact assessment, participatory processes, protection of cultural and natural heritage
Cities: Quality	5: Sustainable urban planning, green corridors, energy autonomy, waste management, public transport, compact cities
Land and coastal management: Quality	5: Ecosystem approach, spatial planning, protection of natural areas, no soil degradation, soil sealing, biodiversity management
Finance: Quality	5: Greening of financial sector (green loans, bonds, banks, ...), financing for both small and large projects, financing of green/social businesses, ban on financing high carbon emission projects (airports, highways, coal plants, mining)

Criteria	Criteria definition and weighting
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics	5: Exhaustive explanation on several pages, several goals, several indicators; 4: good explanation, 1 goal, several indicators; 3: reasonable explanation, at least 1 goal and 1 indicator; 2: short explanation, goals and indicators not so clear; 1: not mentioned or very poorly
Governance & civil society engagement	5: Exhaustive explanation on several pages, several goals, several indicators; 4: good explanation, 1 goal, several indicators; 3: reasonable explanation, at least 1 goal and 1 indicator; 2: short explanation, goals and indicators not so clear; 1: not mentioned or very poorly
Education and Training	
Research and Innovation	
Assessment / Management of ecosystem services	
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	
Others: Health, etc.	
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics: Quality	For the qualitative assessment the criteria to achieve 5 points are described. Fewer points are given at the discretion of the reviewer.
Governance & civil society engagement: Quality	5: Participatory process with independent multi-stakeholder monitoring committees and processes
Education and Training: Quality	5: Green skills and education for sustainable development at universities, schools, training centres, life-long-learning offerings
Research and Innovation: Quality	5: Clean tech strategy, Green patents, Green R&D strategy
Assessment / Management of ecosystem services: Quality	5: Valuing of eco-system services, e.g. TEEB (The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity)
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship: Quality	5: Green jobs strategy, green skills, support for social and green entrepreneurship, incubators, clusters, networking
Others: Health, etc.: Quality	
Evaluation applying GGBP (Green Growth Best Practice Report) criteria (adapted)	5: Exhaustively covered in dedicated chapter, detailed goals and indicators; 4: well covered, at least one goal and several indicators; 3: reasonably well described with goal and indicator; 2: mentioned but with few or not convincing indicators; 1: not mentioned or poorly so
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	5: Exhaustively covered in dedicated chapter, detailed goals and indicators; 4: well covered, at least one goal and several indicators; 3: reasonably well described with goal and indicator; 2: mentioned but with few or not convincing indicators; 1: not mentioned or poorly so
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	
3 Assessing and communicating benefits of green economy	
4 Prioritization and mainstreaming of green economy options and pathways	
5 Policy design and implementation	
6 Mobilizing investment	
7 Public-private collaboration	
8 Integrating sub-national, local and private action	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	

Table 3.2: Evaluation criteria used to assess the national strategies

3.3.3 Overall findings

- In almost all countries the strategic documents have been developed at a high political level, i.e. by national ministries, and they are – at least on paper – backed by ministers or even the presidents of the countries.
- In most cases only one version of the document could be found, i.e. there seem to be few versions that are broken down to specific stakeholder groups or sectors – if those exist they are at least not transparently linked to the national strategy.
- Compared to other sectors, renewable energy is mentioned in almost all documents, even if the quality of how the renewable strategies are described in general is rather mediocre.

- The way strategies deal with fisheries and aquaculture is rather weak, i.e. this sector is not covered by many countries and in the cases it is mentioned, strategies are not necessarily sustainable.
- The assessment and sustainable management of ecosystem services is missing in many strategies.
- Green jobs and green entrepreneurship are rather poorly covered or not even mentioned. This is somewhat surprising as they should be at the forefront of a Green Economy. Even if strategies rather focus on sustainable development, sustainable jobs would be expected to play a more important role.

3.3.4 Summary of country assessment results

The following figure gives an overview of the results of the assessment. We cluster the country strategies in three groups (good, moderate, weak) using each country's average total score. It should be noted again that it is debatable in which group a country's strategy falls (considering the caveats mentioned above).

Figure 3.1: Results of the assessment of published national green economy and sustainable development strategies.

The following table summarizes the findings for each country's strategy.

Country	Name of Strategy	Summary of evaluation
Portugal	- Green Growth Commitment (2015)	Portugal's Green Growth Commitment is good because it is very recent (2015), it focuses on Green Economy, the goals are clear and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal. It is a complete document that covers well all the sectors of the economy.
Morocco	- National Strategy for Sustainable Development (2015-2020)	Morocco's National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2015-2020 is good because it is relevant and directly linked to the SDGs with a clear focus on Green Economy. The goals are clear and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal, it is a complete document that covers well all the sectors of the economy and it is a real framework for policies in Morocco.
France	- National Strategy of Sustainable Development (2015-2020) - Law on Energy transition (2015)	France's National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2015-2020 is good because it is a very complete and relevant framework for policies. The goals are clear and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal. All the sectors are well covered except tourism and fisheries.
Tunisia	- National Strategy of Sustainable Development (2014-2020)	Tunisia's National Sustainable Development Strategy 2014-2020 is good because it is recent, relevant and directly linked to the SDGs. It is a complete strategy and a real framework for policies in Tunisia. Fishery, Finance and Green Jobs are not well covered though.

Country	Name of Strategy	Summary of evaluation
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental legislation for measures to promote green economy and the reduce the excessive use of natural resources (2015) - Environmental Action Strategy for Sustainable Development in Italy (2002) 	Italy has a good strategy because in 2015 it published a law on Green Economy, which is very relevant and sets up a real framework policy to develop GE measures in Italy. The National Strategy for Sustainable Development published in 2002 is outdated but complete and detailed with sustainability relevant measures.
Malta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greening our economy- Achieving a sustainable future (2015) 	Malta's strategy is moderate because the government has still not approved it. A consultation document called "Greening our Economy – Achieving a sustainable future" was recently published. In case this document gets approval, it will be a good basis for a Green Economy strategy even if it needs to be completed (e.g. by adding monitoring indicators).
Israel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SCP Roadmap for Israel (2014) - Connecting the economy to the environment in Israel (2014) 	Israel's strategy is moderate because - even if they have been showing a real interest in GE, SCP or SD issues for years now – their policy documents are rather weak and short, the goals are not clear and many sectors of the economy are not covered or covered in a general way. There is no real framework for policies and there are no indicators. The Green Growth Action Plan 2012-2020 announced in the GE document has never been approved.
Montenegro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Strategy for Sustainable Development (2007-2012) 	<p>Montenegro's National Strategy for Sustainable Development is moderate because it is quite old (*) and some goals are outdated . Nevertheless, this strategy document is reasonably well done and covers all the sectors of the economy in an interesting way.</p> <p><i>* After closure of the project the authors were informed that a new strategy was underway.</i></p>
Jordan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jordan National Agenda (2006-2015) - Strategic Plan: Ministry of Environment (2014-2016) - The National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2015-2020) 	Jordan's strategy is considered moderate . Even if the country does not have a specific GE strategy, Jordan shows a clear intention of pursuing more sustainable development plans. It has incorporated the principle of SD in its specific strategies and it is currently preparing a National Green Growth Plan, which will set a cross-sectorial GE framework.
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategy for sustainable development of the republic of Croatia (2009) 	Croatia's National Strategy for Sustainable Development published in 2009 is moderate ; it is well written but quite short and would require an update.
Algeria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Plan of Action for Environment and Sustainable Development 2002-2011 - National Strategy for an Integrated Management of Coastal Areas (2015) - Sectorial policies : Law on the promotion of renewable energy in the context of sustainable development (2004), Development program for energy efficiency by 2030 (2015), National Plan for Water (2015), Policy for Agricultural and Rural Renewal in Algeria (2010). 	Algeria's strategy is moderate because the National Action Plan for the Environment and Sustainable Development is weak and outdated for 5 years now. More recent sectorial policies for Agriculture, Fisheries, Renewable Energy and Water have been defined but they are not fundamentally sustainable. Nevertheless, it published in 2015 a very relevant National Strategy for an Integrated Management of Coastal Areas that covers many sectors of the economy in the areas where the big majority of the population lives.
Lebanon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable Consumption and Production Action Plan for the Industrial Sector in Lebanon (2016) 	Lebanon's strategy is considered moderate . Even if it does not have a proper National Strategy for SD or GE, it published in 2015 a National Action Plan on Sustainable Production and Consumption (SCP) focusing on the industrial sector (published with the support of the SwitchMed program). It is a quite useful document with relevant goals, but it only concerns the industrial sector.
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partnership Agreement for Development Framework 2014-2020 - Rural Development Programme 2014-2020 	Greece's strategy is considered moderate . Despite not having a relevant GE/SD strategy, it integrates the EU 2020 targets, which implies the greening of many of its sectors. An overarching GE strategy with detailed objectives, targets and indicators is needed with a much clearer picture of the commitment and potential of Greece in developing a GE.

Country	Name of Strategy	Summary of evaluation
Turkey	- Climate Change Strategy (2010-2020)	Turkey's Climate Change Strategy 2010-2020 is moderate . It is not very relevant in terms of sustainability, the goals are often unclear and some of them are outdated. At least there is a short, medium and long term vision.
Spain	- Spanish Sustainable Development Strategy (2007)	The Spanish Strategy for Sustainable Development is considered weak compared to actual standards . At the time of publication, it was well defined, but now it is too old to be really relevant. Spain has not promoted any new initiative to implement a GE or SD strategy in the last ten years.
Slovenia	- Slovenia's development strategy (2005) - Draft for the transition of Slovenia to a low carbon society by 2050 (published in 2012/2013) - Slovenian tourism development strategy (2012-2016)	Slovenia does not have a proper National Strategy for SD or GE. The development strategy sets out the vision and objectives of Slovenia's development but it is weak in terms of sustainability. In addition to this document, the government published an interesting draft for the transition of Slovenia to a low carbon society by 2050 but it is very short (10 pages). The Tourism development strategy (2012-2016) focuses poorly on sustainable tourism.
Albania	- National Strategy for Development and Integration 2015-2020 - Cross-Cutting Environmental Strategy 2015-2020	Albania's strategy is considered weak because the country does not have a proper SD/GE strategy. The recent National Strategy for Development has many objectives relating to sustainability, but with few indicators and it is hard to find specific budgets. On top of that it falls short in key sectors despite the fact that it covers several sectors with objectives that relate well to sustainability.
Bosnia-Herzegovina	- Development Strategy of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina 2010-2020 - PSRP Agricultural sector 2015-2020 - Biodiversity Strategy 2015-2020	Bosnia-Herzegovina does not have a proper GE/SD strategy. In the Development Strategy several key sectors have objectives that relate poorly to sustainability, as for instance, its commitment to continue relying on coal. Even if its strategy is weak it seems that Bosnia-Herzegovina is in the process of developing sustainable legislations and mechanisms but is at a very early stage.
Egypt	- Egypt's vision 2030 and medium term investment framework 2014-2015 / 2018-2019 (2015)	Egypt's Vision 2030 strategy document was recently published but it is considered weak . Although it presents ambitious plans for Egypt's development, it is vague on the details on how to reach its goals. Moreover, it is more a general development strategy than a specific GE or SD strategy.
Palestine	- National Development Plan 2014-2016 - National Agriculture Sector Strategy 2014-2016 - Water Sector Reform Plan 2014-2016 - National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2012-2014	Palestine's strategy is considered weak . Despite incorporating the principles of sustainable development in some strategic objectives, several sectors of the economy lack objectives that relate to GE and there is no overall GE/SD specific strategy.
Cyprus	- Sustainable Development Strategy (2007)	Cyprus's National Strategy of Sustainable Development is quite old (2007) and superficial; it is weak and hardly relevant in terms of sustainability.

Table 3.2: Summary of country assessment

3.4 Country profile indicators

3.4.1 Indicators

For each country a number of indicators are shown. They have been taken from the **Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP) website**. The original values of the GGKP country indicators are shown in the following table.⁸⁰

80 <http://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/map>, accessed 26 May 2016

Short description	Albania	Algeria	Bosnia & H.	Croatia	Cyprus	Egypt	France	Greece	Israel	Italy
Socio-Economic Context										
GDP/cap.	4.652,40	5.360,70	4.655,60	13.529,90	25.249,00	3.314,50	41.420,80	21.910,20	36.151,20	34.619,20
Population	2,77	39,20	3,83	4,25	1,14	82,10	66,00	11,00	8,06	59,80
Pop. density	101,20	16,50	75,10	76,00	123,50	82,40	120,60	85,60	372,40	203,40
Unemployment	14,70	9,80	28,20	15,80	11,80	11,90	9,90	24,20	6,90	10,70
Gini	29,00	35,30	33,00	33,60	N.A.	30,80	31,70	34,70	42,80	35,50
HDI	0,72	0,72	0,73	0,81	0,85	0,68	0,88	0,85	0,89	0,87
Natural Asset Base										
Deforestation	-0,10	0,57	0,00	-0,19	-0,09	-1,73	-0,39	-0,81	-0,07	-0,90
Freshwater withdrawal	472,70	146,00	85,90	147,80	161,20	832,40	478,90	858,50	242,40	759,00
Agricultural land	43,80	17,40	42,30	23,70	13,50	3,63	52,70	63,30	24,20	46,70
Protected areas	9,48	7,38	1,51	10,30	17,10	11,30	28,70	21,50	14,70	21,00
Environmental Productivity										
CO2/cap	1,50	3,33	8,09	4,73	6,98	2,62	5,56	7,77	9,27	6,85
Carbon productivity	2,50	0,94	0,41	2,20	2,49	0,59	6,10	2,78	2,39	4,34
Quality of Life										
Air pollution	7,67	3,19	12,30	13,50	11,10	17,50	10,70	11,60	13,20	13,30
Sanitation access	91,20	95,20	95,40	98,20	100,00	95,90	100,00	98,60	100,00	N.A.
Water access	95,70	83,90	99,60	98,60	100,00	99,30	100,00	99,80	100,00	100,00
Electricity access	N.A.	99,40	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	99,60	N.A.	N.A.	99,70	N.A.
Policies										
Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.	13,40	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	24,50	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Environm. tax	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	1,94	2,78	3,18	3,01
RES-E	100,00	0,38	46,90	60,70	1,34	9,90	13,80	18,30	0,25	25,80
Wealth changes										
Wealth change/cap	147,00	492,10	N.A.	936,90	368,90	-52,00	2.898,40	-2.099,30	2.957,80	686,10

Short description	Jordan	Lebanon	Malta	Montenegro	Morocco	Portugal	Slovenia	Spain	Tunisia	Turkey
Socio-Economic Context										
GDP/cap.	5.214,20	9.928,00	22.779,90	7.125,70	3.108,60	21.035,00	22.729,30	29.117,60	4.329,10	10.945,90
Population	6,46	4,47	0,42	0,62	33,00	10,50	2,06	46,60	10,90	74,90
Pop. density	72,80	436,70	1.322,80	46,20	74,00	114,20	102,30	93,50	70,10	97,40
Unemployment	12,20	8,90	6,40	19,60	9,00	15,60	8,80	25,20	12,80	9,20
Gini	33,70	N.A.	N.A.	30,60	40,90	N.A.	24,90	35,80	35,80	40,00
HDI	0,75	0,76	0,83	0,79	0,62	0,82	0,87	0,87	0,72	0,76
Natural Asset Base										
Deforestation	0,00	-0,45	0,00	0,00	-0,23	-0,11	-0,16	-0,68	-1,86	-1,11
Freshwater withdrawal	145,70	293,20	127,30	258,90	382,00	809,10	457,20	695,90	261,80	535,10
Agricultural land	11,70	71,70	32,20	38,10	68,10	39,70	23,80	54,00	64,90	49,90
Protected areas	0,03	0,48	2,20	12,80	19,90	14,70	54,90	25,30	4,82	2,11
Environmental Productivity										
CO2/cap	3,44	4,70	6,25	4,16	1,60	4,95	7,48	5,79	2,45	4,13
Carbon productivity	0,82	1,51	2,59	1,09	1,49	3,77	2,54	4,37	1,57	1,90
Quality of Life										
Air pollution	12,70	14,10	6,38	12,10	7,25	4,03	2,07	9,17	7,68	12,10
Sanitation access	98,10	98,30	100,00	90,00	75,40	100,00	100,00	100,00	90,40	91,20
Water access	96,10	100,00	100,00	98,00	83,60	99,80	99,60	100,00	96,80	99,70
Electricity access	99,40	99,90	N.A.	N.A.	98,90	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	99,50	N.A.
Policies										
Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Environm. tax	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	2,20	4,13	1,62	N.A.	3,63
RES-E	0,48	5,34	0,00	66,00	18,50	52,80	29,20	32,50	1,17	26,40
Wealth changes										
Wealth change/cap	258,70	-388,60	176,00	N.A.	519,70	-446,90	2.061,60	1.650,30	109,70	660,30

Table 3.3: GGKP indicators for Mediterranean countries

3.4.2 Performance related indicators – spider charts

As mentioned earlier, **the benchmarking of countries' real performance has not been the main focus of this study**. However, in order to give an idea of where Mediterranean countries stand and also to put the results of the strategy review and survey into perspective, a simple method of comparison has been applied for a number of indicators.

This method is based on the one employed by the Bertelsmann OECD SDG Index Report⁸¹ and consists of a **benchmarking against the top performers** within a given set of countries. This gives a reference point that is achievable for many countries, yet sufficiently ambitious that only a handful of countries have yet attained it.

In order to summarize country performance, **15 performance related GGKP indicators** were used. "Performance-related" means that indicators like population or hectare of agricultural land were not included. It would have been possible to use other indicators as well (like the ones used by Bertelsmann) but the GGKP indicators have the advantage that they are focused on Green Economy and are readily available⁸².

81 http://www.bertelsmann-stiftung.de/fileadmin/files/BSt/Publikationen/GrauePublikationen/Studie_NW_Sustainable-Development-Goals_Are-the-rich-countries-ready_2015.pdf

82 It should be noted though that according to stakeholder's feedback apparently not all GGKP data are up-to-date. The team refrained, however, from verifying each and every data point.

To calculate the index, the raw data for each indicator were **normalised** to the interval [0;1] using a linear transformation, with the minimum and maximum values over the observed data points as upper and lower boundaries.

Certain indicators were adjusted in a way that the higher the value, the more preferred it is; for instance a low unemployment rate is better than a high one, therefore the values had to be **inversed** (by calculating simply $1-x$ after the normalization of the values).

Indicator	Short text	Performance related	Inverse indicator	Highest value	Lowest value
Socio-Economic Context					
GDP per capita (current US\$, 2013)	GDP/cap.	x		41.420,80	3.108,60
Population (millions, 2013)	Population			82,10	0,42
Population density (people per sq. km of land area, 2013)	Pop. density			1.322,80	16,50
Unemployment (% of total labor force, 2012)	Unemployment	x	x	28,20	6,40
Gini index (index 0 to 100, 2010)	Gini	x	x	42,80	24,90
Human Development Index (index 0 to 1, 2013)	HDI	x		0,89	0,62
Natural Asset Base					
Average annual deforestation (% change in forest area, 2011)	Deforestation	x		0,57	-1,86
Annual freshwater withdrawals per capita (cubic meters, 2013)	Freshwater withdrawal	x	x	858,50	85,90
Agricultural land (% of land area, 2012)	Agricultural land			71,70	3,63
Terrestrial and marine protected areas (% of total territorial area, 2012)	Protected areas	x		54,90	0,03
Environmental and Resource Productivity					
CO2 emissions per capita (metric tons, 2010)	CO2/cap	x	x	9,27	1,50
Carbon productivity (GDP per kg of CO2 emissions, 2010)	Carbon productivity	x		6,10	0,41
Environmental Quality of Life					
Population exposure to air pollution (PM2,5) (micrograms per cubic meter, 2012)	Air pollution	x	x	17,50	2,07
Access to improved sanitation	Sanitation access	x		100,00	75,40
Access to improved water source (% of population, 2012)	Water access	x		100,00	83,60
Access to electricity	Electricity access	(x) ⁸³		99,90	98,90
Policies and economic opportunities					
Fossil fuel consumption subsidies	Fossil fuel subsidies	(x) ⁸⁴		24,50	13,40
Environmentally related tax revenue (% GDP, 2012)	Environm. tax	x		4,13	1,62
Renewable electricity (% of electricity mix, 2010)	RES-E	x		100,00	0,00
Wealth changes					
Changes in wealth per capita (US\$, 2010)	Wealth change/cap	x		2.957,80	-2.099,30

Table 3.4: GGKP indicators

The Total was calculated as an unweighted arithmetic mean of the 15 individual indicators; where no data for a certain indicator was available, the indicator was not considered in the calculation of the total. **It should be noted that the Total has to be interpreted with care as indicators are not weighted and depending on the inclusion or exclusion of certain indicators in the set, an overall ranking of countries can change considerably.**

In this report we therefore refrain from a direct comparison of the countries' total performance and just show the spider charts country by country.

83 For most Mediterranean countries no data on electricity access is given as most of them do have access. The 7 countries (Jordan, Lebanon, Israel, Egypt, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco) have values which range between 98,9 and 99,9%, so electricity access is largely given and therefore not further considered.

84 Only Algeria and Egypt have fossil fuel subsidies according to and as defined by GGKP ("The subsidies to fossil fuel consumption cover fossil fuels directly consumed by end-users or consumed as inputs to electricity generation"), therefore this indicator is not further considered. It should be noted that most countries do have fossil fuel subsidies if they are defined in a wider sense, see e.g. the OECD fossil fuel support data base, <http://www.oecd.org/site/tadffss/data/>

4 Country assessment details

4.1 Albania

4.1.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	4.652,40	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	1,50
Population [Mio]	2,77	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,50
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	101,20	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	7,67
Unemployment [%]	14,70	Sanitation Access [%]	91,20
Gini-Index	29,00	Water Access [%]	95,70
Human Development Index	0,72	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,10	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	472,70	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	43,80	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	100,00
Protected areas [%]	9,48	Wealth change/cap	147,00

4.1.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Strategy for Development and Integration 2015-2020 (NSDI II 2015-2020); Cross-Cutting Environmental Strategy 2015-2020 (CCES 2015-2020)
Main focus	General development plan; and sectorial environmental plan
Short description	This document is a national framework for policies and actions in order to achieve EU accession in a context of "strong, sustained and environmentally- friendly growth"
Prepared / Published by	Republic of Albania – Council of Ministers
Political backing	Council of Ministers
History / background	This second National Strategy for Development and Integration (NSDI II 2015-2020), is an update of NSDI 2007-2013; both lay out operating principles to ensure that policy planning and implementation are taking place in a satisfactory manner—with the general aim of implementing social measures and pursuing economic growth in order to aspire for EU integration by 2020. CCES 2015-2020 is a strategy derived from NSDI II, which further details the strategic goals in the area of environmental management.
Website English version	http://www.kryeministria.al/en
Local language version	http://www.kryeministria.al/ ; http://www.mjedisi.gov.al/al/ministria/drejtorit
First Date of publication	2016
Last update	-

4.1.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Albania's strategy is considered **weak**; the country does not have a proper SD/GE strategy. The recent National Strategy for Development has many objectives relating to sustainability, but with few indicators and it is hard to find specific budgets. On top of that it falls short in key sectors despite the fact that it covers several sectors with objectives that relate well to sustainability.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expansion of energy with low GHG emissions Related objectives regarding: Forest, Land and Coastal management, with emphasis on biodiversity protection and sustainable management adopting an 'ecosystem services' approach; and Water, focusing on sustainable management and rehabilitation of river beds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No GE strategy Renewable Energy expansion comprises of further development of hydropower plants (HPP), despite great potential of solar and wind energy The areas of Industry, Buildings, Transport and Finance lack objectives relating to Green Economy Lack of relevant indicators

Status/follow-up: No follow up planned.

Brown economy: Development of many hydropower plants can have important negative impacts on the environment. Further research would be required.

4.1.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Albania	
Background	1	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	5,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	4,0	
Number of indicators defined	2,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	3,0	
Document versions	0,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available	2,0	
References to ecological limits	2,5	
Focus on local activities	1,5	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	3,3	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	2,5	
Total	1,8	
Sectors covered		
Agriculture	3,5	3,0
Fisheries	3,0	1,5
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	4,0	3,5
Forests	4,0	3,5
Renewable Energy	3,0	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	3,0	2,0
Waste	4,0	3,0
Buildings	1,0	1,5
Transport	1,0	2,0
Tourism	3,5	2,0
Cities	2,0	2,5
Land and coastal management	4,0	4,0
Finance	1,0	1,0
Total	2,8	2,4
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		
Governance & civil society engagement	2,0	2,5
Education and Training	2,5	2,5
Research and Innovation	2,0	1,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	2,0	2,5
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others	3,0	2,5
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	1,0	
Total	1,9	2,0
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	2,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	3,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	2,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	2,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	2,3	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,7	

4.2 Algeria

4.2.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	5.360,70	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	3,33
Population [Mio]	39,20	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	0,94
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	16,50	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	3,19
Unemployment [%]	9,80	Sanitation Access [%]	95,20
Gini-Index	35,30	Water Access [%]	83,90
Human Development Index	0,72	Electricity Access [%]	99,40
Deforestation [% change]	0,57	Fossil fuel subsidies	13,40
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	146,00	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	17,40	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	0,38
Protected areas [%]	7,38	Wealth change/cap	492,10

4.2.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Document 1: National Environmental Action Plan for Sustainable Development (2002-2012), Document 2: National Strategy for an Integrated Management of Coastal Areas (2015)
Main focus	Sustainable Development
Short description	The first document is a national environmental action plan which sets targets, priorities and defines the strategy to reach a sustainable development. The second document is also a national strategy that aims at promoting measures in various sectors of the economy to develop an integrated management of coastal areas where the biggest majority of the Algerian population lives.
Prepared / Published by	The Algerian Democratic and Popular Republic and its Ministry of Spatial Planning and Environment
Political backing	Government of Algeria
History / background	More than ten years (strategy from 2002)
Website English version	n/a
Local language version	http://www.mre.dz/
First Date of publication	2002 for the National Environmental Plan of Action for SD , 2015 for the National Strategy for an Integrated management of Coastal Areas
Last update	2015

4.2.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Algeria's strategy is considered **moderate**. The National Action Plan for the Environment and Sustainable Development is weak and out-dated for 5 years now. More recent sectorial policies for Agriculture, Fisheries, Renewable Energy and Water are better defined but not fundamentally sustainable. Nevertheless, it published in 2015 a very relevant National Strategy for an Integrated Management of Coastal Areas that covers many sectors of the economy in the areas where the large majority of the population lives.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A detailed (100 pages) and relevant National Strategy for Coastal Areas Water, Forests, Fisheries and Land and Coastal Management are well covered with relevant measures - if taking into account all the documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Action Plan outdated (timeline: 2002-2011) Almost no covering of Buildings, Transports and Green Jobs creation The other sectors are reasonably mentioned but the goals are not so relevant in terms of sustainability, as for example for Cities, Waste, Manufacturing and Industry or Renewable Energy No indicators in the document

Status/follow-up: According the Algerian government a new national document strategy is in preparation for 2016 but there was little information available about it during the time this report was being written.

Any other interesting info: In Algeria, 90% of the population lives in the north of the country within 250 km from the coast which is why the National Strategy for Coastal Areas is particularly relevant.

4.2.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Algeria	
Background	2	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	1,0	
Local language version	2,0	
First Date of publication	3,0	
Last update	3,5	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	4,0	
Number of indicators defined	2,0	
Budget associated	4,0	
Time line	2,5	
Stakeholder involvement	2,0	
Document versions	3,0	
Associated laws	5,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	2,0	
Focus on local activities	2,0	
Link to SDGs	1,0	
Average	3,1	
Tools		
Green Procurment	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	2,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,5	2,0
Fisheries	5,0	4,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	5,0
Forests	3,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	2,5
Manufacturing & industry	3,0	2,0
Waste	5,0	2,5
Buildings	1,5	1,0
Transport	1,5	1,0
Tourism	3,0	3,5
Cities	3,5	2,5
Land and coastal management	5,0	5,0
Finance	5,0	3,0
Total	3,7	2,9
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	4,0	2,5
Education and Training	3,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	3,0	2,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,5	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others		
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	3,0	
Total	2,6	2,0
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	2,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	1,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	1,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	2,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	4,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,0	
8 Integrating subnat, local & private action	4,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	1,0	
Total	2,4	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,0	

4.3 Bosnia and Herzegovina

4.3.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	4.655,60	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	8,09
Population [Mio]	3,83	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	0,41
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	75,10	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	12,30
Unemployment [%]	28,20	Sanitation Access [%]	95,40
Gini-Index	33,00	Water Access [%]	99,60
Human Development Index	0,73	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	0,00	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	85,90	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	42,30	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	46,90
Protected areas [%]	1,51	Wealth change/cap	N.A.

4.3.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Development Strategy of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina 2010 to 2020; PSRP Agricultural sector 2015-2020; UNEP + Ministry of Trade- Biodiversity Strategy 2015-2020
Main focus	National development and sectorial development strategy
Short description	National-level development plan that reviews the state of the economy and sets strategic goals for each sector, aiming for economic growth and aspiring for future EU inclusion
Prepared / Published by	Federal Institute for Development Programming
Political backing	Document is submitted for parliamentary approval.
History / background	Strategic development plan adopted on 9-9-2009, at the 116th session of the government. It sets the strategy to align its policies with EU standards, in order to achieve accession by the early 2020's.
Website English version	http://fzzpr.gov.ba/en/ (Not operating 15/06/2016)
Local language version	http://www.fzzpr.gov.ba/bs
First Date of publication	2010
Last update	-

4.3.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Bosnia-Herzegovina does not have a proper GE/SD strategy. In the Development Strategy several key sectors have objectives that relate poorly to sustainability, as for instance, its commitment to continue relying on coal. Even if its strategy is **weak** it seems that Bosnia-Herzegovina is in the process of developing sustainable legislations and mechanisms but are in a very early stage.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GE related objectives regarding: tourism, with emphasis on multi-stakeholder participation in support of local eco-tourism ensuring protection of natural and cultural heritage; and forests, creating incentives for biodiversity protection (there is strong support for local biofuel production which may be controversial though) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No GE/SD strategy The strategy does not offer a framework for the greening of the financial sector and the creation of green jobs Several key sectors lack relevant goals, for example renewable energy where some wind power expansion is foreseen but the bulk of RES development relies on Hydropower; in Transport there is a lack of incentive measures for adopting eco-fuels. Waste, Buildings and Industry related objectives are poorly explained Lack of relevant indicators

Status/follow-up: No plans for the creation of a SD/GE strategy

Any other interesting info: Bosnia and Herzegovina relies on coal and has a renewable energy target of 40% by 2020. However, the sustainability of this target is hard to assess since the bulk of RES comes from hydropower plants, as solar and wind energy play a marginal role in the sector. Furthermore, the government's will for EU accession is a driving force towards adopting more sustainable policies in accordance with EU requirements.

Brown economy: Coal will continue to have a key role.

4.3.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Bosnia	
Background	3	
Prepared by / Published by	3,0	
Political backing	2,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	3,5	
Website English version	1,5	
Local language version	3,0	
First Date of publication	3,0	
Last update	3,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	1,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	3,5	
Document versions	4,0	
Associated laws	2,0	
3rd party assessment available	2,0	
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	4,0	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	3,0	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	3,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	3,0	3,0
Forests	4,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	3,5	1,5
Manufacturing & industry	3,0	2,0
Waste	2,0	2,0
Buildings	1,0	1,5
Transport	2,0	2,0
Tourism	4,0	4,5
Cities	3,0	2,0
Land and coastal management	3,0	3,0
Finance	2,0	1,5
Total	2,7	2,4
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	2,0	3,0
Education and Training	4,0	2,0
Research and Innovation	2,0	1,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	2,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	2,0
Others: Health, others	3,5	
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,4	1,8
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	3,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	0,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	2,8	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,7	

4.4 Croatia

4.4.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	13.529,90	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	4,73
Population [Mio]	4,25	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,20
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	76,00	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	13,50
Unemployment [%]	15,80	Sanitation Access [%]	98,20
Gini-Index	33,60	Water Access [%]	98,60
Human Development Index	0,81	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,19	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	147,80	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	23,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	60,70
Protected areas [%]	10,30	Wealth change/cap	936,90

4.4.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Strategy for sustainable development of the republic of Croatia (2009)
Main focus	Sustainable Development
Short description	The Strategy establishes guidelines for long term actions by defining objectives and determining measures for their realization, taking into account the present status and undertaken international obligations. The Strategy integrates various development policies by trying to find solutions suitable for all three components of sustainable development: economic, social and environmental.
Prepared / Published by	The ministry of environmental protection, physical planning and construction (now called Ministry of Environmental and Nature Protection)
Political backing	The Croatian Parliament
History / background	This strategy was adopted by the Croatian Parliament at its session on 20 February 2009. Pursuant of Article 44 of the Environmental Protection Act (2007). It follows international commitments of the Rio's conference (1992) and Agenda 21. One of the first documents passed by the Croatian Parliament in which the importance of sustainable development is mentioned is the Declaration on Environmental Protection in the Republic of Croatia adopted in 1992.
Website English version	National strategy link: http://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro105236.pdf http://www.mzoip.hr/en/
Local language version	http://www.mzoip.hr/hr/
First Date of publication	20 February 2009
Last update	-

4.4.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Croatia's National Strategy for Sustainable Development published in 2009 is **moderate**; it is well written but quite short and would require an update.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many and diverse indicators • Concrete until 2020 • Agriculture, Water, Transport, Health, SCP, Land & Coastal Management and Renewable Energy are well covered with sustainability relevant measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some goals are outdated • Quite short document, not very detailed (50 pages) • No budget mentioned • Apparently top-down process, no participatory process with stakeholders is described • Fisheries, Forests, Manufacturing & Industry, Buildings and Finance are weakly covered with measures not relevant in terms of sustainability

Status/follow-up: No follow-up is mentioned in the document. One may suppose that at the end of the period of this strategy in 2020 the Government of Croatia will publish a new one.

4.4.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Croatia	
Background	4	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	2,5	
Last update		
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	2,0	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	2,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	4,0	
Focus on local activities	2,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,1	
Tools		
Green Procurement	2,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	4,0
Fisheries	2,0	2,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	4,0
Forests	2,0	2,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	4,0
Manufacturing & industry	1,0	1,0
Waste	4,0	3,0
Buildings	2,0	2,0
Transport	5,0	4,0
Tourism	3,0	3,0
Cities	2,0	3,0
Land and coastal management	5,0	4,5
Finance	2,0	1,0
Total	3,2	2,9
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,0	3,0
Education and Training	3,5	4,0
Research and Innovation	3,5	2,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others	5,0	
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	5,0	
Total	3,1	2,2
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	5,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	4,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	5,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	1,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	4,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	4,0	
Total	3,6	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,1	

4.5 Cyprus

4.5.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	25.249,00	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	6,98
Population [Mio]	1,14	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,49
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	123,50	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	11,10
Unemployment [%]	11,80	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	N.A.	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,85	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,09	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	161,20	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	13,50	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	1,34
Protected areas [%]	17,10	Wealth change/cap	368,90

4.5.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Sustainable Development Strategy (NSDS)
Main focus	Sustainable development
Short description	The NSDS includes the main topics and subject areas of the renewed EU SDS. The strategy covers the three dimensions of sustainable development.
Prepared / Published by	Department of Environment, Ministry of Agriculture, Natural Resources and Environment
Political backing	Council of Ministers
History / background	This document is the first NSDS of Cyprus
Website English version	National strategy link: http://www.un.org/esa/agenda21/natlinfo/countr/cyprus/nsds_2007en.pdf Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment website: http://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/agriculture.nsf/index_en/index_en?OpenDocument Department of environment website: http://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/environment/environment.nsf/index_en/index_en?OpenDocument
Local language version	Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment website: http://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/agriculture.nsf/index_gr/index_gr?OpenDocument Department of environment website: http://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/environment/environment.nsf/index_gr/index_gr?OpenDocument
First Date of publication	March 2007
Last update	October 2010

4.5.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Cyprus's National Strategy of Sustainable Development published in 2007 is quite old and superficial; it is **weak and** hardly relevant in terms of sustainability.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transport, Land & Coastal management, Forest and Education & Training are sectors reasonably well covered with interesting measures (but still far from perfect). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short and superficial document (37 pages) Quite old (2007) For almost all the sectors the measures are not relevant in terms of sustainability Waste, Cities, Buildings and Finance very poorly covered Few indicators Some goals are outdated

Status/follow-up: No apparent follow-up planned.

4.5.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Cyprus	
Background	5	
Prepared by / Published by		
Political backing		
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	2,0	
Last update	2,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined	4,0	
Budget associated	1,5	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	1,0	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	1,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	5,0	
Focus on local activities	1,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	2,6	
Tools		
Green Procurement	4,0	
Green Tax Policy	3,5	
Total	3,8	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	2,0	1,0
Fisheries	2,0	2,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,0	1,0
Forests	2,0	3,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	1,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,0	1,0
Waste	1,0	1,0
Buildings	1,0	1,0
Transport	4,0	3,0
Tourism	1,0	1,0
Cities	4,0	2,0
Land and coastal management	3,0	3,5
Finance	1,0	1,0
Total	2,2	1,7
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	1,0	1,0
Education and Training	4,0	3,5
Research and Innovation	4,5	2,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others	5,0	
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	3,0	
Total	2,8	1,7
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	1,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	4,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	2,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,5	
Total	2,6	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,6	

4.6 Egypt

4.6.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016³

GDP/cap. [US\$]	3.314,50	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	2,62
Population [Mio]	82,10	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	0,59
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	82,40	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	17,50
Unemployment [%]	11,90	Sanitation Access [%]	95,90
Gini-Index	30,80	Water Access [%]	99,30
Human Development Index	0,68	Electricity Access [%]	99,60
Deforestation [% change]	-1,73	Fossil fuel subsidies	24,50
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	832,40	Environmental. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	3,63	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	9,90
Protected areas [%]	11,30	Wealth change/cap	-52,00

4.6.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Egypt's Vision 2030 and medium term investment framework 2014-2015 / 2018-2019
Main focus	Sustainable Development
Short description	Egypt's Vision 2030 is the Sustainable Development Strategy developed and published by the Egyptian government in order to define a medium term investment framework to improve Egyptian's quality of life.
Prepared / Published by	Prepared by the Cabinet (Prime Minister and Cabinet of Ministers), published by the Government of Egypt.
Political backing	Government of Egypt and the President Abdel Fattah al-Sissi
History / background	2015: first release of the draft. 2016: final release of the strategy.
Website English version	http://sdsegypt2030.com/?lang=en
Local language version	http://sdsegypt2030.com/
First Date of publication	2015
Last update	2016

4.6.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Egypt's Vision 2030 strategy document was recently published but it is rather weak because although it presents big plans to develop Egypt, it is quite short and remains vague on the details on how its goals will be achieved. It is more a general economic development strategy than a specific GE or SD strategy.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent document with a long and mid-term vision and investment framework 45 key performance indicators linked to each goal of the strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Though it is claimed to be a Sustainable Development Strategy, it is far from being one Lacks clear integration of the social and environmental dimension Lacks cross linkages between sectors Lacks a clear plan of action and an implementation mechanism Several sectors not mentioned at all: Water, Finance, Land & Coastal Management, Fisheries and Forests

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet, probably 2018/2019 at the end of the mid-term investment framework.

Additional information: In the tourism sector an initiative called “Green Star Hotel Program” certifies hotels as green hotels through achieving a number of criteria that are related to water resources, waste recycling, energy efficiency, etc.. According to the Ministry of Tourism, the government is engaged in co-investment initiatives for RE/EE measures in hotels and it coordinates with the United Nations World Tourism Organization to set indicators for Sustainable Tourism in Egypt.

4.6.4 Evaluation Detail

Criteria	Egypt	
Background	6	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	3,5	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	3,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	2,5	
Number of indicators defined	4,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	3,0	
Document versions	1,5	
Associated laws	5,0	
3rd party assessment available	3,0	
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	3,0	
Link to SDGs	3,0	
Average	3,6	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	2,5	2,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,0	1,5
Forests	1,0	1,0
Renewable Energy	3,5	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	3,5	3,5
Waste	2,0	2,0
Buildings	3,5	2,0
Transport	3,5	2,5
Tourism	3,5	3,0
Cities	2,0	2,0
Land and coastal management	1,0	1,0
Finance	1,0	1,0
Total	2,3	1,9
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,5	2,5
Education and Training	3,5	2,5
Research and Innovation	3,5	2,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,5	2,0
Others: Health, others	3,5	2,5
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,8	2,2
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	3,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	1,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	1,5	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,0	
8 Integrating subnat, local & private action	3,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	1,5	
Total	2,3	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,8	

4.7 France

4.7.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	41.420,80	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	5,56
Population [Mio]	66,00	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	6,10
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	120,60	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	10,70
Unemployment [%]	9,90	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	31,70	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,88	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,39	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	478,90	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	1,94
Agricultural land [%]	52,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	13,80
Protected areas [%]	28,70	Wealth change/cap	2.898,40

4.7.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Strategy of Ecological Transition towards Sustainable Development 2015-2020
Main focus	Sustainability
Short description	The strategy is a framework for French policies in order to define aims to achieve sustainability in France and to guide stakeholders for the emergence of a new model of society.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Sea
Political backing	Segolène Royale, Minister of Ministry of Environment, Energy and Sea
History / background	Third strategy since 1992. It follows a law voted in 2015 for the energy transition toward green economy and follows the commitments made at international level at the Earth Summit in Rio in 1992 and following summits.
Website English version	National strategy link: http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/150828_SNTEDD_version_EN.pdf
Local language version	National strategy link: http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/SNTEDD.pdf Ministry website link: http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr
First Date of publication	28/08/2015
Last update	15/12/2015

4.7.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: France's National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2015-2020 is considered **good** because it is a very complete and relevant framework for policies. The goals are clear and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal. All the sectors are well covered except tourism and fisheries.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers almost all the sectors of the economy with sustainability relevant goals and measures particularly for Manufacturing & Industry, Transport, Cities, Waste, Land and Coastal Management, Education and Training and Management of ecosystem services Large and well described participatory process for a clear bottom-up strategy Clearly linked to the SDGs Associated with the law for the energy transition toward green economy prepared by the French minister for ecology, Segolène Royal in 2015 Detailed document (130 pages) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget not mentioned in the document Fisheries and Tourism very poorly mentioned

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet, probably 2020 at the end of the time-line of the strategy.

4.7.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	France	
Background	7	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	3,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	5,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	4,0	
Focus on local activities	5,0	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	4,1	
Tools		
Green Procurement	3,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	3,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,0	3,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	3,0	3,5
Forests	2,0	2,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,0	4,0
Waste	5,0	5,0
Buildings	2,0	3,0
Transport	3,0	4,5
Tourism	1,0	1,0
Cities	3,0	4,5
Land and coastal management	3,0	5,0
Finance	5,0	3,0
Total	2,9	3,3
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	5,0	4,0
Education and Training	5,0	5,0
Research and Innovation	5,0	3,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	2,5	5,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,5	3,0
Others: Health, others		
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	3,8	4,0
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	5,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	5,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	5,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	3,9	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,7	

4.8 Greece

4.8.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	21.910,20	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	7,77
Population [Mio]	11,00	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,78
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	85,60	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	11,60
Unemployment [%]	24,20	Sanitation Access [%]	98,60
Gini-Index	34,70	Water Access [%]	99,80
Human Development Index	0,85	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,81	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	858,50	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	2,78
Agricultural land [%]	63,30	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	18,30
Protected areas [%]	21,50	Wealth change/cap	-2.099,30

4.8.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Partnership Agreement for Development Framework (PA) 2014-2020; Rural Development Programme (RDP) 2014 - 2020
Main focus	National development plan; Rural development plan
Short description	The PA seeks to tackle the structural weaknesses in Greece that contributed to the economic crisis; it incorporates the Europe 2020 Strategy's targets via 11 strategic objectives and integrates the Sustainable Development Principle through investments under the thematic priorities of the ERDF, CF, EAFRD, EMFF.
Prepared / Published by	European Commission and Hellenic Republic
Political backing	European Commission and Hellenic Parliament
History / background	The European Committee approved the PA 2014-20 on 23 May 2014 with a budget of €26 billion. The Greek PA has integrated the principles of Sustainable Development and seeks for an optimal use of European Structural and Investment Funds for the period 2014-2020. In 2010 a GE plan was created called "Program for Development Interventions for the Real Economy", but the ongoing scenario of economic crisis has outdated the 2010 program and currently a new GE plan is being drafted that will fit the current situation in Greece.
Website English version	PA 2014-2020: https://www.espa.gr/en/pages/default.aspx Ministry of Environment: http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=37&locale=en-US
Local language version	PA 2014-2020: https://www.espa.gr/el/pages/default.aspx Ministry of Environment: http://www.ypeka.gr/
First Date of publication	2014
Last update	-

4.8.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Greece's strategy is considered **moderate** because, despite not having a relevant GE/SD strategy, it integrated the EU 2020 targets, which implies the greening of many of its sectors. An overarching GE strategy with detailed objectives, targets and indicators is needed with a much clear picture of the commitment and potential of Greece in developing a GE.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports sustainable urban development • Aims at lowering carbon emissions in most sectors • GE related objectives regarding: Agriculture, emphasizing support for organic and climate friendly agriculture; Land and Coastal areas, strongly supporting increase of protected areas adopting the Ecosystem Approach; Forest, focusing on biodiversity protection; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No relevant GE/SD strategy • Objectives relating to Finance, Tourism Manufacturing & Industry and Research & Innovation have few objectives relating to sustainability or are poorly elaborated • No mention of incentives for creation of Green Jobs

Status/follow-up: The Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs are currently coordinating the adoption of SDGs in a new Strategic National Framework. However, the date of publication remains unclear.

Any other interesting info: In 2010 the Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy prepared a National GE plan: 'Program of Development Interventions for the Real Economy'. However, due to the on-going economic crisis this plan is now irrelevant. The adoption of the SDGs in the new plan being drafted, should adapt to the requirements of the latest MoU and Economic Adjustment Program agreed with the European Commission. It remains unclear how the economic adjustment will affect the quality and ambition of upcoming GE/SD policies.

Brown economy: Greece is currently developing its domestic oil and gas industry, including deep-sea oil extraction and is continuing investment in new lignite-burning power plant.

4.8.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Greece	
Background	8	
Prepared by / Published by	5,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,5	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	4,0	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	4,0	
Last update	4,0	
Planned follow-up	5,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined	1,0	
Budget associated	3,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	2,0	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	3,5	
3rd party assessment available	2,0	
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	3,5	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	3,5	
Tools		
Green Procurment	1,5	
Green Tax Policy	3,0	
Total	2,3	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,5	3,0
Fisheries	3,0	2,5
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	3,0	3,0
Forests	4,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	4,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,0	2,0
Waste	3,5	2,5
Buildings	1,5	2,0
Transport	2,0	2,0
Tourism	2,0	2,0
Cities	3,0	3,5
Land and coastal management	3,5	3,5
Finance	0,0	1,5
Total	2,7	2,7
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	2,0	2,0
Education and Training	4,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	2,0	1,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	3,5	2,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	2,0	1,5
Others: Health, others	3,0	0,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	1,0	
Total	2,5	1,6
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	2,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	0,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,5	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	2,5	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	2,5	
Total	2,3	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,0	

4.9 Israel

4.9.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	36.151,20	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	9,27
Population [Mio]	8,06	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,39
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	372,40	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	13,20
Unemployment [%]	6,90	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	42,80	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,89	Electricity Access [%]	99,70
Deforestation [% change]	-0,07	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	242,40	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	3,18
Agricultural land [%]	24,20	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	0,25
Protected areas [%]	14,70	Wealth change/cap	2.957,80

4.9.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Document 1 : SCP Roadmap for Israel (2014) Document 2 : Connecting the economy to the environment in Israel (2014)
Main focus	SCP and Green Growth
Short description	Document 1 was published by the Israeli Ministries of Environmental Protection and Economy as part of the scoping review process of the national policy component of the SwitchMed program (funded by EU). Document 2 published by the Ministry of Environment describes the participatory process and the first actions in order to implement a Green Growth Strategy.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry of Environmental Protection and Economy + SwitchMed
Political backing	Government of the State of Israel
History / background	1988: Creation of the Ministry that will become in 2006 the Ministry of Environmental Protection. 2003: SD Plan. 2009: Green Government Programme. 2010: National Plan for Greenhouse Gas Reduction. 2011: Let's think green campaign. 2011: Green Growth Action Plan, etc.
Website English version	http://kayamut2030.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=178&Itemid=149 http://www.sviva.gov.il/English/AboutUs/Pages/AboutUs.aspx
Local language version	Arabic and Hebrew Version
First Date of publication	2014
Last update	

4.9.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Israel's strategy is **moderate** because - even if they have shown a real interest in GE, SCP or SD questions for years now – their policy documents are rather weak and short, the goals are not clear and many sectors of the economy are either not covered or are covered in a very general way. It is not a real framework for policies and there are no indicators. The Green Growth Action Plan 2012-2020 announced in the GE document has never been approved.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SCP roadmap for Israel helps achieving the challenge of economic growth and development in the face of the limited carrying capacity of the environment Cities and Building sectors are well covered with relevant goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Goals not so clear in the document Many sectors of the economy are poorly covered or covered in a very general way as for example Agriculture, Fisheries, Forests, Renewable Energy, Tourism, Land & Coastal Management No indicators available in the document Quite short document, not very detailed (47 pages)

Status/follow-up: Not planned in the document, the information available on the ministry's website is not clear.

Any other interesting info: Israel shows a clear interest in these issues with some related publications like the Green Government Program (2009), the National Plan for Greenhouse Gas Reduction (2010), a "Let's think green" campaign (2011), the publication of "Indicators for Well-being, Sustainability and Resilience" (2011), and an Environmental Justice Strategy (2014).

4.9.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Israel	
Background	9	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	4,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	2,0	
Number and description of goals	3,5	
Number of indicators defined	3,5	
Budget associated	3,5	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	4,0	
Document versions	3,5	
Associated laws	5,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	4,0	
Focus on local activities	4,0	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	4,2	
Tools		
Green Procurement	5,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	4,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	2,0	2,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,5	3,5
Forests	1,0	1,0
Renewable Energy	2,0	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,5	3,5
Waste	2,5	4,0
Buildings	2,5	4,0
Transport	2,0	4,0
Tourism	2,0	1,0
Cities	3,0	4,0
Land and coastal management	2,0	2,0
Finance	2,0	2,5
Total	2,1	2,7
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,0	3,5
Education and Training	3,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	3,0	3,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	3,0	1,5
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	3,0	4,0
Others: Health, others	3,0	
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	5,0	
Total	3,3	3,1
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	3,5	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	3,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	3,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	3,1	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,3	

4.10 Italy

4.10.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	34.619,20	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	6,85
Population [Mio]	59,80	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	4,34
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	203,40	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	13,30
Unemployment [%]	10,70	Sanitation Access [%]	N.A.
Gini-Index	35,50	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,87	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,90	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	759,00	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	3,01
Agricultural land [%]	46,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	25,80
Protected areas [%]	21,00	Wealth change/cap	686,10

4.10.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Environmental legislation for measures to promote green economy and reduce the excessive use of natural resources
Main focus	Green economy
Short description	General Measures for the Protection of Nature and the Promotion of Sustainable Development. The Law requires the government to approve a National Strategy for Sustainable Development to be updated at least every three years, and creates a National Agency for New Technologies, Energy, and Sustainable Economic Development, to provide services to companies and individuals in those areas. It also establishes the National Strategy for Green Communities.
Prepared / Published by	Italian Parliament
Political backing	Mr. Gian Luca Galletti, Environment Minister
History / background	Last National Strategy from 2002
Website English version	N/A
Local language version	http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/1/18/16G00006/sg
First Date of publication	2014
Last update	2015

4.10.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Italy has a **good** strategy because in 2015 they published a law on Green Economy, which is very relevant and sets up a real framework policy to develop GE measures in Italy. The National Strategy for Sustainable Development published in 2002 is outdated but complete and detailed with sustainability relevant measures.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law of 2015 focuses on Green Economy and is very relevant for Renewable Energy, Waste, Water and Soil degradation • Strategy from 2002 covers almost all the sectors of the economy with sustainability relevant goals and measures particularly Agriculture, Water, Forests, Transport, Land & Coastal management, Governance, Education and Research • Very detailed documents (182 + 78 pages) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Strategy outdated • Agriculture, Fisheries, Tourism, Manufacturing & Industry, Cities and Finance are poorly covered in the 2015 Green Economy law

Status/follow-up: The recent law on Green Economy requires the government to approve a National Strategy for Sustainable Development to be updated at least every three years. It also establishes the National Strategy for Green Communities.

4.10.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Italy	
Background	10	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	3,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	1,0	
Last update	1,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	3,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	5,0	
Stakeholder involvement	2,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws		
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	5,0	
Focus on local activities	5,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,4	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	2,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,5	4,0
Fisheries	4,0	2,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	5,0
Forests	3,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,0	2,0
Waste	5,0	2,0
Buildings	3,0	2,5
Transport	5,0	5,0
Tourism	4,5	2,0
Cities	5,0	3,5
Land and coastal management	5,0	5,0
Finance	3,5	3,0
Total	4,2	3,2
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,5	3,0
Education and Training	4,0	5,0
Research and Innovation	4,0	4,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	3,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	3,0
Others: Health, others	1,0	3,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,4	3,5
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	5,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	5,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	5,0	
Total	3,7	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,5	

4.11 Jordan

4.11.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	5.214,20	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	3,44
Population [Mio]	6,46	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	0,82
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	72,80	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	12,70
Unemployment [%]	12,20	Sanitation Access [%]	98,10
Gini-Index	33,70	Water Access [%]	96,10
Human Development Index	0,75	Electricity Access [%]	99,40
Deforestation [% change]	0,00	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	145,70	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	11,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	0,48
Protected areas [%]	0,03	Wealth change/cap	258,70

4.11.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Jordan National Agenda (JNA) 2006-2015; Strategic Plan: Ministry of Environment (SPMoE) 2014-2016; The National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) 2015-20
Main focus	Development Strategy; Development Strategy regarding the Ministry of Environment; Strategy regarding Biodiversity
Short description	JNA (2006-15) is the last national agenda and sets the broad vision and objectives which are further specified and developed in the respective specific strategy plans, such as SPMoE (2014-16) and NBSAP (2015-20)—all having several objectives relating to GE.
Prepared by / Published by	Council of Ministers; Ministry of Environment; Ministry of Environment
Political backing	King Abdullah II Ibn Al-Hussein; Dr. Taher Radi Al Shakhshir (Minister of Environment)
History / background	The JNA was ordered by Royal Decree on 9 February 2005, with the purpose of creating a comprehensive strategy that will layout the essential objectives towards economic growth and greater social inclusion. To ensure that the national agenda would not be vulnerable to changes of government, it was drafted by a committee comprised by members of different political parties, civil society, media and the private sector
Website English version	http://www.jordan.gov.jo/wps/portal/ (easy access from local version) Ministry of Environment: http://www.moenv.gov.jo/en/pages/default.aspx
Local language version	http://www.jordan.gov.jo/wps/portal/ Ministry of Environment: http://www.moenv.gov.jo/Ar/Pages/default.aspx
First Date of publication	JNA: 2006; SPMoE: 2014; NBSAP: 2015
Last update	-

4.11.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Jordan's strategy is considered **moderate** because even if the country does not have a specific GE strategy, Jordan shows a clear intention of pursuing more sustainable development plans. It has incorporated the principle of SD in its specific strategies in an interesting manner and it is currently preparing a National Green Growth Plan which will set a cross-sectorial GE framework.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE related objectives for: Water, emphasizing sustainable use in all sectors; Waste, striving for reduction and re-use; Tourism, promoting eco-tourism and aiming to reduce the carbon footprint of the sector; and Land and coastal Management, focusing on sustainable management through Ecosystem approach with the priority of combating desertification • Multi-stakeholder participation • Expansion of RE supported by Jordan Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Fund (JREEEF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No GE/SD strategy • Out-dated National Agenda (2006-2015) • Plans for developing nuclear power • Lack of GE related objectives regarding: Agriculture, where water efficiency measures are in place, but organic farming is poorly addressed and the 2013 Biosafety Law, mandating GMO labelling has yet to be ratified; while in Manufacturing & Industry, there is emphasis on energy efficiency but doesn't address eco-design or obsolescence.

Status/follow-up: The MoEnv and GGGI are preparing the National Green Growth Plan (date of publication unclear).

Other interesting info: Jordan's energy supply relies almost entirely on the import of oil & gas but recent policies, such as the 2012 Jordan Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Fund (JREEEF), enable the current initial development stage of several RE projects aimed to lessen the burden of fossil fuel imports. Moreover, fossil fuel subsidies were eliminated in 2012, paving the road for growth in RE investment.

Brown economy: On the other hand, a Committee for Nuclear Power was set up in 2007, with the goal of developing nuclear power facilities in order to provide 30% of Jordan's electricity by 2030.

4.11.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Jordan	
Background	11	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,5	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	3,0	
Local language version	3,0	
First Date of publication	3,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	5,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	4,5	
Number of indicators defined	4,0	
Budget associated	2,0	
Time line	3,5	
Stakeholder involvement	4,0	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	2,0	
Link to SDGs	4,0	
Average	3,5	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,5	3,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	4,0	4,0
Forests	3,0	3,0
Renewable Energy	3,0	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	3,0	2,0
Waste	5,0	4,0
Buildings	3,0	2,0
Transport	3,0	3,0
Tourism	3,5	4,0
Cities	3,0	2,5
Land and coastal management	3,0	4,0
Finance	4,0	3,0
Total	3,2	3,0
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,0	4,0
Education and Training	3,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	3,0	2,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	4,0	4,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	0,0
Others: Health, others	1,0	4,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	3,0	
Total	2,6	2,9
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	3,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways		
5 Policy design and implementation	2,5	
6 Mobilizing investment	3,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,5	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action		
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	4,0	
Total	3,8	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,2	

4.12 Lebanon

4.12.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	9.928,00	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	4,70
Population [Mio]	4,47	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	1,51
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	436,70	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	14,10
Unemployment [%]	8,90	Sanitation Access [%]	98,30
Gini-Index	N.A.	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,76	Electricity Access [%]	99,90
Deforestation [% change]	-0,45	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	293,20	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	71,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	5,34
Protected areas [%]	0,48	Wealth change/cap	-388,60

4.12.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Sustainable Consumption and Production Action Plan for the Industrial Sector in Lebanon
Main focus	SCP in the industrial sector
Short description	The SCP Action Plan can be considered as a nationally validated framework which can be used by the different stakeholders for the implementation of specific activities or sets of activities identified under the action plan.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry of Environment with the support of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) within the framework of the SwitchMed programme, financed by the European Union.
Political backing	Mohamad Al Mashnouk, Minister of Environment
History / background	1993: Law 216/93 introduced by the Ministry of Environment, it was redefined over the years with different amendments (1997, 2005). 2002: Law 444- Environmental Protection Act.
Website English version	http://www.moe.gov.lb/Home.aspx
Local language version	http://www.moe.gov.lb/Home.aspx?lang=ar-lb
First Date of publication	2015
Last update	2015

4.12.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Lebanon's strategy is considered **moderate** because even if it does not have a proper National Strategy for SD or GE, they published in 2015 a National Action Plan on Sustainable Production and Consumption (SCP) focusing on the industrial sector. It is a useful document with relevant goals, but it only concerns the industrial sector.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SCP Action plan is an interesting document with relevant goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only covers the industrial sector No general SD/GE framework policy available in Lebanon

Status/follow-up: No apparent follow-up planned. No national framework policy announced yet.

4.12.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Lebanon	
Background	12	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,5	
History / background / key hits	3,5	
Website English version	4,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	5,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	3,0	
Number and description of goals	4,0	
Number of indicators defined	3,5	
Budget associated	4,0	
Time line	5,0	
Stakeholder involvement	5,0	
Document versions	3,0	
Associated laws	5,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	4,0	
Focus on local activities	4,0	
Link to SDGs	3,0	
Average	4,2	
Tools		
Green Procurement	5,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	4,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	1,0	1,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,0	2,0
Forests	1,0	1,0
Renewable Energy	2,5	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	4,0	5,0
Waste	3,0	3,5
Buildings	2,0	2,0
Transport	1,0	1,0
Tourism	1,0	1,0
Cities	1,0	1,0
Land and coastal management	1,0	1,0
Finance	3,5	4,0
Total	1,8	2,0
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,5	4,0
Education and Training	4,0	4,0
Research and Innovation	2,5	2,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	3,0	3,5
Others: Health, others	1,0	1,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,5	2,6
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	1,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	3,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	2,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	3,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	2,0	
Total	2,6	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,1	

4.13 Malta

4.13.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	22.779,90	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	6,25
Population [Mio]	0,42	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,59
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	1.322,80	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	6,38
Unemployment [%]	6,40	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	N.A.	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,83	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	0,00	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	127,30	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	32,20	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	0,00
Protected areas [%]	2,20	Wealth change/cap	176,00

4.13.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Greening our economy-Achieving a sustainable future
Main focus	Sustainable development
Short description	This document presents Malta's commitment to green growth – a short to medium term strategy and action plan. It seeks to contextualise the nature of Green Economy and has the purpose of bringing together all necessary objectives and actions towards a GE in Malta, giving a framework of structure and timeline, enhancing them and striving towards their effective realisation.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry for Sustainable Development, the Environment and Climate Change (MSDEC)
Political backing	Prime Minister Dr Joseph Muscat
History / background	Associated with the National Environment Policy (2011) which identifies the green economy as one of its six objectives on the basis of which Malta's environment is to be managed and upgraded. Follows the EU commitments (European 2020 strategy) and international commitments (Rio Summits)
Website English version	National strategy link: https://socialdialogue.gov.mt/en/Public_Consultations/MSDEC/Documents/Green%20Economy/Consultation%20Document%20-%20Green%20Economy.pdf English website link: http://environment.gov.mt/en/Pages/mdsec%20main.aspx
Local language version	Maltese Website link: http://environment.gov.mt/mt/Pages/default.aspx
First Date of publication	2015, not officially approved yet, still in a public consultation stage
Last update	

4.13.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Malta's strategy is **moderate** because the government has still not approved it but a consultation document called "Greening our Economy – Achieving a sustainable future" was recently published. If this document gets approval, it will be a good basis for a Green Economy strategy even if it needs to be completed (e.g. by adding monitoring indicators).

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building, Waste, Renewable Energy, Agriculture, Transport and Tourism are well covered with sustainability relevant measures • Detailed document (126 pages) • Recent (even if it is not official yet) • Focused on Green Economy • Consultation process with stakeholders well described for a bottom-up strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not approved yet • No indicators available in the document • In particular Forests and Fisheries are not well covered

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned; first the government has to approve this document.

4.13.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Malta	
Background	13	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	3,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	2,0	
First Date of publication		
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	4,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined		
Budget associated		
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	3,0	
Document versions	3,0	
Associated laws	3.5	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	5,0	
Focus on local activities	5,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,9	
Tools		
Green Procurement	5,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	4,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	4,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	4,0	3,0
Forests	1,0	1,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	1,5
Manufacturing & industry	4,0	2,0
Waste	4,0	4,0
Buildings	4,0	4,0
Transport	4,0	4,0
Tourism	4,0	3,5
Cities	3,0	2,0
Land and coastal management	2,0	3,0
Finance	3,0	3,5
Total	3,2	2,8
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	2,0	1,0
Education and Training	4,0	4,5
Research and Innovation	3,5	1,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	3,0	3,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	4,0	4,0
Others: Health, others	1,0	1,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	2,0	
Total	2,8	2,4
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	2,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	5,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	5,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	5,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,5	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme		
Total	3,8	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,6	

4.14 Montenegro (*)

* After closure of the project the authors were informed that a new strategy was underway.

4.14.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	7.125,70	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	4,16
Population [Mio]	0,62	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	1,09
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	46,20	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	12,10
Unemployment [%]	19,60	Sanitation Access [%]	90,00
Gini-Index	30,60	Water Access [%]	98,00
Human Development Index	0,79	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	0,00	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	258,90	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	38,10	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	66,00
Protected areas [%]	12,80	Wealth change/cap	N.A.

4.14.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Strategy of Sustainable Development of Montenegro
Main focus	Sustainability
Short description	NSSD defines the vision and sets long-terms guidelines of SD in Montenegro, while the time horizon of the NSSD Action Plan is 2007-2012.
Prepared / Published by	The government of Montenegro and its Ministry of Tourism and Environmental Protection prepared this document with the support of UNDP Montenegro, UNEP-MAP and the Italian Ministry of Environment, Land and Sea.
Political backing	Ministry of Tourism and Environmental Protection
History / background	1991 : Declaration of Montenegro as an ecological state, commitment included in the Montenegrin Constitution
Website English version	http://www.mrt.gov.me/en/ministry
Local language version	http://www.mrt.gov.me/ministarstvo?alphabet=lat http://www.mrt.gov.me/ministarstvo?alphabet=cyr
First Date of publication	2005
Last update	2007

4.14.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Montenegro's National Strategy for Sustainable Development is **moderate** because it is quite old and some goals are outdated. No other document is planned to be published soon. Nevertheless, this strategy document is reasonably well done and covers most sectors of the economy.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed with several stakeholder groups in a bottom-up process Detailed document (126 pages) Covers almost all the sectors of the economy Agriculture, Fisheries, Land and Coastal Management, Water, Forests and Tourism are well covered and relevant in terms of sustainability as well as Governance & Civil Society engagement and Education & Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outdated (timeline: 2007-2012) The strategy does not cover Finance and Green Jobs creation well Some sectors are mentioned in dedicated chapters, but the goals are not so relevant in terms of sustainability as for example for Manufacturing & Industry, Cities and Buildings

Status/follow-up: No follow up planned in the document. But according to the Ministry of Sustainable Development and Tourism's website they have started the preparation of a new National Action Program for land protection in Montenegro; for now just a draft is available in Montenegrin.

Brown economy: Thermal power plants were mentioned in the survey.

4.14.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Montenegro	
Background	14	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	4,0	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	1,0	
Last update	2,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	4,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	3,0	
Time line	1,0	
Stakeholder involvement	4,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	3,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	2,0	
Focus on local activities	4,0	
Link to SDGs	2,5	
Average	3,2	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	2,0	
Total	1,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	4,0
Fisheries	4,0	2,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	4,0	4,0
Forests	4,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	4,0	1,5
Waste	4,0	2,0
Buildings	4,0	1,0
Transport	4,0	2,0
Tourism	4,0	4,5
Cities	4,0	1,0
Land and coastal management	4,0	5,0
Finance	3,5	3,0
Total	4,0	2,8
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	4,0	4,0
Education and Training	4,0	4,0
Research and Innovation	4,0	2,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others	4,0	3,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	3,0	2,5
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	1,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	3,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	4,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	4,0	
Total	3,1	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,3	

4.15 Morocco

4.15.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	3.108,60	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	1,60
Population [Mio]	33,00	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	1,49
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	74,00	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	7,25
Unemployment [%]	9,00	Sanitation Access [%]	75,40
Gini-Index	40,90	Water Access [%]	83,60
Human Development Index	0,62	Electricity Access [%]	98,90
Deforestation [% change]	-0,23	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	382,00	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	68,10	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	18,50
Protected areas [%]	19,90	Wealth change/cap	519,70

4.15.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Strategy of Sustainable Development 2015-2020
Main focus	Sustainable Development
Short description	This document is a national framework for policies which sets targets and priorities and defines the strategy to reach them.
Prepared / Published by	Kingdom of Morocco and the Ministry of Energy, Mines, Water and Environment, in charge of Environment.
Political backing	King Mohamed VI
History / background	In accordance with its international commitments in the context of the Rio Earth Summit (1992) and Johannesburg (2002) and the new constitution of 2011 (that defines sustainable development as a civil right), King Mohammed VI urged the Government to launch and define a National Strategy for Sustainable Development in his Throne Speech of July 30, 2009.
Website English version	N/A
Local language version	http://www.environnement.gov.ma/PDFs/SNDD-Rapport-Final-2015.pdf
First Date of publication	March 20, 2014
Last update	

4.15.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Morocco's National Strategy for Sustainable Development 2015-2020 is considered **good** because it is relevant and directly linked to the SDGs with a clear focus on Green Economy. The goals are well defined and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal. It is a complete document that covers well all the sectors of the economy and it is a real framework for policies in Morocco.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers almost all the sectors of the economy with sustainability relevant goals and measures Wide and well described participatory process for a clear bottom-up strategy Clear focus on green economy with dedicated chapters Very complete and detailed document (134 pages) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building sector poorly covered - mentioned in other sectors but not in a dedicated chapter Some sectors are reasonably well mentioned but the goals are not necessarily sustainable. For instance, in Agriculture Morocco sees Genetically Modified Organisms (GMO) as a solution to reach food security; Morocco wants to develop the Fishery sector but not in a fundamentally sustainable way

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet, probably 2020 at the end of the time-line of this National Strategy for Sustainable Development (2015-2020).

4.15.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Morocco	
Background	15	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	1,0	
Local language version	3,0	
First Date of publication	4,0	
Last update	4,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	5,0	
Time line	4,5	
Stakeholder involvement	3,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	4,5	
3rd party assessment available	3,0	
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	4,0	
Link to SDGs	5,0	
Average	3,9	
Tools		
Green Procurement	3,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	3,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	5,0	3,5
Fisheries	5,0	3,5
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	5,0
Forests	5,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	3,5
Manufacturing & industry	5,0	4,0
Waste	5,0	5,0
Buildings	5,0	2,5
Transport	5,0	4,0
Tourism	5,0	4,0
Cities	5,0	4,0
Land and coastal management	5,0	5,0
Finance	5,0	4,0
Total	5,0	4,0
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	5,0	4,0
Education and Training	5,0	4,0
Research and Innovation	5,0	5,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	0,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	5,0	4,0
Others: Health, others	1,0	4,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	5,0	
Total	3,9	3,5
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,5	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	4,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	4,5	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	3,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,5	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	4,5	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	4,5	
Total	4,2	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	4,2	

4.16 Palestine

4.16.1 Profile

No data at GGKP available.

4.16.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Development Plan 2014-16 (NDP); National Agriculture Sector Strategy 2014-16 (NASS); Water Sector Reform Plan 2014-2016 (WSRP); National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2012-14 (NEEAP)
Main focus	General short term development plan and related sectorial and specific sub-plans
Short description	Palestinian Authority drafts the national development plan every 2 years, where it describes the general strategic objectives aiming towards prosperity and sovereignty.
Prepared by / Published by	Prime Minister Rami Hamdallah
Political backing	Council of Ministers
History / background	Security in food, energy and economic as well as territorial autonomy are aspirations that all successive national plans work for by laying out relevant objectives and targets.
Website English version	Ministry of Interior: http://www.moi.gov.ps/en/ Ministry of Agriculture: http://www.moa.gov.ps/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1368&Itemid=268
Local language version	Ministry of Interior: http://www.moi.gov.ps/ Ministry of Agriculture: http://www.moa.gov.ps
First Date of publication	2014
Last update	-

4.16.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Palestine's strategy is considered **weak** because despite incorporating the principles of sustainable development in some strategic objectives, several sectors of the economy lack objectives that relate to GE and there is no overall GE/SD specific strategy.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatively well developed objectives in the areas of Forests, focusing on sustainable management and afforestation; and RE, expanding production and supporting auto consumption Document prepared in consultation with several stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No GE/SD strategy Objectives relate poorly to sustainability in areas regarding: Transport, Tourism, Research & Innovation, and management of ecosystem services Mainly short term objectives

Status/follow-up: No follow up planned

Note: *Palestine's assessment must be treated with care, as it is the only country in this report that does not enjoy an effective permanent sovereignty over its natural resources, a condition that limits the planning capabilities of Palestine and the successful completion of its objectives.*

Brown economy: Israel provides to Palestine energy mostly derived from fossil fuels. Israel has plans to extract natural gas from the Leviathan gas reserve in the Mediterranean Sea, in order to provide energy for both Israel and Palestine.

4.16.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Palestine	
Background	16	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	2,0	
Local language version	3,0	
First Date of publication	4,0	
Last update	4,0	
Planned follow-up	5,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined	3,0	
Budget associated	3,0	
Time line	1,5	
Stakeholder involvement	3,5	
Document versions		
Associated laws	2,5	
3rd party assessment available	2,0	
References to ecological limits	2,5	
Focus on local activities	5,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,4	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,5	
Green Tax Policy	2,0	
Total	1,8	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	2,5
Fisheries	0,0	0,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	3,0	3,0
Forests	3,0	3,5
Renewable Energy	2,5	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	1,0	2,0
Waste	2,5	2,0
Buildings	1,0	2,0
Transport	1,0	1,0
Tourism	1,5	1,5
Cities	2,0	2,0
Land and coastal management	2,5	2,5
Finance	2,0	2,5
Total	2,0	2,1
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	2,5	3,5
Education and Training	3,0	2,5
Research and Innovation	1,5	1,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	2,5
Others: Health, others	3,5	3,5
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,1	2,4
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	1,5	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	0,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	2,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,5	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	2,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	4,0	
Total	2,6	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,6	

4.17 Portugal

4.17.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	21.035,00	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	4,95
Population [Mio]	10,50	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	3,77
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	114,20	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	4,03
Unemployment [%]	15,60	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	N.A.	Water Access [%]	99,80
Human Development Index	0,82	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,11	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	809,10	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	2,20
Agricultural land [%]	39,70	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	52,80
Protected areas [%]	14,70	Wealth change/cap	-446,90

4.17.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	Green Growth Commitment
Main focus	Green Growth
Short description	This document brings together the main guidelines for Green Growth, as a means of joining forces and combining the existing regulatory and planning instruments in Portugal.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry of Environment, Spatial Planning and Energy
Political backing	Minister of Environment, Spatial Planning and Energy
History / background	More than 10 years of SD strategy: Previous strategy (2005-2015)
Website English version	Only general info on the English website but some documents are translated http://www.portugal.gov.pt/en.aspx
Local language version	http://www.crescimentoverde.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/CrescimentoVerde_dig.pdf http://www.crescimentoverde.gov.pt/
First Date of publication	April 2015
Last update	-

4.17.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Portugal's Green Growth Commitment is considered **good** because it is very recent (2015) relevant for all the economic sectors covered and it focuses on Green Economy. The goals are clear and detailed with monitoring indicators for each goal; it is a complete document that covers well all the sectors of the economy.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Covers all the sectors of the economy with relevant goals and measures Wide and well described participatory process for a clear bottom-up strategy Clear targets for each goal and more than 200 performance indicators clearly defined and linked to the goals Very complete and detailed document (182 pages) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Building sector's related goals are rather weak

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet.

Any other interesting info: Portugal has faced and is facing a strong economic crisis, therefore it was seen essential to establish and implement a post-troika vision of long-term development.

4.17.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Portugal	
Background	17	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	2,5	
Local language version	3,0	
First Date of publication	5,0	
Last update	5,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	4,0	
Time line	5,0	
Stakeholder involvement	5,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	5,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	5,0	
Focus on local activities	2,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,9	
Tools		
Green Procurment	5,0	
Green Tax Policy	5,0	
Total	5,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	5,0	4,0
Fisheries	3,0	3,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	5,0
Forests	5,0	5,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	4,0
Manufacturing & industry	5,0	3,5
Waste	5,0	4,5
Buildings	3,0	2,0
Transport	5,0	5,0
Tourism	5,0	4,5
Cities	5,0	5,0
Land and coastal management	5,0	4,5
Finance	4,0	4,0
Total	4,6	4,2
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	4,0	5,0
Education and Training	4,0	4,0
Research and Innovation	4,0	4,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	4,0	5,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	4,0	4,0
Others: Health, others	4,0	5,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	4,0	4,5
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	5,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	5,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	5,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	5,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	4,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	4,3	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	4,2	

4.18 Slovenia

4.18.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	22.729,30	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	7,48
Population [Mio]	2,06	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	2,54
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	102,30	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	2,07
Unemployment [%]	8,80	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	24,90	Water Access [%]	99,60
Human Development Index	0,87	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,16	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	457,20	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	4,13
Agricultural land [%]	23,80	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	29,20
Protected areas [%]	54,90	Wealth change/cap	2.061,60

4.18.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	-1:Slovenia's Development Strategy -2: Draft for the transition of Slovenia to a low carbon society by 2050 -3:Slovenian Tourism Development Strategy (2012-2016)
Main focus	Development, Climate change, Tourism
Short description	- 1: Slovenia's Development Strategy (SDS) sets out the vision and objectives of Slovenia's development, including five development priorities with the corresponding action plans. - 2: The Low Carbon Strategy aims at setting the long-term guidelines and framework for combating climate change. - 3: The 2012-2016 Partnership for the Sustainable Development of Slovenian Tourism (the working title of the new tourism strategy) is based on experience of the previous two decades and, among others, the Slovenian Tourist Board and stakeholders from the private and civil society sectors.
Prepared / Published by	- 1: Government of the Republic of Slovenia, Institute of Macroeconomic Analysis and Development - 2: Republic of Slovenia, Government Office of Climate Change - 3: Republic of Slovenia, Ministry of Economic Development and Technology
Political backing	Government of Slovenia
History / background	Even if Slovenia does not have a proper strategy document on GE or SD, Slovenia has started to green the country, sector by sector, starting with the tourism sector in 2012.
Website English version	- 1: https://www.arrs.gov.si/en/agencija/inc/ssd-new.pdf , Document 2: http://www.arhiv.svps.gov.si/fileadmin/svps.gov.si/pageuploads/strategija/Low_carbon_strategy_Slovenia.pdf , Document 3: http://www.mgrt.gov.si/fileadmin/mgrt.gov.si/pageuploads/turizem/Turizem-strategije_politike/STRATEGIJA_ENG_WEB.pdf , Ministry English website: http://www.mop.gov.si/en/
Local language version	website: http://www.mop.gov.si/si/
First Date of publication	-1:23/06/2005 -2: not clear (2012/2013) - 3: 06/2012
Last update	

4.18.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Slovenia does not have a proper National Strategy for SD or GE. The development strategy sets out the vision and objectives of Slovenia's development but it is **weak** in terms of sustainability. In addition to this document, the government

published an interesting draft for the transition of Slovenia to a low carbon society by 2050 but it is very short (10 pages). The Tourism development strategy (2012-2016) focuses poorly on sustainable tourism.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land & Coastal Management, Agriculture, Transport and Tourism are well covered with sustainability relevant measures (when taking into account the three documents) The Low Carbon Strategy aims at setting the long-term guidelines and framework for combating climate change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No national strategy For most of the sectors the measures are not relevant in terms of sustainability Rather weak document Only few indicators Some goals are outdated Only a few pages dedicated to truly sustainable measures (2 pages in the tourism strategy and 8 in the development strategy)

Status/follow-up: No apparent follow-up planned.

4.18.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Slovenia	
Background	18	
Prepared by / Published by	5,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	1,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	5,0	
First Date of publication		
Last update		
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	3,0	
Number of indicators defined	2,0	
Budget associated	2,5	
Time line	5,0	
Stakeholder involvement	5,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	2,0	
Focus on local activities	2,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	3,2	
Tools		
Green Procurment	3,5	
Green Tax Policy	3,5	
Total	3,5	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,0	4,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,5	2,0
Forests	2,0	3,0
Renewable Energy	4,0	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	2,0	1,0
Waste	3,5	2,0
Buildings	4,0	2,0
Transport	4,0	4,0
Tourism	4,0	3,5
Cities	2,5	2,0
Land and coastal management	3,0	3,5
Finance	1,5	3,0
Total	2,8	2,5
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	2,0	1,5
Education and Training	2,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	2,0	2,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	2,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	2,0
Others: Health, others	3,0	1,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	1,8	2,0
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	1,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	3,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	2,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	1,5	
Total	2,2	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,8	

4.19 Spain

4.19.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	29.117,60	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	5,79
Population [Mio]	46,60	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	4,37
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	93,50	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	9,17
Unemployment [%]	25,20	Sanitation Access [%]	100,00
Gini-Index	35,80	Water Access [%]	100,00
Human Development Index	0,87	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-0,68	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	695,90	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	1,62
Agricultural land [%]	54,00	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	32,50
Protected areas [%]	25,30	Wealth change/cap	1.650,30

4.19.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy Spanish Sustainable Development Strategy (SSDS)

Main focus	Sustainable development
Short description	Framework policy that analyses the main challenges that endanger the sustainability of the Spanish growth model. The SSDS focuses on the environmental, social and global dimension of sustainability, and approaches the high-priority areas defined in the European Strategy according to the three dimensions mentioned. The SSDS ends with guidelines for the follow-up and revision of the strategy. This strategy is framed under the EU Sustainable Development Strategy (SDS).
Prepared / Published by	Inter-ministerial Group, Lead ministry: Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment
Political backing	Council of Ministers
History / background	This document is the first NSDN of Spain.
Website English version	National strategy link: http://www.esdn.eu/pdf/country_profiles/Spain_EEDS.pdf Ministry website: http://www.magrama.gob.es/en/
Local language version	Ministry website: http://www.magrama.gob.es/es/
First Date of publication	23/11/2007
Last update	n/a

4.19.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: The Spanish Strategy for Sustainable Development published in 2007 is considered **weak**, because even it is partially well defined, it is too old to be really relevant. Spain has not promoted any new initiative to update the GE or SD strategy in the last ten years.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land & Coastal Management, Agriculture, Water, Renewable Energy (in 2007, negative changes afterwards), Transport, Cities and Tourism are well covered with sustainability relevant measures Interesting focus on Health, Employment, Social cohesion & Poverty, as well as the promotion of international cooperation to face the challenges of Climate Change Detailed document (125 pages) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing & Industry and Finance are only poorly covered Promotion of GMOs in agriculture to assure food security No focus on Green Economy Quite old (2007) Budget not mentioned Few stakeholders mentioned, it is more a top-down strategy GDP growth appears as an important objective Renewable energy deployment has been drastically reduced since 2009

Status/follow-up: No apparent follow-up planned.

Other information: Some Spanish regions such as Catalonia have developed their own sustainable development strategy recently.

4.19.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Spain	
Background	19	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	5,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	4,0	
History / background / key hits	4,0	
Website English version	2,0	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	1,0	
Last update	1,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	5,0	
Number and description of goals	4,0	
Number of indicators defined	5,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	4,0	
Stakeholder involvement	1,0	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	1,0	
3rd party assessment available		
References to ecological limits	2,0	
Focus on local activities	1,0	
Link to SDGs	2,0	
Average	2,7	
Tools		
Green Procurement	2,0	
Green Tax Policy	4,0	
Total	3,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	4,0	3,0
Fisheries	2,0	3,5
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	4,0
Forests	3,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	2,0
Manufacturing & industry	1,5	1,0
Waste	4,0	2,0
Buildings	2,0	2,5
Transport	5,0	4,5
Tourism	5,0	2,5
Cities	4,0	3,5
Land and coastal management	5,0	3,0
Finance	1,0	1,0
Total	3,6	2,8
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	1,0	2,0
Education and Training	2,0	3,0
Research and Innovation	1,5	2,0
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,0
Others: Health, others	5,0	
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	3,0	
Total	2,1	1,8
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	1,0	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	4,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	3,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	3,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	1,0	
8 Integrating subnat, local & private action	1,0	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,5	
Total	2,4	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,8	

4.20 Tunisia

4.20.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	4.329,10	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	2,45
Population [Mio]	10,90	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	1,57
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	70,10	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	7,68
Unemployment [%]	12,80	Sanitation Access [%]	90,40
Gini-Index	35,80	Water Access [%]	96,80
Human Development Index	0,72	Electricity Access [%]	99,50
Deforestation [% change]	-1,86	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	261,80	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	N.A.
Agricultural land [%]	64,90	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	1,17
Protected areas [%]	4,82	Wealth change/cap	109,70

4.20.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of Strategy	National Strategy of Sustainable Development 2014-2020
Main focus	Sustainable Development
Short description	This document is a national framework for policies which sets targets and priorities and defines the strategy to reach it.
Prepared / Published by	The Republic of Tunisia and its Ministry of Infrastructure, Spatial Planning and Sustainable Development.
Political backing	Government of the Republic of Tunisia
History / background	Tunisia has a commitment to sustainable development policies since 1988. After 2011 the Tunisian authorities started to introduce a new sustainable development strategy in line with its international commitments, as well as the Sustainable Development Goals set by UN countries for the period 2015-2030.
Website English version	http://www.environnement.gov.tn/index.php?id=21&L=1#.VzRHvISLTIU
Local language version	http://www.andd2014.gov.tn/pdf/SNDD-Rapport%20Version%20Mai%202014.pdf
First Date of publication	March 31 st , 2014
Last update	May, 2014

4.20.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Tunisia's National Sustainable Development Strategy 2014-2020 is considered **good** because it is recent, relevant and directly linked to the SDGs. It is a complete strategy and a real framework for policies in Tunisia. Fisheries, Finance and Green Jobs are not well covered though.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete and detailed document (93 pages) • Covers almost all the sectors of the economy with sustainability relevant goals and measures • Wide and well described participatory process for a clear bottom-up strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Economy is recognised as a challenge but there are just two mentions of the term in the document. • Fisheries, Finance and Green Jobs are poorly covered

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet, but probably 2020 at the end of term of the strategy (2015-2020).

4.20.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Tunisia	
Background	20	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	5,0	
Local language version	3,5	
First Date of publication	4,0	
Last update	4,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	3,5	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	4,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	5,0	
Stakeholder involvement	4,0	
Document versions	2,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available	2,0	
References to ecological limits	2,0	
Focus on local activities	2,5	
Link to SDGs	5,0	
Average	3,6	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	5,0	3,0
Fisheries	3,0	2,5
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	5,0	5,0
Forests	5,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	5,0	4,0
Manufacturing & industry	5,0	3,0
Waste	5,0	3,5
Buildings	5,0	4,0
Transport	5,0	3,5
Tourism	5,0	3,5
Cities	5,0	4,0
Land and coastal management	5,0	4,5
Finance	1,0	1,0
Total	4,5	3,5
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	5,0	3,5
Education and Training	5,0	4,0
Research and Innovation	5,0	3,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,0
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,5
Others: Health, others	5,0	3,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production	5,0	
Total	3,9	2,8
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	4,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	2,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	4,0	
6 Mobilizing investment	1,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	4,0	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,5	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,0	
Total	2,9	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	3,6	

4.21 Turkey

4.21.1 Profile

Source: Green Growth Knowledge Platform 2016

GDP/cap. [US\$]	10,945,90	CO ₂ emissions [metric tons/cap]	4,13
Population [Mio]	74,90	Carbon productivity [GDP/kg CO ₂]	1,90
Pop. Density [people/km ²]	97,40	Air pollution (PM2,5) [µg/m ³]	12,10
Unemployment [%]	9,20	Sanitation Access [%]	91,20
Gini-Index	40,00	Water Access [%]	99,70
Human Development Index	0,76	Electricity Access [%]	N.A.
Deforestation [% change]	-1,11	Fossil fuel subsidies	N.A.
Freshwater withdrawal [m ³ /cap]	535,10	Environm. Tax [% GDP]	3,63
Agricultural land [%]	49,90	Renewable electricity [% of mix]	26,40
Protected areas [%]	2,11	Wealth change/cap	660,30

4.21.2 National Green Economy or Sustainable Development Strategy

Name of strategy	Climate Change Strategy (2010-2020)
Main focus	Climate Change and Sustainable Development
Short description	This document is a national framework for SD policies which sets targets and priorities and defines the strategy to reach those targets.
Prepared / Published by	Ministry of Environment and Urbanization
Political backing	Erdoğan Bayraktar, former minister of Environment and Urbanization
History / background	2001: Establishment of the Coordination Board on Climate Change (CBCC). 2004: Turkey became a party of the UNFCCC. 2009: Ratification of Kyoto Protocol. 2010: expansion of 11 technical working groups of the CBCC
Website English version	http://www.dsi.gov.tr/docs/iklim-degisikligi/ulusal_iklim_de%C4%9Fi%C5%9Fikli%C4%9Fi_strateji_belgesi_eng.pdf?sfvrsn=0
Local language version	http://tarim.kalkinma.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/iklim_Degisikligi_Stratejisi-04-11-2014.pdf
First Date of publication	May 03, 2010
Last update	April 04, 2014

4.21.3 Snapshot / Evaluation

Summary: Turkey's Climate Change Strategy 2010-2020 is considered **moderate** because it is not very relevant in terms of sustainability, the goals are often unclear and some of them are outdated. It does have a short, medium and long term vision.

Strong points	Weak points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interesting short, medium and long term vision for the sectors mentioned • Water, Forests and Transport sectors are well covered with sustainability relevant measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many sectors mentioned are not so relevant in terms of sustainability • Cities, Building, Fisheries, Tourism and Green Jobs are not covered at all • Short and superficial document (32 pages)

Status/follow-up: No follow-up planned yet, probably 2020 at the end of term of this strategy (2010-2020).

4.21.4 Evaluation Details

Criteria	Turkey	
Background	21	
Prepared by / Published by	4,0	
Political backing	4,0	
Level (national, regional, local)	5,0	
History / background / key hits	5,0	
Website English version	4,0	
Local language version	4,0	
First Date of publication	3,0	
Last update	4,0	
Planned follow-up	1,0	
Nº of pages (total, core, annex)	1,0	
Number and description of goals	5,0	
Number of indicators defined	1,0	
Budget associated	1,0	
Time line	3,0	
Stakeholder involvement	3,5	
Document versions	1,0	
Associated laws	4,0	
3rd party assessment available	4,0	
References to ecological limits	3,0	
Focus on local activities	3,0	
Link to SDGs	3,0	
Average	3,2	
Tools		
Green Procurement	1,0	
Green Tax Policy	1,0	
Total	1,0	
Sectors covered		Quality
Agriculture	3,5	3,0
Fisheries	1,0	1,0
Water (rivers, sea, ...)	2,5	4,0
Forests	3,0	4,0
Renewable Energy	3,0	3,0
Manufacturing & industry	3,0	3,0
Waste	3,0	3,5
Buildings	1,0	1,0
Transport	3,0	4,0
Tourism	1,0	1,0
Cities	1,0	3,0
Land and coastal management	3,0	3,5
Finance	3,0	3,0
Total	2,4	2,8
Cross-cutting, transversal sectors / topics		Quality
Governance & civil society engagement	3,5	3,5
Education and Training	3,5	4,0
Research and Innovation	3,5	3,5
Assessment / Mgmt. of ecosystem services	1,0	1,5
Green Jobs and green entrepreneurship	1,0	1,5
Others: Health, others	3,0	3,0
SCP : Sustainable Consumption & Production		
Total	2,6	2,8
Evaluation applying GGBP criteria (adapted)		
1 Planning, governance and co-ordination	3,5	
2 Establishing vision, baselines, and targets	2,0	
3 Assessing & communicating benefits of GE	2,0	
4 Prioritization of GE options & pathways	2,0	
5 Policy design and implementation	3,5	
6 Mobilizing investment	2,0	
7 Public-private collaboration	3,5	
8 Integrating subnat., local & private action	3,5	
9 Monitoring and evaluation scheme	3,5	
Total	2,8	
Total (average, all weighted equal)	2,7	

5

Financing Green Economy

5.1 Introduction

5.1.1 Definitions

What emerges from a literature review in the area of Green Growth, Green Economy or climate finance is that there is little available on the definition of 'green finance'. This lack of conceptualisation makes the assessment problematic as terms are not used consistently and data cannot be easily compared across sources. Different definitions have been proposed in the paper "South-originating Green Finance"⁸⁵ and are showed in the box below.

Green investment refers to the overall capital cost of the transition to a green economy, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, increasing resilience, securing food systems and managing of water, forest, transport and waste systems.

Green finance represents a wider lens than green investment. It includes capital cost and, unlike green investment, includes operational costs such as project preparation and land acquisition costs.

South-originating green finance is the green finance originating broadly in non-OECD countries, from both private and public sources, and both cross-border financial flows and domestic finance.

Climate finance is distinguished from green finance or investment by referring specifically to the financial flows deemed eligible to be counted as part of the UNFCCC process.

In this study we refer to green finance broadly as the set of financial mechanisms, tools and programs to promote sustainable development, as opposed to a reduced green finance scope which is only focused on financing of environmental projects. In our definition, we also assume that green finance should integrate social goals such as inclusiveness, fairness or equity in the same line as our definition of Green Economy as formulated in Chapter 1.

85 Zadek and Flynn (2013). South Originating Green Finance: exploring the potential. The Geneva International Finance Dialogues; UNEP inquiry report.

5.1.2 Pillars and role of green and inclusive finance

Financing sustainable development is possible through efficient markets, risk management and ethical standards. While an efficient market should guarantee fair allocation of resources to benefit communities, risk management refers to addressing adequately the consequences of societal risks (such as climate change, geopolitics, etc.); ethical standards ensure fair treatment to all parties including future generations and minorities. Efficiency, risk management and ethical standards are therefore main pillars of green finance, which can contribute in a tangible and measurable way to the Sustainable Development of the Mediterranean region.

5.1.3 Main barriers to green finance

The International Finance Corporation's report on "Inclusive Green Growth Investment"⁸⁶ reviews the existing mechanisms to mobilize private capital for inclusive green growth (IGG) investments in developing countries. It reveals that, for the investors, the main barriers to **green investments** in such countries are the following:

Unclear business case: perceived lack of opportunities, policy reversals.

Policy uncertainties: lack of meaningful action on climate.

Country risks: poor governance and inadequate investment processes.

Lack of track record and experience.

Liquidity concerns: green infrastructure investments can tie up capital.

Investment time horizons: financial performance assessed on short-term results.

To efficiently promote Green Economy, such barriers have to be addressed adequately through the development and implementation of strategies and actions linked with awareness, training, technical support, financial incentives and public/political leadership.

5.2 Review of financial actors

Financial institutions have a critical role in supporting the transition to Green Economy that requires diverse and adaptable investments into green infrastructures, businesses and activities. In this subchapter, we review the most relevant actors and their potential contribution to this green transition.

5.2.1 Multilateral Development Banks

*World Bank*⁸⁷

The World Bank Group (WBG) is a global financial institution that provides loans to developing countries. Since 2011, it has committed USD 52 billion to more than 900 climate-related projects, an average of USD 10.3 billion per year. In 2015, the WBG made 188 climate-change related investments in 59 countries, ranging from helping farmers adapt to a changing climate with heat resistant seeds to new investments in renewable energy. The private-sector arm of the WBG, the International Finance Corporation (IFC), started tracking the climate-smart components of its investments and advisory services in 2005. Since then, it has provided about USD 13 billion in long-term financing for renewable power, energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, green buildings and private sector adaptation to climate change.

In Jordan, through an investment of USD 79.66 million and the mobilization of an additional USD 107 million, the IFC helped fund the construction of seven solar PV projects to boost renewables use and transform the country's energy sector. The project is the largest private-sector led solar initiative in the Middle East and North Africa⁸⁸.

The World Bank Group approved Global Environment Facility (GEF) and Special Climate Change Fund grants totalling USD 8.73 million for the West Balkans Drin River Basin Management Project for Bosnia and Herzegovina (USD 3.37 million), Montenegro (USD 2.72 million), and Serbia (USD 2.63 million). The project aims to ensure a rational and equitable management of the Drin River basin supporting the significant socio-economic development opportunities offered by its abundant natural resources, while at the same time protecting the environment⁸⁹.

Nevertheless, the World Bank still finances fossil fuel projects, despite repeated calls by its president to end the global subsidies

86 International Finance Corporation (2013). Mobilizing Public and Private Funds for Inclusive Green Growth Investment in Developing Countries.

87 <http://www.worldbank.org>

88 <http://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/climatefinance/overview>

89 <http://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2016/05/09/bosnia-and-herzegovina-montenegro-and-serbia-cooperate-to-strengthen-resilience-to-climate-change>

for oil, coal and gas. Oil Change International (OCI)⁹⁰ identified USD 3.4bn of loans, grants, guarantees, risk management and equity for fossil fuel-related projects in the developing world in the 2013-14 financial year⁹¹.

European Investment Bank (EIB)⁹²

The EIB is the European Union's non-profit long-term lending institution established in 1958 under the Treaty of Rome. As a "policy-driven bank" whose shareholders are the member states of the EU, the EIB uses its financing operations to bring about European integration and social cohesion. It is the world's largest international public lending institution.

In 2015, renewables financing by the EIB totalled EUR 34 billion (including 434 million for projects to connect renewable energy to national electricity networks, 464 million for offshore wind, 752 million for onshore wind, 405 million for solar, 373 million for hydropower, 13 million for geothermal). In 2015, the EIB also financed EUR 19.6 billion in projects enhancing environmental protection in various sectors (energy, transport, water, biodiversity, forests...). For instance, the EIB gave a strong support (400 million EUR) for the energy efficiency of public buildings in France⁹³.

EIB also works to develop opportunities and support its southern Mediterranean neighbours by providing private sector support in the areas of MSMEs, industry, energy, transport and telecom, environment and human and social capital. As an example, the EIB signed in 2016 a loan contract with Groupe Chimique Tunisien (GCT) for EUR 19 million to reduce the environmental impact of GCT's production activities. This additional loan follows on from an initial EUR 55 million contract signed in 2008 for the same environmental upgrading project⁹⁴. In 2016, The Arab Republic of Egypt and the EIB signed a loan agreement worth EUR 200 million for financing a project to promote public transport in Greater Cairo⁹⁵. It is too early to evaluate the real impact of these large investments.

However, a closer look at the EIB investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy *vis-à-vis* fossil fuels, reveals that its contribution to the global effort to tackle the climate crisis remains insufficient at best. Most notably, during 2013-2015, EIB lending toward renewables in Europe has dropped, whereas its lending to fossil fuels has modestly but consistently increased⁹⁶.

European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)⁹⁷

The EBRD is a multilateral development bank founded in 1991 and originally created to support the transition of eastern countries towards market economy, investing mainly in private businesses. It has since then expanded its activities into other regions such as the Mediterranean. The EBRD's activities focus on fostering the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) through investments in loans and equities, boosting agribusiness, improving banking services, creating local capital markets and supporting renewable energy and energy efficiency. By November 2015 the EBRD had invested close to EUR 2.3 billion in more than 80 projects in the SEMED region, in addition to EUR 82 million in technical assistance funded by donors and shareholders⁹⁸.

In 2015 the EBRD launched the Green Economy Transition (GET) approach⁹⁹ to contribute in mitigating and building resilience to the effects of climate change and other forms of environmental degradation. EBRD financed more than 1000 "green" projects since 2006 accounting for EUR 19.6 billion in investments. As an example of green investment in the SEMED region, we can mention the EUR 10 million in debt financing for the construction, development and operation of five solar photovoltaic parks with total capacity of 11.9 MWp that EBRD gave to Cyprus in 2016¹⁰⁰.

However, if we have a closer look at the EBRD funded projects in the energy sector we can see that, despite the bank's rhetoric about promoting sustainable energy, its balance sheet has still fossil fuels assets. Indeed, a recent research¹⁰¹ has indicated that,

90 <http://priceofoil.org/>

91 <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2015/apr/17/world-bank-fossil-fuel-lending-leapt-in-2014-despite-its-calls-to-end-subsidies>

92 <http://www.eib.org/?lang=en>

93 <http://www.eib.org/infocentre/press/releases/all/2015/2015-296-soutien-massif-400-meur-de-la-bei-pour-lefficacite-energetique-des-batiments-publics-en-france-avec-la-banque-postale-le-groupe-bpce-et-le-credit-agricole.htm?lang=en>

94 <http://www.eib.org/infocentre/press/releases/all/2016/2016-128-la-bei-accorde-un-pret-de-19-meur-42-m-tnd-en-faveur-de-laction-climat-en-tunisie.htm>

95 <http://www.eib.org/infocentre/press/releases/all/2015/2015-319-eib-promotes-public-transport-in-egypt-with-eur-200-million-loan-for-cairo-metro.htm>

96 <http://bankwatch.org/publications/european-investment-bank-and-its-energy-sector-lending-2013-2015>

97 <http://www.ebrd.com/home>

98 <http://www.ebrd.com/the-EBRD-and-the-SEMED.html>

99 <http://www.ebrd.com/what-we-do/get.html>

100 <http://www.ebrd.com/news/2016/ebrd-supports-expansion-of-solar-energy-in-cyprus.html>

101 <http://bankwatch.org/news-media/blog/ebrd-fueling-future-or-stuck-past>

between 2012 and 2014, almost 70% of the bank's financing in SEMED countries' energy sectors (EUR 419 million) was spent on oil and gas-based electricity generation, as well as hydrocarbon extraction and distribution. By contrast, the bank's support for renewables and energy efficiency totalled just 14%, or EUR 85 million. One illustration is the EUR 156 million the EBRD lent to the state-owned Egyptian Electricity Holding Company to convert two existing power plants to combined cycle gas turbines, in order to increase their generation capacity.

*African Development Bank Group (AfDB)*¹⁰²

The AfDB, founded in 1964, is a multilateral development finance institution established to contribute to the economic development and social progress of African countries. Recently the AfDB launched a Green Bond Program¹⁰³ in order to promote green growth through the financing of eligible climate change projects. It already funds projects in Morocco, Tunisia and Egypt especially in the areas of water and energy.

Since 2012, AfDB supports the Ouarzazate (Morocco) solar power station project with EUR 168 million, from its own resources, in addition to a concessional loan of USD 100 million granted through the Clean Technology Fund (CTF), one of the AfDB-hosted Climate Investment Funds (CIF)¹⁰⁴. In 2012, AfDB also gave a EUR 32 million loan to Tunisia in order to finance a waste water treatment infrastructure rehabilitation project across the country. The project will improve the quality of treated water used to irrigate 8,500 hectares of farmland and open land¹⁰⁵.

5.2.2 Bilateral Development Banks / Institutions

*AFD*¹⁰⁶

The AFD (French Agency for Development) is a French public financial institution that implements the policy defined by the French Government. It works to fight poverty and promote sustainable development. This public institution is active in Africa, Asia, the Middle East, Latin America, the Caribbean and the French overseas territories. In 2015, AFD Group committed over EUR 2.9 billion to finance 82 climate projects that contribute to preventing the temperature from rising and increase resilience to the consequences of climate change (renewable energy, energy efficiency, clean transport, forest protection, agro-ecology, climate change adaptation). In 2015, climate projects accounted for 63% of financing in the Mediterranean. In 2013, the French Global Environment Facility (FFEM) financed the ACCAGRIMAG Project for EUR 1.5 million to facilitate climate change adaptation measures for agriculture in Morocco and Tunisia. In 2014, AFD Group supported the development of renewable energy in Jordan, which is highly dependent on hydrocarbons. With EBRD, AFD has allocated a USD 100 million loan for the construction of three of the first solar power plants in the country¹⁰⁷.

*KfW*¹⁰⁸

The KfW is a German government-owned development bank, based in Frankfurt. It was formed in 1948 after World War II as part of the Marshall Plan. KfW is operating worldwide (Balkans, North Africa, the Middle East) and is promoting climate-friendly projects. 4.7 billion EUR (64 %) of the 2014 commitments totalling EUR 7.3 billion pertained to climate and environmental protection. KfW issued the largest green bond ever with a volume of EUR 1.5 billion¹⁰⁹. In 2015, KfW provided support for sustainable energy investment in Morocco together with EBRD, AfD and EIB for a total amount of EUR 80 million¹¹⁰.

5.3 International financial frameworks, tools and initiatives

In this sub-chapter we explore the different initiatives and programmes linked with green finance at national or international level.

5.3.1 European financial system

Innovations in ethical finance, social entrepreneurship and responsible investment are practical efforts to build a financial

102 <http://www.afdb.org>

103 <http://www.afdb.org/en/topics-and-sectors/initiatives-partnerships/green-bond-program>

104 <http://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/article/morocco-works-on-worlds-largest-solar-plant-financed-by-afdb-go-underway-11775/>

105 <http://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/article/afdb-loans-eur32-5m-to-tunisia-to-boost-flow-of-irrigation-water-to-countrys-farms-8881/>

106 <http://www.afd.fr/>

107 http://www.afd.fr/webdav/site/afd/shared/PORTAILS/SECTEURS/CLIMAT/fiches-2015-va/AFD_solutions-around-the-world.pdf

108 <https://www.kfw-entwicklungsbank.de/International-financing/KfW-Entwicklungsbank/>

109 https://www.kfw.de/KfW-Group/Newsroom/Aktuelles/Pressemitteilungen/Pressemitteilungen-Details_214336.html

110 <http://www.ebrd.com/news/2015/international-support-for-sustainable-energy-investment-in-morocco.html>

system that supports sustainable development, which emerged from European financial capitals such as London, Paris and Frankfurt. EU Member States organizations and firms pioneered the debate on sustainability-related disclosure (including GHG emissions), environmental, social and governance (ESG) integration and environmental finance markets. Today Europe is home to the largest share of assets managed in accordance with ESG factors, with 64% of the global total. 47% of the signatories to the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI) are based in the EU. The EU and its Member States are global leaders in climate finance, delivering a combined total of EUR 14.5 billion in 2014¹¹¹.

Furthermore, a focus on systemic risk led to the implementation of new regulatory frameworks for banking, insurance and investment. Several initiatives relevant to sustainable finance, are currently underway within the European Commission level and Member States, but there is still a lack in considering these at a strategic level, to seek the proactive contribution of the financial system to both renewed economic competitiveness and enhanced sustainability performance.

5.3.2 UNEP Finance Initiative

Over 200 institutions, including banks, insurers and fund managers, work globally to understand the impacts of environmental and social considerations on financial performance through the **UNEP Finance Initiative** (UNEP FI)¹¹². The Initiative's work includes:

- Capacity building and sharing of good practices;
- Pioneering research and tools;
- Setting global standards and principles;
- Engaging stakeholders, both public and private;
- Facilitating the networking through global events and regional activities.

While most of the major financial institutions from the North Mediterranean have joined UNEP FI, only the Moroccan bank BMCE is a member from the South Mediterranean side.

5.3.3 Thematic funds

*Green for Growth Fund (GGF)*¹¹³

The GGF was initiated in December 2009 by the European Investment Bank and KfW Development Bank, along with financial support from the European Commission and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development. They committed for EUR 367 million of capital. The purpose of the GGF is to broaden the financing base of energy efficiency and renewable energy investments in Southeast Europe, the European Eastern Neighbourhood region, and recently expanded to include North Africa and the Middle East. In addition, it increases awareness of energy efficiency and small renewable energy products among companies and private households and contributes to broadening and deepening the financial sector servicing those development needs.

While the initiative to create a thematic fund to finance Green Growth is of course positive, the dedicated amount is far too low to be effective and relevant.

*Climate Investment Funds (CIF)*¹¹⁴

The Climate Investment Funds (CIF) was launched in 2008 by multilateral development banks to mobilize significant climate finance to developing countries to support high impact investments in renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transport, climate resilience and sustainable forest management. With USD 8.3 billion, it is supporting 72 developing and middle income countries to manage climate change challenges and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In 2013, the Climate Investment Fund provided USD 660 million to Algeria, Egypt, Jordan, Libya, Morocco and Tunisia to support the creation of 1,120 megawatts (MW) from Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants for the region¹¹⁵.

Other thematic funds are also available or near to be launched. But for the scope of this study we focused on the most innovative or active in the Mediterranean region. It could be interesting to further investigate what are the best institutions and financing mechanisms that could support an effective and fast implementation of green economy in the region.

111 The Inquiry and The 2° Investing Initiative (2016). Building a Sustainable Financial System in the European Union. The Five 'R's of Market and Policy Innovation for the Green Transition

112 <http://www.unepfi.org/>

113 <http://www.ggf.lu>

114 <http://www-cif.climateinvestmentfunds.org>

115 <http://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/article/climate-investment-funds-give-north-africa-and-middle-east-green-light-for-revised-regional-solar-plan-11734/>

5.3.4 Green Bonds

The European Investment Bank (EIB) issued the first green bond in the form of a structured product in 2007. The market has now grown from USD 4 billion in 2010 to over USD 37 billion in 2014¹¹⁶. Green bonds integrate environmental criteria, earmark proceeds and monitoring actions¹¹⁷. According to the Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI) 2014 report¹¹⁸, green bonds are mainly issued from Development banks (44%), Corporate (33%) and Municipalities (13%).

Figure 4.1: Global labelled green bond issuance (USD billion/year), Source: Climate Bonds Initiative (2016)¹¹⁹

The World Bank also launched its own Green Bonds, raising funds from fixed income investors to support projects that mitigate climate change or help affected people adapt to it. Since 2008, the World Bank has issued over USD 9 billion equivalent in Green Bonds through more than 120 transactions in 18 currencies¹²⁰. In the MENA region, World Bank Green Bonds were issued to finance green projects in Morocco (Ouarzazate Solar Power), Tunisia (Northwest Mountainous and Forested Areas) and Turkey (Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency)¹²¹.

5.3.5 Other financial tools

Apart from the traditional financial tools listed above, new informal mechanisms are emerging in the Mediterranean region, such as the diaspora economic capability that can be canalized through crowdfunding platforms, particularly relevant for financing new green businesses¹²².

The SwitchMed initiative, mentioned in chapter 1, is also promoting a Green Impact Investing Network in the MENA region. The aim of the Network is to create a group of interested international and national financing institutions that can invest in green start-ups in the North African countries¹²³.

5.4 Climate finance

Only climate finance has available consolidated reports, such as the one published each year by the Climate Policy Initiative (CPI)¹²⁴ that defines geographical, institutional and political structures and gaps on financing climate change mitigation and adaptation. In this chapter, we therefore analyse the origin and distribution of climate finance as an approximation to green finance's state of play.

116 EC DG Clima (2015). Shifting private finance towards climate-friendly investments

117 The World Bank & IPIAF (2015). What are green bonds http://treasury.worldbank.org/cmd/pdf/What_are_Green_Bonds.pdf

118 CBI (2016). Scaling up green bond markets for sustainable development. <https://www.climatebonds.net/resources/publications/scaling-green-bond-markets-sustainable-development>

119 <https://www.climatebonds.net/resources/publications/scaling-green-bond-markets-sustainable-development>

120 <http://treasury.worldbank.org/cmd/htm/WorldBankGreenBonds.html>

121 <http://treasury.worldbank.org/cmd/htm/MoreGreenProjects.html>

122 <http://www.switchmed.eu/en/e-library/synthesis-of-the-survey-on-crowdfunding-in-the-mena-region>

123 <http://www.switchmed.eu/en/corners/impact-investors>

124 CPI (2015). Global Landscape of Climate Finance 2015 <http://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Global-Landscape-of-Climate-Finance-2015.pdf>

Figure 4.2: Global landscape of climate finance 2015 (Source: Climate Policy Initiative)

According to the CPI study, the main investors are multilateral, bilateral and national Development Finance Institutions (DFIs)¹²⁵ with a commitment of USD 131 billion covering 33% of total Climate Finance. Public actors, including governments and bilateral aid agencies (commitment of USD 15 billion) and Climate Funds (USD 2 billion), drive the bankability of such investments by reducing the costs and risks of climate investments and strengthening knowledge and technical capacity of government and private sector actors. Meanwhile private investors contribute to climate finance by controlling the resources needed to steer the transition towards low-carbon and climate-resilient growth.

This study also shows that private actors rely primarily on their own resources to finance renewable energy projects (corporate and households), which globally accounted for USD 175 billion or 72% of total private investment in 2014. Project developers remained the most prominent private investor class with USD 92 billion, or 38% of total global private climate finance. Commercial institutions contribution is USD 42 billion; and private equity, venture capital, infrastructure funds contribute just USD 1.7 billion. Institutional investors – with just USD 0.9 billion – are generally increasingly investing more in fixed income and alternatives, and less in equities.

As final use, mitigation accounted for 93% of total climate finance in 2014, or USD 361 billion, 81% of which went toward renewable energy. Adaptation finance reached USD 25 billion or 17% of all public climate finance in the same year.

Most of climate finance providers and beneficiaries (74%) reside in the same country highlighting the importance of domestic frameworks for attracting investment. Western Europe is the second main destination of climate finance flows worldwide in 2014, totalling 24% of flows for USD 93 billion¹²⁶, while the Middle East and North Africa region, in the same year experienced a significant increase in climate finance investments up by 114%. Morocco is in fact the fourth country receiving most of climate finance funds in the world (USD 628 million), while Turkey (USD 439 million) and Egypt (USD 197 million) are included in the top 20 countries (see figure below).

125 "National and international development finance institutions (DFIs) are specialised development banks or subsidiaries, majority-owned by national governments, set up to support private sector development in developing countries" OECD <http://www.oecd.org/dac/stats/development-finance-institutions-private-sector-development.htm>

126 (<http://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Global-Landscape-of-Climate-Finance-2015.pdf>)

Multilateral climate finance recipients

Figure 4.3 Climate Finance Funds, Mediterranean countries (Source: www.climatefundsupdate.org, May 2016)

5.5 Examples of national strategies

In this subchapter we briefly present green finance strategies from two very different countries: France and Tunisia. These two countries, so dissimilar in size, history, culture and socio-economic structure, demonstrate that it is possible to reform the financial sector to enhance its contribution to green economy projects and initiatives.

5.5.1 France

The French strategy¹²⁷ to mainstreaming sustainability issues in the national financial sector can be summarised in three areas of action:

- **Better disclosure of risks and impacts.** Reporting for listed companies on governance and social issues is now mandatory as part of the 2001 New Economic Regulation law (NRE) dealing with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). ESG reporting is mainstreamed for financial institutions in 2010 through the adoption of the Grenelle II law¹²⁸, which addresses a broad range of environmental issues.
- **Transparency and information.** In addition to transparency and reporting, the labelling of financial products is seen as a useful tool to support the development of Socially Responsible Investment products. The purpose is to give sufficient, reliable and concise information on extra-financial issues to inform investors' choices.
- **Capital mobilization,** complemented by climate strategies and public intervention. Since public financial institutions represent a relatively small part in the volume of the French financial system, their action to support national policy objectives through direct financing, is supported by market development and capacity building actions.

5.5.2 Tunisia

Tunisia¹²⁹ has been adopting a legislative and regulatory framework to finance investments in renewable energy, energy efficient and other environment-friendly technologies. It is mainly counting on multilateral institutions and government funding. In fact, businesses investing in green sectors can receive financing from international credit lines, grants and national funds.

Tunisia's policies ensure the involvement of commercial banks, simplifying administrative procedures and creating reliable quality management. The combination of a suitable and affordable finance mechanism, a simplified administrative procedure and an extensive quality verification system with penalties for failure, ensures repayment of product loans to financial institutions.

Moreover, the introduction of mandatory energy audits for energy-intensive companies, together with subsidies for subsequent energy efficiency measures through the national fund for energy conservation, has increased awareness of the financial benefit of energy efficiency and led to substantial investments in energy efficiency by the industry.

127 The Inquiry and I4CE – Institute for Climate Economics (2015). France's Financial (Eco)system Improving the Integration of Sustainability Factors, http://unepinquiry.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/France_Financial_Ecosystem.pdf

128 http://www.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Grenelle_Loi-2_GB_.pdf

129 GIZ (2014). Financing Green Growth. A review of green financial sector policies in emerging and developing economies, p. 83-88

5.6 Women's access to finance

Advancing women's access to finance is a critical socio-economic challenge¹³⁰, in particular in the Southern Mediterranean countries where the need for legislation and legal reform in Women's Human Rights and Gender Equality should become a priority¹³¹ and a pillar for cross border cooperation in the region.¹³² The economic challenges women have to face are even more important when it comes to the transition from traditional economy to an inclusive green economy, where ethics, responsibility and innovation are strongly required.

As shown in the following figure, the actual general admission of women to the formal economy compared to men, using being a bank account holder as basic indicator, divides the Mediterranean countries into different groups.

Figure 4.4: Statistics on accounts in financial institutions for men and women (Source: Gender Statistics, The World Bank¹³³)

In just a few countries, more than 75% of women can be active economic agents (Spain, Malta, France, Cyprus, Israel, Croatia, Greece and Italy) with a very small difference to their male counterparts. In Croatia the share of women having a bank account is 3.5% higher than men. This can be explained by having more women than men in tertiary education and consequently a higher than EU-27 average rate (16%) of women holding board positions in large companies (16% compared to 14% EU-average)¹³⁴. Montenegro follows with a rate of 58% and a male-female difference of 4%. In all other countries less than 50% of women have a bank account, with a notable two-digit difference compared to men. Turkey shows the highest spread of almost 25 percentage points.

The full set of data for selected Mediterranean countries is exhibited in the following table together with other economic indicators showing the ability of women - compared to men - to borrow money for their business or to start a new business:

130 McKinsey Global Institute (2015) How advancing women's equality can add \$12 trillion to global growth

131 Regional Situation Analysis: Women's Human Rights and Gender Equality in the Southern Mediterranean (2010) EU Neighbourhood Library <http://www.enpi-info.eu/library/content/regional-situation-analysis-women%E2%80%99s-human-rights-and-gender-equality-southern-mediterranean>

132 EuroMed info center (2016) Gender equality, a pillar of Cross Border Cooperation in the Mediterranean <http://www.enpi-info.eu/medportal/news/latest/45434/Gender-equality,-a-pillar-of-Cross-Border-Cooperation-in-the-Mediterranean>

133 <http://databank.worldbank.org>

134 The current situation of gender equality in Croatia – Country Profile 2012 http://ec.europa.eu/justice/gender-equality/files/epo_campaign/country-profile_croatia_en.pdf

2014	Account at a financial institution, female (% age 15+) [ts]	Account at a financial institution, male (% age 15+) [ts]	Borrowed from a financial institution, female (% age 15+) [ts]	Borrowed from a financial institution, male (% age 15+) [ts]	Borrowed to start, operate, or expand a farm or business, female (% age 15+) [w2]	Borrowed to start, operate, or expand a farm or business, male (% age 15+) [w2]
Albania	33.6	42.5	9.7	10.8	3.0	4.9
Algeria	40.1	60.9	3.0	1.3	2.3	5.7
Bosnia and Herzegovina	47.1	58.8	16.3	11.5	2.0	2.7
Croatia	87.7	84.2	20.3	26.0	2.9	5.6
Cyprus	90.3	90.0	9.2	10.0	0.8	2.6
France	95.5	97.8	14.7	15.6	1.0	3.3
Greece	86.6	88.5	9.1	11.3	0.3	2.1
Egypt, Arab Rep.	9.2	18.0	4.9	7.6	1.2	3.5
Israel	90.0	89.9	40.2	40.8	3.9	8.0
Italy	83.2	91.9	10.6	16.6	0.6	1.7
Lebanon	32.9	62.4	10.9	20.8	4.1	8.0
Morocco
Spain	97.6	97.6	15.5	20.6	4.7	7.6
Tunisia	20.5	34.1	6.2	9.9	3.3	5.9
Turkey	44.3	69.0	14.8	25.3	3.2	4.3
Jordan	15.5	33.3	10.3	16.7	1.5	3.9
Malta	95.6	97.1	9.4	9.6	1.2	0.7
Montenegro	57.9	61.9	21.4	25.7	2.9	4.4

Source: Gender Statistics. Click on a metadata icon for original source information to be used for citation.

Table 4.1: Financial Gender Statistics of Mediterranean Countries (Source: World Bank)

The map below shows how the access to financial borrowing is distributed for females around the Mediterranean. Israel has the highest degree of 40%. Very low rates characterize the situation in Egypt, Algeria and Greece. With an unstable political and economic context, they may have other priorities than introducing gender criteria/incentives and even more so green growth or sustainability in their development policies. Surprisingly also in Italy women have a low access to borrowed finance.

Figure 4.5: Map of female borrowing from financial institutions (Source: authors' elaboration based on World Bank data)

Receiving borrowed money to start a business shows a wide inequality between men and women in every country with a difference up to 4 percentage points (Israel, even though rates are overall higher in Israel for both men and women compared to other countries). The borrowing process for a new business normally includes an existent credit risk profile and collateral availability. Both requirements are very difficult to satisfy for a woman particularly in the Southern Mediterranean. Furthermore, in the case of an innovative green business, the credit risk scores even higher because of the market perception that innovation is risky and 'green' is less profitable (as an example Venture Capital investments in green Small Medium Enterprises are just 2% of the economy in Europe)¹³⁵.

To facilitate women's access to finance and to promote investments in women's innovative businesses a change in risk perception is needed. This can be achieved by providing differentiated customised financial products for women by country type (e.g. Islamic finance) alongside with capacity development within the financial sector regarding green economy business models.

5.7 Recommendations

The results of the analysis suggest that both public policy and public finance play an important role in green finance mobilisation

globally. Estimating empirically green finance investment is complex and data availability is an issue, therefore the focus is on the renewable energy sectors and climate finance. The good news is that there are opportunities to scale up climate finance and shift the pattern of green growth to other sectors.

Two overall recommendations emerge:

First, enhancing the transparency, comprehensiveness, and consistency in accounting approaches of climate and green finance¹³⁶.

Second, designing efficient domestic public policies to increase private finance mobilisation¹³⁷.

Following the measures adopted by France in its law on energy transition for Green Growth and the recommendation to G7 countries¹³⁸, the first action is to encourage governments to produce national decarbonization strategies for their economies and their financing through both public and private funding. Among the key indicators for such strategies could be the relative volume of 'green' investments compared with total global investments made each year, combined with annual targets.

Countries such as Tunisia¹³⁹ or Spain¹⁴⁰ have been able to develop mechanisms to attract commercial capital into renewable energy investment by coherently addressing the relevant barriers, both technical and financial. However, the lack of a long-term approach, often readjusting policies and incentives to the detriment of investors' trust, can quickly erase benefits achieved as can be seen in the example of Spain.

In developing countries, investments in large-scale renewable energy are mostly driven by international finance and development institutions. The domestic legal, structural and economic frameworks are often too weak to allow the emergence of domestically financed market-based renewable energy development. Increasingly, financial policymakers and regulators should explore their role in enabling an orderly transition to a prosperous low-carbon economy¹⁴¹.

136 CPI (2015). Global Landscape of Climate Finance 2015 <http://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Global-Landscape-of-Climate-Finance-2015.pdf>

137 Haščič, I. et al. (2015), "Public Interventions and Private Climate Finance Flows: Empirical Evidence from Renewable Energy Financing", OECD Environment Working Papers, No. 80, OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5js6b1r9lfd4-en>

138 Report of The Canfin-Grandjean Commission (2015). Mobilizing Climate Finance A Roadmap to Finance a Low-Carbon Economy, page 22

139 GIZ. Financing Green Growth. A review of green financial sector policies in emerging and developing economies

140 Robinson D., Oxford Energy Institute (2013). Pulling the plug on renewable power in Spain.

141 The Inquiry and The 2^o Investing Initiative (2016). Building a Sustainable Financial System in the European Union. The Five 'R's of Market and Policy Innovation for The Green Transition

6

Recommendations and conclusions

This chapter provides proposals, recommendations and guidelines to policy makers and civil society actors to accelerate the development of Green Economy at national and regional level. They are based on the findings of the country assessments and the survey results as well as the outcomes of the expert workshop that took place in Tangier in July 2016.

6.1 Design ambitious, coherent and consistent national strategies

6.1.1 Align and mainstream Green Economy/Sustainable Development concepts

Findings

Both traditional and new/emerging concepts and terms linked with sustainability (like green economy, circular economy, SCP, etc.) are often not well understood and also interpreted differently among countries. For example, various countries use the term 'sustainable development' when they actually mean 'sustained economic growth' regardless if it is environmentally friendly or not. Also perceptions and longstanding assumptions, such as the trickle-down effect, may lead to these different interpretations of concepts. The popular understanding of sustainable development views society, environment and economy as three separated but connected and equally important spheres. However, the economy is frequently given priority leading inevitably to trade-offs, for instance by accepting increased pollution to allow for an increase of traditionally conceived economic growth.

Recommendations

Country policies and strategies have to express more clearly their interpretation of Sustainable Development and Green Economy concepts, based on recognized international standards, international agreements and scientific literature. As described in Chapter 1, the core principles of social equity, community ownership and ecological limits, should form the basis to build national Green Economies. Additionally, the Mediterranean countries must put emphasis on sustainable *coastal* and *marine* related sectors and activities such as Tourism and Fisheries, or Building and Transport in view of foreseen coastal population increase, etc.

6.1.2 Clearly formulate objectives, actions and indicators

Findings

The large majority of the countries have out-dated or incomplete national GE/SD strategies, often they are vague by not providing measurable objectives or setting indicators to monitor implementation progress. Only five countries (France, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Tunisia) have up-to-date and detailed strategies with clear targets, or – in the case of Italy – supporting legislation in place. The survey shows also that, overall, national strategies are perceived as weak. Badly designed strategies are unfortunately not useful to guide countries through the complex path of change towards sustainability. On the contrary, they dilute interest, increase misunderstandings and weaken the much needed trust of authorities, experts, investors and other stakeholders.

Recommendations

It is important that the countries improve their national strategies through participatory consultations to have a common vision, specific objectives and well defined course of action and commitments regarding GE and SD. All countries should have clearly formulated (on a consensus basis) targets, actions and indicators in order to monitor the progress of implementation, through (bi)annual reviews and open data sharing processes easily accessible and understandable by stakeholders and citizens.

6.1.3 Integrate new international commitments

Findings

In the last months several major international initiatives addressing GE/SD issues have been adopted at global and regional level. The revised Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) 2016-2025 was approved in early 2016 by all Mediterranean countries with specific goals and actions on green and blue economy. More globally, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) shape common objectives for all developed and developing countries through green and inclusive economy. Finally, the Paris Agreement on Climate Change reinforces mitigation and adaptation actions especially in the energy sector while providing a robust framework on climate finance. These agreements provide targets, measures, tools and indicators on cross-cutting issues related to sustainability, such as, among others, health, education, environment, climate change, social cohesion, etc.

Recommendations

All countries should review and update their strategies and policies in light of these new international commitments. Objectives, actions and indicators linked to the SDGs, the MSSD (2016-2025) and Climate Change commitments should be integrated into national sustainability strategies. For the majority of countries this would mean to set more ambitious and concrete targets which have to be meticulously tracked with consistent and coherent monitoring processes, together with supporting finance and implementation mechanisms.

6.2 Improve awareness, commitment and involvement

6.2.1 Raise awareness about national and regional sustainability strategies

Findings

It is not surprising that respondents to the survey have contradicting views on the national strategies of their country. Various countries that have Green Economy or Sustainable Development strategies are often not only outdated but are also insufficiently communicated. Often it is difficult to know to which extent they are still valid, when they will be updated and how the revision process will be managed. Unfortunately, even a very well designed strategy will not have real impact if it is not known, understood and endorsed by relevant stakeholders and actors. The same applies to the MSSD (2016-2025) at regional level, which is very little known beyond a small circle of regional environmental actors.

Recommendations

Countries need to put more effort in communicating and disseminating national GE/SD strategies to all relevant stakeholders, including economic actors and opinion leaders. Targeted awareness campaigns showing the benefits of GE and SD will help to engage citizens. On a regular basis, the outcomes of the strategy – both positive and negative - should be widely shared to enhance transparency and accountability. By doing so, countries will enter in a virtuous circle to improve the quality, attractiveness and inclusiveness of the strategy and its associate policies. Similarly, the communication strategy of the MSSD 2016-2015 needs to be considerably strengthened.

6.2.2 Strengthen the engagement and commitment of relevant stakeholders

Findings

With few exceptions, stakeholder involvement in the formulation of national strategies is unfortunately rather low and many countries do not have clear consultation and participation mechanisms in place. In addition, the survey clearly showed that the level of commitment of most stakeholders, especially the ones in government/public administration, business and finance, is perceived as low, or moderate at best. To be relevant and effective, Green Economy or Sustainable Development strategies should be conceived and implemented through community and stakeholder involvement. The proposed Green Economy model (Chapter 1) requires strong bottom-up dialogue processes and participatory policy design, implementation and monitoring.

Recommendations

Well designed stakeholder consultations should be undertaken during the revision/elaboration, implementation and monitoring of national, sectorial or local Green Economy and Sustainable Development strategies. When necessary, technical and financial support - through capacity building, operational grants, etc. - might also be provided to ensure real and constructive contributions from civil society organizations, in particular from distant or marginalised groups that might have difficulties to participate in such processes. Civil society plays here a constructive 'watchdog' role in counterbalancing the vested interests of powerful industrial or other lobbies, political wrong-doing and corruption. Addressing these challenges early, even if difficult, pave the way for smoother progress in the medium and long term.

6.2.3 Promote Green Economy/Sustainable Development initiatives led by local stakeholders

Findings

As resulting from the survey and the review of regional GE/SD initiatives, a large number of green projects are designed, promoted and implemented by local or sector specific actors (entrepreneurs, NGOs, farmers, ...) without necessarily being linked to a formal national strategy on GE or SD. These actions are usually cost-effective, inclusive, accepted by and beneficial to the local communities. They have to be identified and integrated into the national reporting process and promoted as successful stories to learn from.

Recommendations

Local, national and regional (Mediterranean) institutions should promote actions, tools and mechanisms (through the web, handbooks, networking or capacity building activities, etc.) to identify, assess and disseminate successful local or sector specific GE/SD initiatives. They should also provide technical and financial support to scale-up and extend their impact to other geographical or sectorial areas.

6.3 Phase out Brown Economy, mainstream Green Finance and enhance Green Economy implementation

6.3.1 Phase out 'brown' incentives and initiatives

Findings

According to the survey results and the Green Finance chapter, a number of environmentally harmful infrastructures, policies and initiatives, either underway or in planning, are still supported by governments and financial institutions. In particular, fossil fuel subsidies (almost all countries), exploration for gas and oil (Spain, Israel and Cyprus), coal plants development (Albania), nuclear energy (Egypt), unnecessary highway construction, uncontrolled urban sprawl and tourism development, are all sending a wrong signal to the market and decision-makers.

Recommendations

Financing of Brown Economy, in particular through (hidden) subsidies, has to be phased out as soon as possible, following the OECD¹⁴² and G7/G20¹⁴³ commitments. Projects that go directly against environmental and social sustainability and serve only short-term and non-equitable benefits, have to be stopped to avoid wasting precious natural and financial resources and send the right messages to the market and decision-makers.

142 <http://www.oecd.org/environment/support-to-fossil-fuels-remains-high-and-the-time-is-ripe-for-change.htm>

143 <http://www.mofa.go.jp/files/000160266.pdf>

6.3.2 Catalyse and mainstream Green Finance

Findings

As deduced from the survey results and the UNEP financial inquiry report, the financing sector does not sufficiently support the transition towards a Green Economy in the Mediterranean region. Only a minor part of the total financial portfolio of public and private institutions is targeting green initiatives (as reviewed in the chapter on Green Finance). Additionally, the willingness and expertise to effectively support innovative GE/SD projects is often lacking. Without a strong and effective commitment of international and national financial institutions, no real change will happen on the ground at the required scale and speed.

Recommendations

Public funding of Green Economy has to be scaled up, both at local, national and regional level, e.g. through the launch of green public banks as they exist in the UK, Greece and France. Such institutions should focus exclusively on supporting sustainable and responsible investments, in particular for households (energy efficiency), R&D (cleantech) and SMEs (green businesses). A Green Mediterranean Financial Initiative funded by a large Green Bonds programme could also be launched to provide access to finance for green initiatives and infrastructures. The tax system should also be reviewed to tax environmentally damaging activities and reinvest in poor and marginalized communities and areas.

6.3.3 Pursue regional cooperation and peer learning

Findings

Although many GE/SD activities concern a specific sector or geographical area, there are a number of issues where multi-sectorial and transnational cooperation makes sense because it allows the sharing of (positive and negative) experiences and leads to quicker results. This can be in the area of education and training (development of courses with similar content on GE topics such as renewables, Waste, etc.), innovation and the development of green(er) industries at a region-wide level, for instance through regionally common industry standards which enhance the market for suppliers of green products and services.

Recommendations

International cooperation in GE areas should be further strengthened. International organisations such as UNEP/MAP and its RACs, the UfM Secretariat or OECD; or regional initiatives such as the Mediterranean Commission for Sustainable Development, the Horizon 2020 Initiative for a Cleaner Mediterranean, etc. can assist countries in these efforts and further nurture regional dialogue and progress on Green Economy and Sustainable Development. Countries can learn from each other through experience sharing, benchmarking and regional cooperation. Peer exchanges and learning mechanisms between national and international stakeholders as well as among national peers are strongly encouraged.

6.4 Conclusions

Overall it can be stated that all Mediterranean countries still have a long way to go to mainstream green and sustainable development principles into their economies. While some countries have well defined Green Economy/Sustainable Development strategies (such as France, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Tunisia), they still lack concrete implementation mechanisms, stakeholders' commitment and systematic follow-up and evaluation. Several countries have not yet developed/published relevant national policies that sufficiently take into account Green Economy, the SDGs or other sustainable development elements and commitments (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Cyprus, Egypt, Palestine, Slovenia, Spain).

Of course, dedicating scarce human and financial resources to design such long term strategies may be viewed as disconnected from priorities and realities on the ground that include addressing high unemployment rate, extreme poverty, human rights infringements, high rates of population growth, armed conflicts and terrorism, or corruption. Yet, embracing Green Economy and Sustainable Development is perhaps the only option at hand that could promise a more secure, equitable and prosperous Mediterranean region in the decades to come.

In the case of Libya and Syria (the two countries that could not be included in this review), should their forthcoming reconstruction process include the development of an ambitious, consistent and participative national strategy on Green Economy and/or Sustainable Development, a meaningful and promising contribution to an inclusive, resilient and more likely to be sustained rebuilding effort could be boasted.

Given the historical consistency of the Mediterranean in being on the one hand a region of convergence but on the other of frequent conflict, developing and implementing robust long-term Green Economy/Sustainable Development strategies could strengthen the resilience of the region as a whole, the countries individually and of their communities, in resisting or better adapting to external and internal shocks that tend to negatively impact the region.

7 References

Note: We apologize that due to time constraints we do not list all references in a formally correct way.

7.1 References for the Chapter on GE concepts

General

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 OECD External Development Finance Statistics database: <http://www.oecd.org/dac/stats/climate-change.htm>
 OECD work on green finance (Green investment banks, green bonds, inventory of climate funds...): <http://www.oecd.org/env/cc/financing.htm>
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SDGs

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SCP

<http://www.unido.org/en/what-we-do/environment/resource-efficient-and-low-carbon-industrial-production/cp/cleaner-production.html>
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http://www.unep.org/10yfp/Portals/50150/downloads/publications/ABC/ABC_ENGLISH.pdf
http://www.unep.org/10yfp/Portals/50150/downloads/publications/Paving_the_way/Paving_the_way_final.pdf
http://www.unep.org/10yfp/Portals/50150/downloads/publications/Global_Outlook/Global%20Outlook%20on%20SCP%20Policies%20FULL.pdf

Resource efficiency

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Ministry website: Ministry of environment, forestry and water administration

<http://www.adaptation-undp.org/partners/ministry-environment-forestry-and-water-administration-albania>

Local language website includes more resources: <http://www.mjedisi.gov.al/>

Indicators:

Green Growth Platform, <http://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/country/albania>

European Environment Agency, <http://www.eea.europa.eu/soer-2015/countries/albania>

Other resources:

«A new path for the sustainable development: a green economy for Albania», <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/1014albanianationalreport.pdf>

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7.2.2 Algeria

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Indicators:

<http://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/country/algeria>

Other resources:

Article de Abdelatif Kerzabi est Maître de conférences à la Faculté de gestion et des Sciences économiques de l'Université de Tlemcen en Algérie. <http://www.cairn.info/revue-marche-et-organisations-2009-1-page-61.htm>

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(Footnotes)

83. For most Mediterranean countries no data on electricity access is given as most of them do have access. The 7 countries (Jordan, Lebanon, Israel, Egypt, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco) have values which range between 98,9 and 99,9%, so electricity access is largely given and therefore not further considered.
84. Only Algeria and Egypt have fossil fuel subsidies according to and as defined by GGKP ("The subsidies to fossil fuel consumption cover fossil fuels directly consumed by end-users or consumed as inputs to electricity generation"), therefore this indicator is not further considered. It should be noted that most countries do have fossil fuel subsidies if they are defined in a wider sense, see e.g. the OECD fossil fuel support data base, <http://www.oecd.org/site/tadffss/data/>
85. We were informed that some GGKP indicators are outdated. For reasons of consistency and time constraints we did not collect data from different sources. More recent data may be found at <http://www.capmas.gov.eg/>
86. <http://www.greenstarhotel.org/>, accessed 29 July 2016.

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